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Thematic Contents of Preschool-Aged Children's Utterances as Media to Shape Their Understanding of the World

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Abstract

Language ability develops greatly during preschool age. Triggered by the high curiosity that goes hand in hand with the exposures to others around them, preschool-aged children show great efforts in creating a collection of vocabulary to help them learn and use language in real contexts. This research aims to identify the thematic contents of preschool-aged children's utterances and explain the categories of these thematic contents to shape their understanding of the surrounding world. To answer these objectives, both qualitative and quantitative data were used. The qualitative data were the utterances of preschool-aged children when participating in conversations, while the quantitative data were the frequency of occurrence of each thematic content, which is used to support the qualitative interpretation. The data were collected during classroom sessions in two preschools in Yogyakarta, Indonesia for a one-week period. The participants were 29 preschool-aged children, whose age ranges from 3 to 5. Audiovisual recordings, field notes, datasheets, and ELAN 5.5. and FLEx 8 software were the instruments for data collection and analysis. The results show that there are two main thematic contents expressed by these preschool-aged children, i.e., objects and people. These thematic contents can be detailed into 9 categories of objects and 4 categories of people. These support the overall interpretation revealing the picture of the world as perceived by the children. In general, through the thematic contents of their utterances, preschool-aged children try to build a complete understanding of the world they live in and these thematic contents also serve as the media for understanding the stance of their peers and teachers in a conversation.

Keywords: preschool-aged children; thematic contents; utterances

INTRODUCTION

Preschool age is marked with some vast development in terms of language ability. The discussion on preschool-aged children, especially regarding their language ability, has been of increasing attention especially among those in psychology, early childhood education, and linguistics. In psychology, some studies of preschool-aged children's language focus on preschool-aged children's language skills and behavior problems (Davis & Qi, 2020; Goldstein & Naglieri, 2011; Martins et al., 2016), how emotion affects preschool-aged children's language (Alcock, 2016; Martins et al., 2016) and the relationship between preschool-aged children's socio-cultural backgrounds with their language skills (Becker et al., 2013; Dolores et al., 2013; Kontopodis et al., 2011). Meanwhile, the discipline of early childhood education mainly investigates the educational aspects of preschool-aged children's language, such as how to deal with preschool-aged children in classroom settings (Dalgren, 2017; Geary & Berch, 2016; Hornby, 2011; McCabe et al., 2000) and how the curriculum accommodates preschool-aged children's language development (Dickinson & Porche, 2011; Dwyer & Harbaugh, 2018; Justice et al., 2011). In linguistics, the discussions are quite more various, from language development in general (Becker et al., 2013; Fiano, 2014), to the structural and pragmatic aspects of the development (Carmiol & Vinden, 2013; D. K. Oller et al., 2013; Sorsana et al., 2013; Wasik & Iannone-Campbell, 2013).

In terms of their language ability, preschool-aged children start to develop a higher ability in producing utterances, using syntactically more complex constructions and moving closer to that of adults. Some previous studies found that preschool-aged children master up to 1,000 vocabulary items and use around 12,000 words per day (Arnett & Maynard, 2013; Davies, 2011; Owens, 2012). These vocabularies are largely acquired through their verbal interactions with people in their environment, including families, caregivers, and peers. These interactions are sources of whatever the children need to learn, as they provide opportunities for them to recognize, internalize, store, and use the words they hear. Nevertheless, in learning the words, preschool-aged children also learn how to correctly use them according to the grammar of the language they are exposed to (Davis-Kean et al., 2016; Tabors et al., 2001; Weisleder & Fernald, 2014). Participating in such interactions, preschool-aged children start to use specific registers and adapt their

voice and intonation according to the role they played in the interactions. This discursive ability is clearly represented in their utterances. For instance, 3-year-old preschool-aged children are good at imitating adults' heavy tones during pretend plays with peers (Ervin-Tripp et al., 2005; Stude, 2014), and 4-year-olds start to have the ability to negotiate roles in pretend plays and differentiate imaginary things from the real ones (Stude, 2014).

In order to provide a comprehensive picture of preschool-aged children's language, an investigation on Mean Length of Utterance (MLU) is seen to be more accurate than using age alone as a variable (Behrens, 2009; Foster-Cohen, 2009; Kupisch et al., 2009; McDaniel, 1996). By doing this, researchers can reveal the complexity of preschool-aged children's language, especially in terms of the vocabularies and grammatical structures of their utterances. Parker & Bronson (2005), for instance, compared Mean Length of Utterance in Morphemes (MLUm) and Mean Length of Utterance in Words (MLUw) and found that MLUw is simpler and easier, yet it yields the same effectiveness in providing a picture of preschool-aged children's language. In addition, MLUw can be applied to a wider range of languages due to the many differences regarding the concept of morphemes in different languages in the world (Kupisch et al., 2009).

Meanwhile, calculating the MLU of preschool-aged children's utterances is not the only way to map their language ability. Some researchers prefer to investigate the richness of preschool-aged children's vocabulary, with emphasis on the elements composing their utterances, such as the lexical content, the subject and predicate, and the themes discussed in an interaction. O'Neill et al. (2009) and Ifantidou (2014) mention that the variety of themes brought by preschool-aged children in their utterances is a clue to their pragmatic competence. Themes change dynamically in preschool-aged children's conversations, enabling relatively short turn-takings and unfinished exchanges of information, representing the here-and-now concept. Therefore, in order to become an active participant in a conversation, preschool-aged children need to actively take turns. However, this task involves a complex communication skill, which requires their sensitivity such as knowing when it is possible for them to take turns and what to do when they get their turns.

In fact, children, in general, cannot acquire these communication skills by themselves. They need some exposures from which they can learn about the skills from their surroundings, either from parents and other family members, caregivers,

other adults (such as teachers in nurseries, daycare centers, and kindergartens) or peers. These people provide some scaffolding for the children through examples in given contexts. As mentioned by Bryant (2009) and Santrock (2011), families, peers, and schools are important for a child's all-aspect development. They build what Bruner (1983) referred to as Language Acquisition Support System (LASS). Each element in this support system goes hand in hand in creating opportunities for children to learn about the language and how to use it. Family is the first and main environment where children learn all about their life and the life of others. Meanwhile, when children began to get along with people out of their families, school environment is important to acknowledge.

In Indonesia, early childhood education institutions are playing more important roles nowadays. More parents put their preschool-aged children under the care of teachers in preschools and kindergartens. As a consequence, there are more opportunities for preschool-aged children to interact with people other than their families, i.e. with both peers and teachers, and therefore, there are more chances that preschool-aged children develop their communication skills in the school environment. Sammons (2010) acknowledges that being involved in preschool interactions is beneficial for preschool-aged children as they can develop their intellectual as well as their social skills and behavior. Especially for those who do not get sufficient exposures from their main environment at home, preschools surely become the medium from which preschool-aged children can learn about being social and gain new experiences and linguistic exposures.

In the context of preschool-aged children in Indonesia, some studies of preschool-aged children's language in preschool settings were already conducted, such as by Iswatiningsih (2016), Prihantoro (2014), Siddiq (2019), and Sukartiningsih (2010). These studies were on the acquisition of *Bahasa Indonesia* as preschool-aged children's first language and the structural and pragmatic dimensions of the acquisition. Although they discuss the structural aspects of the acquisition, the discussion was mainly on the syntactic structure of preschool-aged children's utterances. The thematic contents of the utterances have not gained much attention. Nevertheless, this is an important aspect to discuss within the study of preschool-aged children's language as it is believed that how they build their understanding of the surrounding world can be seen through the way they employ

lexicons and build themes. With regards to this, this research aims to highlight the thematic contents of preschool-aged children's utterances in *Bahasa Indonesia* and the preschool-aged children's world as represented through the thematic contents of their utterances.

RESEARCH METHOD

As the research was mixed-method, both qualitative and quantitative data were used. Preschool-aged children's utterances, when conversing with their peers and teachers, served as the data source. 29 preschool-aged children, ranging from 3 to 5 years old, and 5 teachers from 2 preschools in Yogyakarta, Indonesia became the participants. The instruments were audio-visual recordings and transcripts of the conversations between preschool-aged children and their peers and teachers, fieldnotes, datasheets, and ELAN 5.5. and FieldWorks Language Explorer (FLEX) 8 software, which were employed for data transcription and identification of lexicons' frequency.

Prior to data collection, a pre-research activity of observation was conducted in several preschools in Yogyakarta to determine the research setting. Two preschools were finally selected as the setting due to the fulfilment of some criteria, such as high opportunities of verbal interactions between preschool-aged children and their peers and teachers, the availability of various playthings and learning resources that can be accessed and used by the preschool-aged children, and a smaller number of preschool-aged children under the supervision of a teacher. As this research involved preschool-aged children, in order to fulfill the research ethics, informed consent was distributed to parents prior to any participation of the preschool-aged children in the research, and only the initial of the children's first names were disclosed.

The data were collected by recording the conversations between preschool-aged children and their peers and teachers during classroom sessions. The recordings were done for an hour a day for a week (six days) period, resulting in 11 hours 27 minutes duration of the recording. The next step was transcribing the utterances using ELAN 5.5. When the transcription was completed, the preschool-aged children's utterances were identified, resulting in 4,198 utterances, and examined using FLEX 8 in order to identify the lexicons that reveal the thematic content of their utterances.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The results show that there are 2 main themes shown in the preschool-aged children's utterances, i.e. objects and people. Objects become the main thematic content delivered by preschool-aged children. Seventy five percent of the thematic contents were about objects, which occur 437 times. Meanwhile, the theme of people is the next thematic content, with 147 occurrences (25%). There are 9 categories of objects and 4 categories of people that are discussed by preschool-aged children, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1 shows that preschool-aged children mainly talk about objects when conversing with their peers and teachers in the classroom setting. The discussions on objects are meant to enrich the preschool-aged children's vocabularies and enhance their understanding of the elements existing in their surrounding world, shown by the nouns representing things around these preschool-aged children. Besides objects, preschool-aged children complete their picture of the world by discussing people – both real people in their life and imaginary characters from movies or stories, and the places where they do their activities. All these thematic contents provide a complete description of the world as understood by the preschool-aged children.

Tabel 1.

The Thematic Contents of Preschool-Aged Children's Utterances

No	Thematic Contents	Frequency
1. Objects	Things around at the moment of speaking	83
	Food and drink	77
	Parts of body and accessories	77
	Houses/buildings/public places	61
	Abstract concepts/ideas	43
	Animals	42
	Nature	25
	Vehicles	16
	Occupations/social status	13
	Total	437
2. People	Interlocutors (peers and teachers)	72
	Family	39
	Others	30
	Self-speakers	6
	Total	147
	Total Sub-themes	584

As language develops with age, compared with younger children, preschool-aged children are faced with more complex communicative situations. They sometimes need to participate in multi-participant conversations, which of course requires sophisticated communication skills. In order to participate in such conversations, it is necessary to actively take turns and monitor their understanding of what their interlocutors say. In general, preschool-aged children with more advanced communication skills during interactions with a peer are more likable to befriend. The same kind of acceptance by peers also occurs to ones with rich vocabularies (Owens, 2012). Social cognitive ability, therefore, is one of the earliest important abilities that children need to acquire.

Preschool age is a period during which lexicons and conceptual meanings are greatly developed by children (Owens, 2012). This implicitly signals the possibility of a high variety of thematic contents discussed in conversations, in which they become participants. However, some studies found that these thematic contents are still closely related to the principle of here-and-now, as in earlier age. As mentioned by Dardjowidjojo (2000) and Ninio (2014), topics in conversations with preschool-aged children are relatively fast-changing, with things familiar to them becoming the main ones to discuss.

Due to the dynamic changes in topics, identifying the thematic contents in conversations with preschool-aged children as participants is a complex task. Marvin (1996) and Ifantidou (2011) suggest that the genres or themes discussed by preschool-aged children can be identified by investigating the referents related to time, people, objects, activities, and ideas that are presented in preschool-aged children's utterances. Therefore, the semantic content of the preschool-aged children's utterances can be revealed. As mentioned by Simms (2008) and Rowland (2014), nouns and pronouns are clearly the word classes that can resemble the contents of preschool-aged children's utterances. Thus, in the present study, the identification of thematic contents is based on the investigation of nouns and pronouns in the utterances of 29 preschool-aged children that become the participants in the research, resulting in objects and people as the main thematic contents of their utterances.

Objects as the main thematic content of preschool-aged children's utterances

Various objects are discussed in preschool-aged children's utterances, which are discussed 437 times, which accounts for 74.8%. When discussing objects, preschool-aged children mostly talk about familiar things located at the same place at the moment of speaking. There are 9 categories of objects that are discussed: 1) things around, 2) food and drinks, 3) parts of body and accessories, 4) houses/buildings, 5) abstract concepts/ideas, 6) animals, 7) nature, 8) vehicles, and 9) occupation/social status. Table 2 presents some examples of how these thematic contents are presented in preschool-aged children's utterances.

Table 2 shows the categories of objects discussed by preschool-aged children. The main objects to discuss are things that are around them and familiar to them, comprising technology-related items, household things, valuables, stationery, playthings, and unspecified things in a near location which are usually referred to using demonstrative pronouns. In addition, preschool-aged children already have some awareness regarding valuables such as money and gold. Although these nouns only exist in the context of pretend play, it is clear that preschool-aged children have developed a certain level of understanding that some things have more value than others and can be used to buy other things.

Table 2.

The thematic content of objects in preschool-aged children's utterances

No	Object Category	Examples
1	Things around at the moment of speaking	Technology-related items, household things, valuables, stationery, playthings, unspecified things in a near location
2	Food and drinks	Spices, vegetables, fruits, drinks, fast food, cakes, and cooking activities
3	Parts of body and accessories	Parts of body, jewelry, outfit, cosmetics/medicine
4	Houses / buildings / places	Parts of a house, public places, commercial places
5	Abstract concepts / ideas	Temporal concepts, colors, possession, faith
6	Animals	Real animals, animals in fantasy/stories, animals in rituals
7	Nature	Plants, sky objects, natural phenomena, geographical location
8	Vehicles	Kinds of vehicles, parts of vehicles
9	Occupation/social status	Kinds of occupation, social status

Meanwhile, although all utterances in the research data are produced in a classroom context, there are not many discussions on stationery and other writing utensils. The same case also occurs when the preschool-aged children are in the playground. There are not many play things that become parts of the discussion. Instead, the preschool-aged children talk about the activity they do with their peers there. This finding implies that preschool-aged children tend to have an interest to discuss the detail of their actions rather than discussing the tools they use to do the activities. It is interesting to note that when discussing the activities, demonstrative pronouns are often used to point to objects that are not familiar to preschool-aged children, either because they do not know the name of the objects or because they have not seen them yet, to point to familiar-but-forgotten objects, and to point to several objects without specifying any of them.

The next category of object discussed in conversations involving preschool-aged children as participants is food and drinks. When talking about food and drinks, all aspects in this regard are discussed, from the raw ingredients for making food and drinks, the activities of cooking, to the ready-to-eat one. The preschool-aged children talk about them by describing their appearance, characteristics, taste, what to do with them, benefits of consuming them, and just sharing their experience regarding the food and drink discussed.

Comparing the two preschools that become the research setting, it is seen that the discussion about food and drinks occurs only in one preschool, but not in the other. This is due to the difference in classroom arrangement between the two schools. One of the preschools divides its classrooms based on the functions of the rooms, such as Preparation, Role-play, and Nature. The discussions on food and drinks occur in the Role-play room, where the room is set like rooms at home: a living room, kitchen, bathroom, etc. Although when role-playing preschool-aged children have the freedom to talk about anything they like, as the activity and playthings are set exactly like in a real home, the discussion is usually around home activities, such as eating behaviors in the dining room. The availability of thematic playthings in each classroom serves as a means that teachers can use to scaffold their students' activities in the class.

Meanwhile, other objects discussed by preschool-aged children in their interactions with peers and teachers are houses, buildings, and places, which can be detailed into parts of a house, public places, and commercial places. When discussing their houses, preschool-aged children tend to use the common noun *rumah* 'house' and other rooms such as *tempat bikin roti* 'a place for baking cakes' or 'kitchen' and *meja makan* 'dining table.' In addition, there are also some other buildings to discuss, such as *penjara* 'jail' and *kuburan* 'cemetery,' which are found in the context of pretend plays, *masjid* 'mosque,' and minimarket, as a location where one of the preschool-aged children bought his food.

Besides discussing real objects, preschool-aged children also develop their ability to regard abstract objects or ideas. This thematic content is discussed more frequently than that of animals. Several abstract concepts are discussed by preschool-aged children in the two preschools: temporal concepts, colors, possession, and concepts related to faith and rituals. In terms of temporal concepts, preschool-aged children have developed their understanding of day (name of days and 24-hours duration as a day) and time during the day (morning, noon, and evening). In addition, they also understand the differences among colors, although they are still confused about differentiating color gradation. In relation to possession, preschool-aged children understand that some Indonesian suffixes signal possession, such as the suffix *-ku* 'my', *-mu* 'your', and *-nya* 'his/her/its'. Meanwhile, preschool-aged children also develop their understanding of faith and other religious/cultural rituals through the learning processes. When teachers explain a topic about nature, for instance, they can provide scaffolding to their students by asking them to answer questions about things that God has created and some religious values about this. Through such scaffolding, preschool-aged children are encouraged to explore and share their experiences with their peers. Therefore, the knowledge becomes shared knowledge. To understand these abstract concepts/ideas, preschool-aged children need to show stronger efforts compared to that understanding concrete objects as their memory is still developing and has not been at its maximum capacity. Besides, processing abstract concepts and their

representations are much more complicated than understanding concrete objects that can be seen and touched (Schneider, 2015; Viau et al., 2010).

The next object to discuss by preschool-aged children in their interactions with peers and teachers is animals. Three categories of animals are discussed: 1) sea, land, and air animals, 2) animals in fantasy/stories, and 3) animals in rituals. When talking about animals, preschool-aged children mostly talk about animals that are familiar to them and often seen in daily life, such as fish and cows. However, the discussion of fantasy animals, such as dinosaurs and dragons, is also present, as these toy animals are available in the classroom or brought by the preschool-aged children from home. Discussing them, preschool-aged children compare and share their understanding regarding the physical appearance and characters of these animals as what they saw in movies or read in stories. The last category is animals that are related to a ritual, whether it is a religious ritual or a cultural one. For instance, when sharing about their experience attending the Eid-al-Adha celebration, these preschool-aged children also discuss the common sacrificial animals in the celebration, such as cows and camels.

In addition, there are also some discussions on objects that are related to nature, such as plants, celestial bodies, natural phenomena, and geographical conditions. Plants that become a sub-theme in the speech of preschool-aged children are plants that are around them, either at home or at school or in other places they have visited, as well as those related to their playing activities. For example, when asked to describe the situation around her house, B told her friends about the guava tree in her house, and while playing, she said that the dinosaurs' diet was grass. Meanwhile, the sub-theme about celestial bodies appeared in the conversations of preschool-aged children when they were learning about God's creation. Another example was produced by L when she saw M carrying a pair of binoculars. Because she has experience and knowledge about the object, she can tell the function of the object.

In addition, there are 2 natural phenomena that are also told in the stories of preschool-aged children, namely earthquakes and rain. The earthquake was told by A as part of God's creation, which at that time became the theme of the lesson. A received exposure to this earthquake from TV, as

he agreed when asked by the teacher about where he got to know about earthquakes. Experience, either directly or indirectly, is a source of language exposure in early childhood. For instance, when the teacher was conveying the importance of maintaining cleanliness in order to have a healthy body, P suddenly shouted that he had just played in the rain. C responded to this statement, stating that P could have a cold as a result of playing in the rain.

The last object category whose frequency of occurrence as a sub-theme in the speech of preschool-aged children is very minor is vehicles, whether land, sea, and air vehicles or their parts, as well as occupations or status. When talking about vehicles, most of them only mention names, for example, *kereta bandara* 'airport train' and *mobil polisi* 'police car', while parts of vehicles and other things related to vehicles are not discussed too much, for example, *helm* 'helmet' and *setir* 'steering wheel.' This sub-theme about vehicles often appears in context when talking about work. For example, in a pretend play to catch criminals, words related to these activities appear, such as *mobil polisi* 'police car', *penjara* 'jail', and work as a *polisi* 'policeman'. Several other jobs that are also found in the speech of preschool-aged children include the work that is being played by the child, such as *penjual es krim* 'ice cream seller' and what he aspires to be, such as *dokter* 'doctor'. Apart from work, the status during pretend plays is also discussed, such as *pangeran* 'prince'. This is also the case with the status attached to someone or something that is known to the child, for example, the status of *juara* 'champion'.

People as the second thematic content of preschool-aged children's utterances

The theme of people also gets sufficient attention in the speech of preschool-aged children, as evidenced by the high frequency of occurrence (147 times or 25.2%) in the speech produced by these children. There are several categories of people being discussed, namely peers and teachers (72), family (39), self-speakers (6), and others (30).

Table 3.

The thematic content of objects in preschool-aged children's utterances

No	People category	Examples
1	Interlocutors (peers and teachers)	Second personal pronouns, 'friends', the address term 'Ma'am'
2	Family	'Father', 'mother', 'grandparents', 'uncle and aunty', 'brother', 'sister'
3	Self-speakers	First personal pronouns, own name
4	Others	Movie characters, ghosts

In discussing the interlocutor, be it peers or teachers, mentioning the name of the speech partner is the most important thing to use. Next is the mention using the noun *teman-teman* 'friends', pronouns for people, for example *kalian* 'you', *kamu* 'you', and *dirimu* 'yourself' to mention peers, and the address term *bu* 'Ma'am' to refer to teachers. As all the teachers are females, it is reasonable that the word *bu* becomes the most frequently used noun by preschoolers, which is used 540 times in 4198 utterances. The role of the teacher in interaction in the classroom with preschool-aged children is indeed quite central, where the teacher is usually the most active party in learning activities in the classroom. Although the pattern of learning carried out is slightly different because it is center based, in the second preschool, the teacher's role in learning activities is also quite basic. Although in the main activity the teacher does not constantly intervene in the activities executed by the children, she still monitors the course of activities and immediately provides feedback if the activities carried out have started to get out of control.

Meanwhile, there are quite a number of family members who become sub-themes in the speech of preschool-aged children, especially members of the nuclear family, namely *ayah* 'father', *ibu* 'mother', *adik perempuan* 'sister', and *kakak laki-laki* 'brother'. In addition, other family members who were also discussed were *kakek-nenek* 'grandparents' and *pakde-bude* 'uncle and aunty'. All of these family members appear as sub-themes in the speech of preschool-aged children, both when the children tell their real experiences and when they are playing roles. Meanwhile, when these preschool-aged children talked about themselves, they mostly used the word *aku* 'I', followed

by *saya* 'I', and their names. Of the 29 preschool-aged children who participated in this study, only 3 always used their names to refer to themselves.

In addition to the three sub-themes above, there are also several other people or personas that become sub-themes in the speech of preschool-aged children, and are classified into others since each of them occurs with little frequency. Most of them are characters in stories or movies, such as 'zombies', *setan* 'devils', and *Upin dan Ipin* 'Upin and Ipin', and general nouns such as *orang* 'person', *bayi* 'baby', and *perempuan* 'woman'.

To sum up, it is clearly visible that preschool-aged children already have the ability to participate actively in conversations with their peers and teachers in the preschool setting. They show their cooperation with their interlocutors in building and managing conversational themes. This way, they also complete their understanding of the world they live in, which is captured from the way they use nouns and pronouns in their utterances to refer to objects and people in real life.

CONCLUSION

Preschool-aged children mostly talk about themes related to the here-and-now principle as well as fictional stories wrapped in pretend play activities when interacting with peers and teachers, with objects dominating the children's conversations, followed by the theme of people. It is interesting to note that family is also discussed even though the setting of all conversations was at preschools. The high use of the types of words with reference (nouns and pronouns) in preschool-aged children's utterances indicates that the semantic content in the form of themes represented through these nouns and pronouns is an important part that contributes to the success of conveying the meaning of speech produced by these children. They help the children to build a complete picture of their surrounding world.

Studies on preschool-aged children's language are important to conduct as they can provide significant contributions to many parties, such as parents, educators, other researchers, and education policymakers. However, in this study, observations were only made on the utterances of preschool-aged

children in two preschools, so the results cannot be used as generalizations in the wider context. Therefore, it is recommended that further researchers conduct similar research in a wider scope and involve more participants.

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Stance Expressions in Introduction of English Research Articles written by Cambodian Authors

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Abstract

Stance Expression indicates feelings, certainty or uncertainty, and interests of the authors. As the increasing needs of the readers on significant findings from the introduction section of research articles, a study on Stance Expression of introduction section in the English research articles written by Cambodian authors has been conducted to employ crucial aims of the study: (1) examine stance expression types and the categories of each type; (2) compare the similarities and differences of stance expression types used in the introduction section of English RAs written by Cambodian authors published in local and international journals. Thirty research articles written by Cambodian authors published in local and international journals were used in this study. To fulfill these research objectives, the mixed-method research design was utilized in this study. All the four stance features, such as Hedges, Boosters, Attitude Markers, and Self-expression, proposed by Hyland (2005), were used as a lexical analysis framework model in this study. The results revealed that four stance expression types were found in this study. The hedge was the most frequently employed among the other types of stances. There is a significantly different in terms of the frequencies of hedge used within both RA journals, but there is no for booster, attitude marker, and self-mention. Local Cambodian authors should follow the international authors as models in applying stance in their RAs. A comparison study of the stance expression and engagement between Cambodian and international authors in the introduction should be expanded more different articles from available journals.

Keywords: english research article, introduction section, stance expression, local journals, international journals

INTRODUCTION

Stance expressions in written articles are very significant for extinguishing the quality of the research thesis and written articles. Stance illustrates the feelings, uncertainty, certainty, and interests of the writers which is a significant area of writing consideration. Also, the writer's way of writing can be similar or different in their English research article writing like in the introduction section. Accordingly, many international researchers studied the use of stance within research articles, theses, or dissertations in applied linguistics and science or other fields such as Miasari et al. (2018)- studied authorial stance in research article introductions in the field of science written by Indonesian authors, who found that the four types of authorial stances in this field of science (Biology, Physics, and Chemistry) like hedges: verb, adjective, adverb, noun and modal; booster: verb, adjective, adverb, Modal and Noun, yet among these subcategories adverbs were the most commonly found. While attitudinal markers were highly counted in Adjectives, and self-mention, last, subjective pronouns were often accounted for self-mention. Wu and Paltridge (2021) studied the stance expression in academic writing in Chinese students' MA dissertations and doctoral PhD theses; the results showed that all four types of stance expression were found in both degrees, but the highest frequency used was hedges while the attitude markers were the lowest rate. PhD students utilized fewer boosters and presented a broader set of attitude markers within their writing, which showed PhD students have increased their abilities in declaring a position. In the same vein, Lancaster (2016) conducted stance use in undergraduate writing between the Econ students and the PolTh writer; hedges, disclaim markers, boosters, and self-mentions were significantly greater frequently used than the PolTh writers. The significantly greater frequency was attitude markers applied. However, none of the studies on the use of stance features were done in articles and none of the categories of each stance expression type on RA introduction written by Cambodian authors were found, such as hedge, booster, attitude markers, and self-mention. Thus, there is also no study about the comparison of the similarities and differences of stance expression types used by Cambodian authors in Language Education in their article introductions published in local and international journals. More importantly, it is a rare case to find written research articles by Cambodian authors regarding stance analysis in writing.

Therefore, there is no study of a comparison of the similarities and differences between the two groups of articles. This study is important because it can help article

writers in applying stance expression in the correct way and forms within their RAs writing, especially in showing their certainty of claiming the truth of information to persuade the readers with the real objective of the study. Thus, it also gives international readers more different information about the quality of local and international research articles written by Cambodian authors in using stance expression in their writing. This provides them with more concepts in comparing the quality of local and internal research in terms of stance expression use. Through these gaps, this study aims to identify the stance expression types used in the introduction of research articles (IoRAs) in language education fields and find out the similarities and differences between the two groups of English research articles written by the Cambodian authors. This research aimed to answer the following questions:

- 1) What stance expression types and categories are used by Cambodian authors in their introduction of research papers in language education published in local and international journals? and
- 2) What are the similarities and differences of stance expression types and categories used by Cambodian authors in Language Education in their article introductions published in local and international journals?

RESEARCH METHOD

This study was designed following Creswell (2012) as both qualitative and quantitative methods. It was built on corpus-based descriptive qualitative and quantitative research methods on the use of stance expressions in the introduction of English research articles written by Cambodian authors published in local and international journals. The qualitative analysis was conducted to present the examples of each research question and objectives by analyzing stance expression in the sample text and the quantitative analysis was focused to calculate the frequency and percentage of stance expression types and sub-categories of each stance type. The researcher used the lexical analysis framework model of the four stance features analysis of Hyland (2005) as the research design. The model of stance expressions focused on Hedges, Boosters, Attitude Markers, and Self-mention in the introduction section of each English research article.

The corpus of the study

This study involved thirty articles from local and international journals in the field of language education written by Cambodian authors. Convenience sampling was utilized as a sampling method for selecting the 30 articles in this corpus. The corpus of this study contained thirty English research articles focused on only the introduction section.

Table 1.

Distribution of the Articles in the Study.

No	Sources of Research Articles	Code	Number of Articles Discussion	Average Length of the Introduction in word count
1	Local Journals	LoJ	15 (50%)	604.6
2	International Journals	InJ	15 (50%)	754.2
Total		30 (100%)		

Table 1 shows that the research articles (RAs) in the field of Language education have the most words on average with 604.6 found as written words in the RAs introduction section written by Cambodian authors published in a local journal, Cambodia, while the average of word counts with 754.2 was found as the written word in the introduction section of research articles written by Cambodian author published in international journals. The articles were selected from two types of journals including Local Journals and International Journals, regarding several considerations as the following: 1) RAs are written in English by Cambodian authors; 2) RAs are in the language education field; 3) RAs have published from 2006 to 2021; 4) the papers are open-access, freely read and downloaded for who needs it; and, RAs are indexed by SCOPUS, ERIC, ESCI, EBSCO, MAS, SCImago, Open J-Gate, CrossRef, Google Scholar, Sinta2, DOAL, EBSCOhost, ajournalSeek, ERA, ARC, OPenDOAR, Springer, Sage, CLaSIC, and ROAR; The RAs published in local journals are under the controlled of the university only.

There was no limitation of sample size in the qualitative research study. According to Baker and Edwards (2012), the participant numbers needed to ensure a sufficient sample for a project can be varied from one up to more than a hundred. As, qualitative research studies are mostly run with small samples (Sandelowski, 1995) as well as making 10 research samples is quite usual (Lichtman, 2010, as cited in Sandelowski, 1995). Otherwise, Adler and Adler (2012), students should orientate a small sample size from 6 to 12 or whatever they catch (cited in Mocănașu, 2020). As an example, a study of the authorial stances in English RA introductions written by

Indonesia authors within the science field such as Biology, Physics, and Chemistry, by Miasari et al. (2019) also included only 30 articles in their study.

The Procedure of Data Analysis

The data was analyzed by marking stance expression of the four features model: hedges, booster, attitudinal markers, and self-mention, within frequency and percentage of each category: adjective, adverb, verb, modal, noun, subject pronoun, common nouns, possessive adjectives, and objective pronoun. Furthermore, the procedures of data analysis were regarded as the following. Thirty English research articles were downloaded from different Cambodian local journals focusing on language education as mentioned above. The introduction of each article in the corpus of this study was read to get a thorough understanding of the content in the text and the 30 articles were converted into file text to fit the AntConc Software program; The text was reread to pinpoint the stances use of the text within the introduction, and each device of the stance features used in the introduction of RAs was counted through AntConc (v.3.5.8, 2021). To certify the reliability of this study, the researcher invited an experienced teacher of the second language, who taught second-language writing and majoring in the English language to be a second-rater. Comparing both data from co-rater and researcher results after the following the frequency and percentage of stance. Last, the interpretation of the data was described based on the identical features shown in the table/figure of the statistical research framework.

The Reliability of Analysis Results

An independent co-rater was a lecturer from the English department of the Institution of Foreign Languages. Then the independent co-rater was trained for a week to identify or code the RA's introduction based on the types of stance styles framework. Next, the result of the analysis was discussed, negotiated, and clarified for an agreement between the researcher and the co-rater if there were any miscoding occurred. Finally, the co-rater could work on their own independently to code the 6 sample texts on the stance framework. McHugh (2012) stated that the stance identification results from the co-rater and the researcher on a sample of 6 (20%) RAs introductions were compared through the Kappa score. Brown (1996) illustrates that Cohen's Kappa has made the maximum score of 1.00 and the lowest score of 0.00, (as cited in Nur et al., 2021). Consequently, Kanoksilapatham's (2005) study was adopted in this study, if Cohen's Kappa mark is less than 0.40, this was regarded as 'poor',

between 0.40–0.59 ‘average’, between 0.60–0.74 ‘acceptable’, and 0.75 or above ‘excellent’. The following table 3 showed the result of the Kappa measurement of the researcher’s checklist and the co-rater’s checklists

Table 2.

Inter-Rater agreement Result

The number used of stance expression	No. of agreement	No. of Disagreement	K	Percentage
107	107	0	100	100%

According to table 2, the researcher and the two co-raters discovered forty-one decision data drawn out while examining the Corpus. Most interestingly, the same data results between the researcher and the two co-raters unfolded. This meant that the random agreement data (Pr(e)= 0% or 0.00), whereas 107 data were categorized as the same agreement data (Pr(a)= 100% or 1).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The expression styles in the introduction section by Cambodian authors

The first finding of this study was significantly expressing a common occurrence in the local journals and international journals. The below table demonstrates the frequency styles of stance expression which were commonly found in Local journals (LoJ) and international journals (InJ) in this study. Hedges, boosters, attitudinal markers, and self-mention were the four forms of stance expression styles discovered by data analysis from LoJ and InJ publications through AntConc. software.

Based on table 3, it can be seen that there are four types of styles found in this research: hedges, boosters, attitude markers, and self-mention. The total frequency of stance expressions from the thirty-research article introduction sections was 444 times; the frequent use of stance expression types in the research article introduction sections publish in Local journals is greater than the research article introduction section published in international journals, which was counted in 201.

Otherwise, the hedge was mostly found in both research articles which were published in local journals, and international journals were 228 or 51.35%, applied by the Cambodian authors in writing the RAs introduction section. The second most frequent stance expression type use was boosters with a total number of 87 or 19.60%. These types are, must, really, find, found, and many others.

Table 3.

Stance expression types found in research article introductions

No	Stance Expression Categories	(LoJ)	(InJ)	Total	%
		N=15	N=15	N=30	
		Frequency			
1	Hedges	140	88	228	51.35
2	Boosters	38	49	87	19.60
3	Attitude Markers	43	36	79	17.79
4	Self-mentions	22	28	50	11.26
	Total	243	201	444	100%

Additionally, the following rank was the use of attitude markers whose percentage accounted for 79 or 17.79% among all of the cases. They are *appropriate*, *demonstrate*, *belief*, *find*, *shown*, even though, even, etc. Finally, it is different from the above three stance expression styles. There are only 50 or 11.26% of self-mention were found in this research such as I, my, the researchers, we, our, the writer, etc, to identify themselves in writing the research article introduction section.

Some examples presented about stance expression types engaged by the Cambodian authors in their research article introduction sections published in local and international journals as the following:

Example1:

*"Clayton (2006) has **shown**, that the Khmer embraced learning English, as another to French (their colonial language.....)" [03_InJ]*

Example2:

*"This means **the researcher** should have a decent understanding of the curriculum, the materials, and also the language levels the scholars are taking." [06_InJ]*

Accordingly, example 1 shows that the author applied the verb "shown" as a past participle in present perfect tense to express the action which has just happened recently, and it is employed to cite the information that can be used about the writer's stance. Last, in example 2, the common noun "the researcher" was taken to directly mention the researcher who was doing the research.

The hedges categories

The following tables presented the total number of hedges found with examples in thirty RA introductions.

Table 4.

The frequency of hedges categories in the research article introduction section

No.	Hedges categories	RAs in LEF		Total	%
		LoJ	InJ		
		Frequency			
1	Modal Auxiliary verbs	76	33	109	47.81
2	Epistemic lexical verbs	40	27	67	29.39
3	Epistemic adjectives& adverbs	24	28	52	22.80
	Total	140	88	228	100

Hedges were demonstrated in three diverse lexical categories, as shown in Table 6. It can be noted that modal auxiliaries were the most frequently employed was 109 or 47.81% of all cases; through these results the researcher found that there are 76 modal auxiliary verbs were counted in the research article introduction section published in local journals, while only 33 out of 109 modal verbs were accounted for RAs published in international journals (i.e., can, should, would, etc.); the second most utilized was epistemic lexical verbs with 67 or 29.39% of all thirty RAs introduction sections published in both journals (i.e., seems, feel, suggested, claimed, preferred, argue, and so on). It showed that 40 out of 67 epistemic lexical verbs were found in ARs published in local journals, but there are only 27 times counted for RAs published in international journals.

The last was epistemic adjectives and adverbs which accounted for just 52 times or 22.8 % of the total, likely largely, rather, etc. We can illustrate that the frequent use of adjectives and adverbs was slightly different between the LoJ RAs and InJ RAs (24 to 28 adv & adv). There were 24 adjectives and adverbs found in LoJ RAs, similarly, 28 out of 52 accounted for InJ RAs. Some examples presented about hedge categories as following:

Example 3

*".....English needs analysis **should** be conducted before formulating any English language program....." [04_InJ]*

According to the use of "should", a modal verb hedge, in example 3 is applied to express the uncertain suggestion of evaluating the English language program before creating or running any English language program or courses. As a result of these above examples, it was possible to conclude that hedges can contribute to authors reducing the risk of dissimilarity. It can also be used to disprove the authors' claim and demonstrate doubt about the writers' entitlement to information.

The booster categories

The three categories of boosters were discovered in these academic texts such as modal auxiliary verbs, epistemic lexical verbs, and epistemic adjectives and adverbs. Table 5 below lists the boosters discovered in this study's corpus.

Table 5.

Booster categories in the research article introduction section

No	Boosters Categories	RAs in LEF		Total	Percentage
		LoJ	InJ		
		Frequency			
1	Modal Auxiliaries verbs	0	5	5	5.75
2	Epistemic lexical verbs	27	28	55	63.22
3	Epistemic adjectives& adverbs	11	16	27	31.03
Total		38	49	87	100

Based on table 5, it can be seen that in the English research article introduction sections written by Cambodian authors; three categories of booster were counted for RAs published in international journals as modal auxiliary verbs, lexical verbs, and adjective and adverbs while there were only two categories of booster were found in RAs published in local journals: epistemic lexical verbs and adjectives and adverbs. As a result, the epistemic lexical verbs were the most commonly utilized by the writers with 27 times for RAs in local journals and 28 times for RAs in international journals. Meanwhile, there were two results of this study also were shown that booster adjectives and adverbs were found more than 10 times from LJ Ras 11 of 15 cases and IJ Ras 16. Finally, the author realized that modal auxiliaries were found 5 times counted for IJ RAs of this study. The writers brought out some examples of the two types of RAs:

Example 4

*"Making a quotation takes the exact words from a source without any change and is **clearly** indicated as such, by quotation marks for example (Anker, 2009; Bailey, 2011)." [02_Lo]*

According to example 4 above, it was presented that adverb booster "clearly" was employed to show the stance of the author about making a quotation mark to the exact words of sources. So, it can be concluded that booster stances can be formed in verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and modal auxiliary verbs, yet modal auxiliary verbs were not frequently found in these articles' studies. The adjective, adverbs, verbs, and modal auxiliary verbs that have been mentioned and discussed above can be used to direct the certainty of the writers and emphasize a fact that they focused on.

The attitude markers categories

The following table illustrates the three categories of attitude markers stance: they were attitude verbs, sentence adverbs, and attitude adjectives. The details and examples are presented below in the table.

Table 6.

Attitude Marker categories in the research article introduction section

No	Attitude Markers Categories	RAs in the LE field		Total	%
		LoJ	InJ		
		Frequency			
1	Attitude verbs	3	1	4	5.06
2	Sentence adverbs	5	8	13	16.46
3	Attitude adjectives	35	27	62	78.48
	Total	43	36	79	100

Table 6 shows that the three categories of attitude markers were found in RAs journals, and the most common frequently used attitude marker stance was attitude adjectives, which accounted for 62 or more than 78 percent of the two RAs. It can be seen that the adjectives were mostly employed in RAs local journals 35 times when only 27 out of 62 were counted for RAs international journals. Notedly, adverbs were known as one of the attitude markers that were poorly found with only 13 or just more than 16 percent of thirty cases. A number of 8 out of 13 were found in RAs of International journals; however, 5 out of 13 were adverbs used in RAs published in local journals. Finally, the poorest frequently use was attitude verbs with only 4 times in both types of RAs Journals. We can see that the writer rarely utilized this category, and it was just only 1 calculated for RAs international journals.

As can be seen, the use of attitudinal markers in the form of adjectives, adverbs, and verbs was taken to demonstrate the importance of the information in terms of building the field being researched, as well as to assist the author in expressing their thoughts toward the information. The use of attitude markers was pointed out through the following examples.

Example5

*“..... the fact that one of the most **important** stages in any lesson is the Warming-up Phase..... [08_Lo]”*

For example5, the word ‘important’ was used by the authors to stress their positive ideas on the effective using the warming-up stage among all the instruction phases in getting students’ attention. In short, it can be seen that attitude markers can

be used in various forms as verbs, adjectives, and adverbs which were applied to address the importance of the information for strengthening their studying fields. Thus, this type of stance expression can be used to support the writers to prompt their awareness toward the information which was considered as effective information and important information as to their research information.

The Self-mention expression categories

The table below brings the detailed result of self-mention analysis used by the writers in the written English research article introduction section in the language education field.

Table 7. Self-mention categories in the research article introduction section

No.	Self-Mention	RAs in LE field		Total	Percent.
		LoJ	InJ		
		Frequency			
1	Subject Pronouns	12	17	29	58
3	Common Nouns	5	7	12	24
4	Possessive Adjectives	5	4	9	18
2	Object Pronouns	0	0	0	0
	Total	22	28	50	100

Based on table 7, the total number of using self-mention was 50 times of all thirty cases, which were published in local journals and international journals. However, 29 out of 50 frequencies were the subject pronouns 'we' were the most commonly employed by the authors in both types of RAs journals. There were 17 times found in RAs published in international journals, and in the RAs published in local journals, there were only 12 counted in the study. The lower rate of use of common nouns "the researcher, the author" was also found in both RAs journals with 12, which accounts for 24%. The lowest frequency found on the possessive adjectives was only 9 or 18% from both types of RAs journals. We can clearly see that 5 possessive adjectives were found in RAs' local journals; similarly, 4 out of 9 were counted for IJ RAs. It was 'our'.

Therefore, the subject pronoun 'we' was found as the most commonly used by the authors in this research. The authors used 'we' to present themselves in the writing research. The authors in both journals of the thirty English research articles did not use objective pronouns in presenting themselves in their text. The following example is presented about self-mention stance types.

Example6

*“Based on **our observations**, some learners,...they fail to remember the detailed information in the stories.” [07_LoJ]*

According to example6, the author used the possessive pronoun ‘our’ to originally show their operating work in their study. Through these examples, it can be concluded that the authors rarely referred to themselves as he or she in their text. As well, there were not many dissimilarities in self-addressing of self-mention stance regarding the thirty articles written by the Cambodian authors published in both journals.

The comparison between both RAs’ introductions

Figure 1. the comparison of using each stance expression type

Based on figure 1, it can be seen that the total frequency of using each category of stance expression within the RAs introduction section published in local journals was 243 by the Cambodian authors while 201 times used in each category were counted in the IJ RAs introduction section. Moreover, the researcher found that hedge was more highly used in RAs in the local journals than in RAs in international journals, with 148 times while there were only 88 times found in InJ Ras by Cambodian authors. In contrast, the result revealed that booster was mostly utilized in the InJ RA introduction with 49, but 38 times were discovered in the LoJ RA introduction. On the other hand, the figure also showed that the attitude markers used were greater found in the LoJ RA introduction with 43 while there were only 36 counted in the InJ RA introduction. Last, there are similar numbers of self-mention used were employed in both journals’ RAs with 22 of LoJ and 26 of InJ introduction. It means that the use of self-mention in both RA journals is almost the same, yet it is significant differences in the use of hedge, booster, and attitude markers in both RA journals written by Cambodian authors.

Discussion

The first research question was that the hedge categories are used by Cambodian authors in the introduction of English research articles in the field of language education. The result showed that all four types of stance expression proposed by Hyland (2005) appeared in the two RAs' introduction journals. They named hedges, boosters, attitude markers, and self-mentions. Interestingly, the highest frequency used type was a hedge in both research article journals written by Cambodian authors. However, the hedge has been often employed in Local journal research articles than international journal articles. This can be assumed that local RA writers overused the hedge, which is not important, and this showed that local article journal writers were less confident than international RA writers in demonstrating their findings. Thus, this might be due to the cultural factors of local writers who consider face-saving and respect to be an important reason to use hedges in their RA writing. Getkham (2016) found that hedge was the biggest dominant used in the introduction and discussion sections. He stated that might be because of the cultural factor impact on saving face and showing politeness.

Thus, the hedge allows the author to expose a broad space where readers can discuss their understandings (Hyland, 2005). This study is closely related to Papangkorn and Phoocharoensil's (2021) study; they found that hedge was the most commonly used in English argumentative writing by Native and Thai learners. They also stated that this result showed weakness and less confidence on the part of both Native and Thai learners in tentatively expressing their argumentative text. Hence, the finding of this research is in line with Incharoesak (2018), in which Thai high school students were sent to U.S middle college because they frequently used hedge in application essays to express their confident predictions. However, this result is contrasted with Moini and Salami (2015), who found that there was slightly less use of hedge in journal author's guidelines because this light use was employed to soften the impact of journal assertions and to prompt probability.

Moreover, the hedge can be used to show the writer's views, criticism, uncertainty, and little confidence and applied to soften the text or reduce the reluctance of the force of a statement. Thus, this finding was supported by Shen and Tao (2021) who also revealed that the most frequent type of stance markers in both newspapers OC and medical RA was hedge. This high-frequency use of hedge demonstrated the authors' caution and weakening in creating appropriate truth expressing claims and

necessity for a statement. In this respect, Petchkij (2019) found that the modals as sub-categories of hedge were the most frequently employed by Thai EFL students in the academic writing classroom. The result of this study is also related to that of Alghazo et al. (2021), in which modals and semi-modals were mostly counted and increasingly contributed to applied linguistics than in the literature research article abstract. The reason was that the slippery nature of the applied linguistic subject is remarked by uncertainty and ambiguity. That is why it impacted the LA writer's use of hedge sub-categories in their writing as well as LE writer's writing too.

The lexical verbs of sub-categories were booster and were the most frequent use the same in both English research articles. Both authors used these sub-categories to show the strong certainty degree of their belief in a statement. This means that they revealed either the accepted idea or fact as evidence to represent their confidence in stating a statement. Yet, this finding is closely associated with Shen and Tao's (2021) study, which illustrated those epistemic lexical verbs of the booster category were mostly accounted for newspaper genre. It can be assumed that both researchers are confident enough in emphasizing a statement.

The adjectives sub-category of attitude marker were mostly counted in these two RA introduction sections. The attitude markers are used by the authors to show the important judgment of a statement to pull the readers into a conspiracy of agreement as well as attitude markers refer to the affective of the writer (Hyland, 2005). The result from Getkham (2016) also supported this study that Thai doctoral students often utilized adjectives as subcategories of attitude markers in their doctoral dissertation writing.

Otherwise, the useless one was subjective pronouns of self-mention were frequently counted in both RA introduction sections. However, the author realized that this subject pronoun was more commonly used in IJRAs than in LJRAs. This study is supported by Karahan (2013), who studied self-mention use by Turkish and Non-Turkish in scientific writing articles and found that the subject pronoun of self-mention was always used in both Turkish and Non-Turkish scientific writing articles. This can be assumed that the authors were not confident enough in addressing themselves in the introduction because their findings were not released yet. This is supported by Getkham (2016) who presented the finding that writers used less self-mention in the introduction rather than in the discussion section because they felt more confident once they see the result in their discussion section.

The finding showed that there were no significant differences in terms of the frequent use of boosters, attitude markers, and self-mention. However, there was a significant difference in terms of the frequent use of hedges in both RA introductions. The hedge was the highest proportion of all stance expression types accounted for both research article types. This finding is similar to Papangkorn and Phoocharoensil's (2021) comparison study that found the difference in frequencies of stance expression use, hedge was the biggest used in THAI writers and Native writers. This is closely related to Petchkij's (2019) finding about hedges being the most frequently used by native writers as well as Sukhanindr (2008) found that native writers used more hedges than Thai writers in the discussion section of research articles. Therefore, this finding contrasted with the findings from Incharoensak (2018) that hedge was used more in Thai writers' writing than in Native writers' writing. This can be concluded that Thai and Cambodian authors have similar cultures, which is the cause of the increase in the distribution of hedges.

CONCLUSION

There are some points to be concluded in sequence: first, it was found that all four stance expression types proposed by Hyland appeared in both RA introduction published in local journals and international journals. They were hedges, boosters, attitude markers, and self-mention. However, we see that the biggest frequency use type among the four types of stance expression was a hedge sub-category in the RA introduction sections of both journals. Second, the subcategory of self-mention was mostly accounted by the subject pronoun "we" in the RA introduction sections of both journals. Thirdly, the researcher found that differences in terms of the frequencies of use of hedge in the RA introduction sections of both journals were significant in this study. But there was no significant difference in terms of the booster, attitude markers, and self-mention because there was a very small difference in the frequency use of these types within both RA introduction sections.

The Cambodian authors use more attitude markers and boosters of stance expression in their introduction section to improve their research article writing quality. There were only 15 RAs selected from local journals and the other 15 RAs were chosen from international journals. However, the other content such as the abstract, methodology discussion, and conclusion section were not discussed in this study and should be discussed by another researcher. Furthermore, for further study, the researchers can study the comparison of the stance expression and engagement

used between native Cambodian authors and non-native Cambodian authors in RAs published in international journals in the introduction section or the discussion section by expanding more sample from different research articles from diverse available journals.

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Developing Thinking Reading Classrooms: Insight from Pre-Service EFL Teachers' Lesson Plans and Classroom Instructions

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Abstract

Numerous studies have investigated the integration of critical thinking in EFL classrooms and textbooks. Still, relatively few have investigated the integration of critical thinking into reading lesson plans and classroom instructions. The current study adopted a qualitative case study approach to provide insight into how pre-service EFL teachers infused critical thinking skills into online reading classrooms. The study also gives information on pre-service EFL teachers' challenges in critical thinking integration into reading classrooms. Eight pre-service EFL teachers who completed all three phases of the faculty-mandated teaching practicum program participated in the study. Document analysis, virtual classroom observations, and semi-structured interviews were used as data collection techniques to fulfill the research objectives. As the study framework, Bloom's revised taxonomy was applied to lesson plan data to examine how critical thinking components are incorporated. Virtual classroom observations illuminated the incorporation of critical thinking into reading lessons. In addition, semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather more information regarding the challenges of integrating critical thinking skills. The present study reveals that pre-service EFL teachers integrated critical thinking aspects into reading online classes with a greater emphasis on lower-order cognitive than higher-order cognitive processes. It implies that pre-service EFL teachers had insufficient preparation for teaching practicum programs. Due to the significance of critical thinking skills for EFL students, this study recommends that teacher training institutes strengthen the critical thinking abilities of pre-service EFL teachers so that they are more equipped to teach and promote critical thinking in EFL classrooms.

Keywords: classroom instructions, critical thinking, lesson plans, pre-service teachers

INTRODUCTION

The concept of education has undergone a substantial transition in recent years. Students in this era must adapt to the 21st century's needs and acquire critical thinking abilities to participate in an ever-changing and increasingly complex world. Critical thinking has been a persistent focus for schools, companies, and policymakers since it is seen as a significant life skill and a beneficial tool in the workplace (Koenig, 2011). Critical thinking has various definitions and a wide range of meanings. The researcher considered critical thinking an internal concept essential in a person's academic learning and social life (Wilson, 2016). Interpretation, analysis, evaluation, conclusion, explanation, and self-regulation are all part of critical thinking (Facione, 1990). In addition, critical thinking includes critical thinking abilities and dispositions to think critically (Ennis, 1996). According to Ennis (1996), critical thinking is a rational, introspective thought oriented towards determining what to perceive or do. People with critical thinking abilities are capable of making well-founded choices and decisions.

Furthermore, critical thinking is defined as the capacity for investigating and assessing one's thoughts to improve them (Paul & Elder, 2009) and the ability to identify and solve problems (Wineburg, 1998). It promotes students' acceptance of information and response to it since it is a cognitive process that engages the mind and focuses on reasoning (Cottrel, 2005). Anderson and Krathwohl (2001) reexamined and updated Bloom's taxonomy's cognitive domain, known as Revised Bloom Taxonomy. It includes a hierarchical scale of skills -remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating-which have been connected to critical thinking (Ghanizadeh et al., 2020). Critical thinking as an essential aspect has been promoted to be taught (Abrami et al., 2008). These abilities help students identify the reasons they want to learn, determine their learning objectives based on those needs, and effectively manage their practice time.

Critical thinking is essential to education, including language education (Wilson, 2016); various studies provide empirical findings on the benefit of incorporating critical thinking into foreign language instruction (El Soufi & See, 2019; Heidari, 2020). Critical thinking can stimulate the achievement of language abilities (Yanning, 2017; Wu et al., 2013; Yang & Gamble, 2013). Critical thinking enables students to explore and evaluate topics and decide their own academic choices in language learning (Nold, 2017). It also supports students in developing their

cognitive abilities to select relevant and essential information and evaluate and decide the most effective approaches for reaching learning objectives (Lin, 2018; Zhang et al., 2020). Students who strengthen their critical thinking skills improve their ability to solve problems and make decisions. Thus, scholars have placed emphasis upon encouraging this form of thinking in language classrooms (Zhao et al., 2016).

As required in today's world, learners must communicate effectively, analyze messages, draw arguments and conclusions, and critically construct their own opinions. Many studies argue that critical thinking is required for effective language learning regarding these demands. Therefore, training in critical thinking should be incorporated into the ELT program (Bağ & Gürsoy, 2021). However, there are some challenges in critical thinking integration in EFL classrooms. Some factors listed are time constraints, material resources, and L2 proficiency (Floyd, 2011; Li, 2016a; Manalo & Sheppard, 2016). Students' insufficient mastery of English makes it hard for them to communicate their thoughts and feelings. Due to the difficulties inherent in integrating critical thinking, EFL teachers must construct the most effective classroom activities.

Planning a lesson is essential in the realm of education. Lesson planning is a crucial aspect of teaching since it provides teachers with a roadmap to follow during a class. A lesson plan is an invaluable tool that embodies the teaching philosophy and learning objectives (Nesari & Heidari, 2014). Effective lesson planning supports successful teaching and curriculum policy implementation. In addition, it is essential to comprehend the distinction between conventional and critical thinking classes. The teacher, throughout a traditional class, constantly instructs students. Since reading is a complex activity, lesson plans must require teachers to choose the most effective exercises. Diverse cognitive skills are needed for textual meaning extraction, and students gradually gain literacy (Huang & Yang, 2015).

Some studies have found that critical thinking integration in EFL courses yielded positive effects in Indonesia. Critical thinking can develop higher-order thinking in students because it compels them to distinguish between fact and opinion (Haryati & Hidayati, 2017). In addition, mobile learning applications can improve critical thinking skills in assessing, reasoning, and drawing conclusions (Agustina et al., 2022). However, challenges to incorporating essential thinking remain, including lack of clarity in the curriculum, unfriendly culture, and teaching-learning

approaches to promote students' critical thinking (Lamb, 2004). Teachers' lack of critical literacy comprehension also contributes to highlighted factors (Gustine, 2018). Several studies have also shown the presence of critical thinking in EFL textbooks. Solihati and Hikmat (2018) used content analysis to determine whether textbook assignments improve students' critical thinking skills. The study showed that textbooks provide few critical thinking exercises. Aside from that, there was a lack of variety in tasks that encouraged students to think critically.

In addition, the pandemic COVID-19 led to a shift in teaching and learning from face-to-face learning mode to the online mode. This transition presented some daunting issues for teachers and students alike. Several studies highlighted critical thinking integration in online language learning. Tathahira (2020) identified several obstacles to critical thinking integration into online language learning, including the socio-cultural issue, the student's learning habits, and their experience with utilizing modern technology for learning. In addition, Loo (2020) found that recognizing sentence functions in a paragraph, identifying sentence functions in connection to verbs, and completing grammar quizzes are tasks that facilitate the incorporation of critical thinking into online academic writing classes.

Despite a growing number of research studies on critical thinking integration in EFL classrooms and textbooks, exploring critical thinking integration in online reading classes, from lesson planning to classroom instructions, has received little attention. Therefore, the purpose of the present study was to examine how pre-service EFL teachers infuse critical thinking skills into online reading classes, from lesson planning to instruction. The study also aimed to shed light on pre-service EFL teachers' obstacles when infusing critical thinking into classroom instruction.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study utilized a case study to understand a phenomenon's context comprehensively. The present study aimed to investigate how pre-service EFL teachers infuse critical thinking abilities into their online reading classes and identify obstacles in critical thinking integration. Altogether, eight pre-service EFL teachers, six females and two males participated in the study. The participants were recruited through the technique of convenience sampling, which includes readily available individuals who volunteer or can be quickly recruited (Johnson, R. B., & Christensen, 2017). The participants were students in the English Education Program at an

Islamic University in Indonesia who had completed the faculty-mandated teaching program. All participants in this study are presented with pseudonyms.

Data Collection

The researchers used document analysis, virtual classroom observation, and semi-structured interviews to collect data. The use of document analysis illustrated how parts of critical thinking were incorporated into reading lesson plans. This study includes ten lesson plans from eight pre-service EFL teachers, as two participants created two lesson plans each. In addition, five recorded virtual classrooms were scrutinized to see whether pre-service EFL teachers integrated critical thinking into classroom instructions. The virtual classrooms observation data demonstrated the instructional activities of two to three pre-service EFL teachers teaching in teams. Each participant was given the opportunity to teach the lesson twice with different partners in the teaching practicum program. For further investigation, semi-structured interviews with eight participants attempted to elucidate the perspectives of pre-service EFL teachers on the challenges of integrating critical thinking into online reading classes. This method promotes consistency and flexibility in investigating teacher perceptions and practices, as it is organized sufficiently to answer specific interview questions while allowing participants to contribute additional meanings. The interview with each participant lasted between 20-30 minutes via Google Meet and WhatsApp. The researchers used Bahasa Indonesia in the interview to get precise information and reduce misunderstandings.

Data Analysis

Lesson plan data, including assignments and activities, were categorized into potential themes. Pre-service EFL teachers' lesson plans were analyzed using revised Bloom's taxonomy by Anderson et al. (2001) as the research framework. The researchers took field notes during virtual classroom observation to identify tasks and activities pertinent to the research. The virtual reading classes were recorded to make it easier for the researchers to reexamine the learning processes. In addition, the researchers analyzed the interview data to gain insight into pre-service EFL teachers' views on integrating critical thinking. The researchers went through data condensation, display, conclusion drawing, and verification to analyze the data (Miles et al., 2014).

First, the researchers listened to the recorded interview data several times while coding the data informally. Second, the researchers transcribed the interview data

verbatim to achieve high accuracy. Then the researchers immersed themselves in the data during the condensation phase by reading and rereading the transcripts. The researchers marked participants' opinions using highlighters regarding integrating critical thinking into online reading classes. After all the data were coded and compiled, the researchers refocused the study on themes, rather than codes, by sorting the codes into probable themes and combining all the relevant coded data extracts inside the discovered themes. The classifications were then amended if errors were discovered. Then, the researchers compared across sections of all categories.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

This section examines how pre-service EFL teachers integrated critical thinking into online reading classes. It also includes information regarding pre-service teachers' challenges in the classrooms. For each point, the most representative data are presented as evidence.

Critical Thinking Integration into Reading Lesson Plans

The analysis found that pre-service EFL teachers have attempted to include critical thinking into reading lesson plans, making students the focus of the learning process. As one of the essential skills in language learning, teaching reading skills requires teachers to devise innovative and effective learning activities including tasks, questions, and activities to promote students' critical thinking skills. The lesson plans analysis was based on Bloom's revised taxonomy by Anderson et al. (2001). The participants used six cognitive processes in their lesson plans, ranging from the simplest, remembering, to the most difficult, creating. Pre-service EFL teachers used different tasks and activities based on their objectives.

Remembering

Remembering is essential for meaningful learning and problem solving, given that the knowledge gained in 'remembering' is subsequently utilized in more complex tasks (Anderson et al., 2001). Thus, remembering plays a crucial role in language learning. In the reading classes, teachers can incorporate 'remembering' into introductory activities such as brainstorming. The lesson plan data revealed that pre-service EFL teachers integrated 'remembering' activities into online reading classes. Some lesson plans involved 'remembering' activities with the teacher as the central actor in the learning procedures, for example:

Teacher asks students about the topic covered at the prior meeting. (PST 2/LP/IL)

Teacher instructs students to create questions based on the topic. (PST 5/LP/IL)

By asking students to clarify previously covered material and generate questions based on the topic, pre-service EFL teachers assisted students in recalling previously acquired information.

In addition, the data indicated that pre-service EFL teachers attempted to design lesson plans with students as the central focus of learning. Some 'remembering' activities such as:

Students identify the structure of formal and informal invitation letter. (PST 4/LP/IL)

Students match the word with the correct illustration. (PST 3/LP/IL)

The learning activities above enabled students to recall prior knowledge and identify specific information. Students must use their minds to complete the above assignments. Remembering as a cognitive process involving the use of the mind is consistent with Cottrel's (2005) notion that critical thinking is a cognitive process involving the mind and focusing on arguments.

Understanding

By 'understanding,' students can interpret the issue and construct the meaning of instructional messages, which may be spoken, written, or graphic. The 'understanding' process categories involve interpreting, illustrating, classifying, summarizing, deducing, comparing, and explaining (Anderson et al., 2001). The investigation found that pre-service EFL teachers employed 'understanding' activities in their lesson plans to deliver learning materials. PST 4 wrote:

Students comprehend the teachers' explanation about tourist destinations. (PST 4/LP/DT)

Activities that test students' comprehension are the first step toward more challenging work. Additionally, PST 7 devised an assignment involving tasks such as comparing and contrasting two topics to test student's comprehension of the materials. Students' ability to discern between two issues demonstrates their comprehension of the material.

'Understanding' has become a required stage in teaching reading since students must comprehend a reading passage and frequently answer the questions following

it. Students' ability to participate in subsequent cognitive processes depends on their understanding level—the ability to understand and to think critically, consistent with Facione (1990).

Applying

Applying is carrying out a technique in a particular context (Anderson et al., 2001). Two cognitive processes comprise the apply category: executing and implementing. The task of 'executing' is familiar and can be handled, whereas the process of 'implementing' is new (Anderson et al., 2001). The applying process can be observed in the effort to apply knowledge to problem-solving since students are frequently confronted with various issues during the lessons. Students usually use the previous information in a task that instructs them to modify, construct, or solve a problem in the applying process.

From the analysis, the researchers found only a few 'applying' activities, and PST 8's lesson plan contains one of the examples. PST 8 designed various classroom activities, including student group discussions and presentations. In the discussion, students apply their knowledge to offer and accept one of the other's viewpoints, whereas when presenting their work, they attempt to provide a solution for a problem. Discussion and presentation are two activities that might assist students in developing their critical thinking abilities since students select and use pertinent information when participating. It is consistent with Lin's (2018) argument that learning critical thinking helps students select and apply relevant and essential information to determine the most effective ways to achieve their goals.

Analyzing

Analyzing is figuring out how various components are connected (Anderson et al., 2001). Differentiating, organizing, and attributing are three cognitive processes in analyzing activities (Anderson et al., 2001). This process begins with examining concepts, followed by identifying and analyzing arguments. Pre-service EFL teachers employed some 'analyzing' activities in their lesson plans, for instance:

Students analyze the invitation cards to determine the structure and content
(PST 7/LP/IL)

Students need to recognize the connections between several components to analyze the structure of a text successfully. They are required to investigate the concept first and then locate each specific item of information before arriving at an analysis.

Critical thinking, defined as having the ability to analyze is comparable to Facione's (1990) notion.

Evaluating

Evaluating is the process of judging based on categories or criteria, which include checking and criticizing procedures (Anderson et al., 2001). Pre-service EFL teachers had the evaluation process in their lesson plans, as demonstrated below:

Students evaluate their work through collaborative corrections. (PST 8/LP/DT)

The activity above instructed students to complete evaluation activities as part of a collaborative learning environment. This task encouraged students to learn from each other's mistakes and improve their work through collective corrections.

In addition, PST 1's lesson plan included an activity that involved summarizing. PST 1 asked students to summarize the previously learned content. Students must ensure that all significant features of the topic are included in their summary. This section contained evaluation-related content. This idea is similar to Yang and Gamble's (2013) arguments, which claimed that EFL teachers perceive critical thinking as the ability to evaluate, summarize, discover norms and patterns, solve problems, negotiate solutions with peers, and construct evidence-based arguments.

Creating

Creating is regarded as the most advanced cognitive sub-skill. Pre-service EFL teachers used 'creating' tasks as the most complex activities in their learning design. 'Creating' indicates whether students comprehend the lesson and can apply it to the creative activities. Three cognitive processes are involved in the creative process: generating, planning, and producing (Anderson et al., 2001). 'Generating' entails expressing the problem and arriving at alternatives or hypotheses that match specific criteria. Planning entails constructing a solution approach that fulfills the requirements of an issue, i.e., developing a plan for fixing the problem. Producing entails a procedure for selecting a specific problem that fits specified criteria (Anderson et al., 2001). The activity of 'creating' is presented below:

Students compose descriptive texts using themes such as historical locations, tourism attractions, animals, objects, and people. (PST 3/LP/DT)

PST 3 asked students to produce descriptive writings on the specified topics. To engage in a creative process, students must draw on their knowledge and experience

to generate, plan, and produce a new form of meaning. 'Creating' comprises assembling knowledge from several sources into new patterns and offering solutions to solve problems (Anderson et al., 2001). Students can use the three strategies of generating, planning, and finally producing to complete a descriptive task as instructed by their teachers. The notion of critical thinking as a creative process is consistent with Elder and Paul's (2006) definition, which states that critical thinking is a mode of thinking about any subject, substance, or issue in which the thinker methodically analyzes, evaluates, and reconstructs the thinking to improve its quality.

Critical Thinking Integration into Online Reading Classroom

In this study, participants exercised their teaching skills through team teaching. Each team teaching consisted of two to three pre-service EFL teachers, who worked together in the classroom to present the lesson and accomplish the learning objectives. In their practices, they divided the responsibilities and taught in rotation. Pre-service EFL teachers employed several strategies to include critical thinking in online reading classes. The reading classes were conducted virtually via Google Meet. The researchers participated as observers and documented the learning process. Documentation was prepared to allow the researchers to conduct quality assurance checks on the data and to ensure that the data gathered were accurate. During the participation in the teaching and learning activities, the researchers also kept a field note to capture genuine emotions and experiences. The recorded virtual teaching and learning process revealed that pre-service EFL teachers used brainstorming, questioning, and various learning tools in online reading classes. All strategies addressed reading activities before, during, and after the lesson.

Brainstorming

Pre-service EFL teachers employed brainstorming by posing questions related to previous knowledge at the beginning of the lesson. Prior knowledge questions were considered lower-cognitive since they required students to recollect specified knowledge immediately. Brainstorming is commonly linked to problem-solving. In reading comprehension, brainstorming allows readers to generate and share past knowledge to solve problems and achieve the objective (Tran, 2017). Pre-service EFL teachers believed brainstorming helps investigate the students' understanding of specific topics. Instead of enforcing the opinions presented in the text, brainstorming facilitates activating students' prior knowledge or schema (Ghabanchi & Behrooznia,

2014). Virtual classroom observation data revealed that pre-service teachers allowed students to state their understanding of the issues before proceeding to the main activities. Participants in this study were scheduled to teach descriptive texts and invitation letters at Senior High Schools.

Pre-service EFL teachers initiated the reading session with a brainstorming activity by posing questions to the student. Teaching in the same team, PST 3 and PST 6, used descriptive text entitled 'Historical Building' to be discussed in the classrooms. PST 3 started the lesson by inquiring about students' knowledge of historic buildings. This question aimed to explore students' initial understanding of historical buildings. PST 3 also utilized this approach to introduce descriptive texts. PST 3 continued the lesson by allowing students to discuss a descriptive text, while PST 6 assisted students in responding to text-based questions. Brainstorming is a component of remembering activities because, in this activity, students compile a list of pertinent facts about the topic under discussion. Brainstorming techniques positively and significantly affect the participants' critical thinking and reading comprehension skills (Ghabanchi & Behrooznia, 2014).

Questioning

Teachers can effectively integrate critical thinking into their teaching by focusing on the quality and types of questions posed in classes. Questioning is an effective method of encouraging students to think critically. Higher-level inquiries and probing techniques encourage students to reason, evaluate, research, expand their views, and enhance critical thinking (Zhao et al., 2016). Questions that encourage critical thinking should guarantee that students are not merely repeating data but are making judgments or evaluating various alternatives (Case, 2005). Virtual classroom observation data showed that pre-service EFL teachers posed specific questions in the reading classrooms, such as questions about factual or particular information in the text and evaluation or analysis questions.

Questions referring to factual or particular information in the text are questions that concern explicitly stated facts in the text and do not require students to think critically. Pre-service EFL teachers posed the following questions:

What evidence can you find in the text about the characteristics of Purna Bhakti Pertiwi Museum? (PST 1/CO/DT)

Where is the National Monument Located? (PST 2 & PST 3/CO/DT)

These questions indicated that pre-service EFL teachers tend to emphasize subject matter expertise over developing critical thinking skills. On the other hand, pre-service EFL teachers might also utilize lower order thinking questions to stimulate class involvement and minimize anxiety among students with limited English competence.

In addition, questions related to evaluating or analyzing appeared in the reading classroom, such as:

From the text, we can infer that? (PST 3 & PST 6/CO/IL)

Which statement is true based on the text? (PST 3 & PST 6/CO/IL)

These questions required students to analyze the detailed information presented in the text to draw a conclusion and determine the correct information. In addition, pre-service EFL teachers also used questioning to assess students' comprehension of the presented material. In their teaching practice, PST 3 and PST 6 asked students about their knowledge of the provided materials and allowed them to ask questions on sections they did not fully comprehend. Pre-service EFL teachers developed students' ability to think critically, assessed their learning, and asked follow-up questions by allowing them to raise questions. Questioning allows students to negotiate meaning through engaging, thought-provoking discussions and activities (Seker & Kömür, 2008).

Using Various Learning Materials

To foster the development of critical thinking in reading lessons, pre-service EFL teachers employed a variety of media, including reading passages, visuals, games, music, and YouTube videos. Pre-service EFL teachers utilized illustrated or image-filled texts for teaching descriptive text. They provided students with a descriptive text for discussion and exercises. In addition, pre-service EFL teachers used a greater variety of text in the session on formal and informal invitation letters to teach students to distinguish between formal and informal invitation letters. The strategies adopted by pre-service EFL teachers are consistent with the assertion that the learning material should be chosen with care regarding topic familiarity and language complexity to enhance students' engagement in critical thinking (Setyaningsih, 2019). Student participation in their studies is increased when learning materials are engaging and varied.

The virtual classroom observation data also revealed that learning tools such as graphics, games, music, and YouTube videos were predominantly used for ice breaking and brainstorming. Few of these were used for more critical learning tasks, such as analysis, evaluation, and creativity. Pre-service EFL teachers did not utilize the learning media optimally. For instance, at PST 8's second meeting, games were used to assess students' comprehension of the previous content, but they were not integrated into the main learning activities. PST 8 began the session by reviewing prior content with Quizizz. She asked questions to assess how well students remembered and understood the previous materials. Games and other technological applications can increase student engagement in classroom activities. Therefore, pre-service EFL teachers should utilize these specialized tools extensively because technological media encourages students to be more active in their learning (Jodoi et al., 2021).

The virtual classroom observation data demonstrated that pre-service EFL teachers did not execute all the activities from their lesson plans due to teaching obstacles. Pre-service EFL teachers faced several barriers, including students, teachers, time constraints, and technical issues. The activities that were not covered in the class were, for instance, students' production of descriptive texts depending on the theme selected by the teacher, which were included in PST 3's lesson plan. Still, this activity was not executed in classroom instruction due to time constraints.

The challenges of Integrating Critical Thinking into Reading Classrooms

The interview data showed that critical thinking integration into online reading classes presented several challenges for the participants. Pre-service EFL teachers cited four challenges of incorporating critical thinking into online reading classes. Factors include students' lack of motivation, lack of understanding, lack of self-confidence, teacher's limited knowledge, time constraint, and technical issues are all identified as obstacles.

Students

Pre-service EFL teachers identified that students' lack of motivation, lack of understanding, and lack of self-confidence are all the issues students must encounter. PST 1 and PST 2 believed that students' lack of motivation to share their opinions is one of the obstacles that must be faced:

It is not easy to get students to think critically since they tend to be walled off.
(PST 1/Interview/LoM 1)

Students are not accustomed to expressing their opinions. (PST
2/Interview/LoM 2)

In most cases, students were constrained and hesitant to engage in critical thinking. They are not accustomed to it; therefore, they prefer silence. The connection between motivation and critical thinking development was explained by Turner (1995) stated that when students are given opportunities for problem-solving, critical thinking, and individual methods, regardless of standard instructional patterns, their motivation increases and they become more strategic and effortful.

The second student's factor is lack of understanding. PST 3 argued that students did not engage in essential activities of thinking due to students' competence to understand information.

Usually, some students did not understand the questions due to a lack of knowledge of the material. (PST 3/Interview/LoU 1)

Several aspects must be considered at this point; the ability to comprehend and communicate something is closely tied to language competency but is not immediately related to a person's critical thinking skills. Critical thinking is not rooted in language proficiency (Wallace, 2003). A comprehension threshold must be surpassed to engage in critical thinking. Setyaningsih (2019) discovered that learners demonstrate a hint of critical thinking skills but are off-goal for various reasons. These include unfamiliarity with the covered issue, unaccustomed to critical thinking, misinterpretation of the problem, and inability to express ideas due to language barriers; for these reasons, material selection is essential for incorporating CT or CL into EFL classrooms (Setyaningsih, 2019).

The third student factor is a lack of self-confidence. PST 8 considered lack of confidence as a possible factor impeding students' critical thinking abilities.

Some students were still hesitant to answer questions and lacked the confidence to do so. (PST 8/Interview/LoSC 1)

The type of self-confidence mentioned by the participant is confidence in answering questions and expressing their critical opinions despite the possibility of unpleasant feedback. This type of confidence is pertinent to the idea of "confidence in reason" (Paul & Elder, 2013). However, Manalo and Sheppard (2016) claimed that students'

critical thinking engagement might be hindered by their L2 proficiency, which can contribute as a potential factor to their unwillingness to address questions.

Teacher

Inadequate technical knowledge for integrating critical thinking abilities creates obstacles that impede the integration of critical thinking skills. Due to the fact that teachers regularly face multiple challenges in the classroom, they must possess the ability to deal with them. The following excerpt supports this point:

During the learning process, when students did not respond to what I explained, I felt confused, and I tried several methods without success. I had no idea what else to do. (PST 6/Interview/IK)

The statement above indicated that PST 6 was not well-versed in the best methods that should be implemented in the classroom in order to encourage students' critical thinking skills. As learning facilitators, teachers must possess sufficient knowledge to facilitate successful learning and increase student participation in classroom activities. The fact that teachers play a significant role in critical thinking integration is similar to Gustine's (2018) statement that the incapacity of teachers to comprehend critical literacy has also become one of the impediments to critical thinking integration. Regarding teachers' function as transformative intellectuals (Johnson, 2006) whose learning emerges from and is supported by classroom and school experience, teachers' knowledge plays a significant role in integrating critical thinking into EFL classrooms.

Time constraints

Pre-service EFL teachers stated that time constraints are a barrier in their reading classes. Due to online learning, pre-service EFL teachers were assigned less time for teaching. The time allotted for each meeting is 40 minutes long. PST 8 claimed that it was insufficient to cover all the materials. She asserted that she had insufficient time to teach. In line with PST 8, PST 5 stated that the obstacle he found was the limited teaching time. Time constraint as a barrier to critical thinking integration is in accordance with Li's (2016) concept that time is a significant challenge for establishing critical thinking activities. Thus, teachers must maximize time to meet learning objectives in an online reading lesson with limited time.

Technical Issues

The next issue highlighted by the participants was an unstable internet connection. Pre-service EFL teachers noted that unstable internet connection hindered their teaching activities and student responses. As PST 7 said below:

The student's response was not as expected because of the unstable internet connection. (PST 7/Interview/IC 1)

When presenting lessons, pre-service EFL teachers believed that students did not respond as expected because the message was frequently not transmitted owing to network issues or disconnections. This problem affected the teaching and learning process. Due to digital media used in learning activities, the consideration of acceptable learning media and the selection of digital media for learning must consider activities such as accessibility, affordability, technology, interactivity, organization, and innovation (Susanty et al., 2021). Therefore, teachers must prepare alternative solutions when technical issues arise in their teaching activities. Rahman (2020) advised teachers to adopt well-equipped language learning platforms and educational institutions to train teachers and students to run online teaching-learning programs efficiently.

CONCLUSION

This study revealed that pre-service EFL teachers incorporate only a few tasks that support the higher cognitive function, such as applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating into their reading lesson plans. In addition, pre-service teachers employed a more significant portion on remembering and understanding. Consequently, the cognitive activities associated with 'applying' to 'creating' must be intensified. Pre-service EFL teachers need to add more activities and tasks to develop students' critical thinking in reading classrooms. Furthermore, pre-service EFL teachers identified challenges when integrating critical thinking into online reading classes, including students' lack of motivation, comprehension, self-confidence, insufficient teacher knowledge, time constraints, and technical issues.

The research findings led to various theoretical contributions for EFL teachers, pre-service EFL teachers, and teacher training institutions. The result of the study provides insight for EFL teachers and pre-service EFL teachers about the knowledge of critical thinking integration into lesson plans and reading classroom instructions. Identifying critical thinking integration barriers encourages teachers to anticipate

similar challenges in their instructional activities and devise solutions. Additionally, the findings imply that teacher training institutions should focus on strengthening the critical thinking skills of pre-service EFL teachers to integrate critical thinking skills into EFL classrooms successfully.

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Lecturers' Challenges and Strategies in Teaching Maritime English Online to Students with Low English Proficiency

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the problems faced by ESP lecturers when teaching low English proficiency students during online Maritime English lessons and their strategies in dealing with the problems. A questionnaire with 6 open-ended questions was distributed to 9 Maritime English lecturers from 6 different Maritime Polytechnics in Indonesia. A follow-up interview was conducted with 4 lecturers to obtain more detailed information regarding their online teaching practices, especially the difficulties and the strategies to mitigate them. The findings of this study revealed three main problems faced by the lecturers. Firstly, students were reluctant to interact and participate in class activities. Secondly, students showed low motivation and interest in learning English. Thirdly, the lecturers needed extra time to explain the teaching materials. To overcome the problems, the lecturers used various texts, pictures, videos, or online platforms to expose students to maritime vocabulary. They also grouped the lower proficiency students with the higher proficiency students in a collaborative activity, designed class activities based on students' learning styles, and employed various scaffolding techniques.

Keywords: English for Specific Purposes (ESP) teaching, low English proficiency, Maritime English, online learning.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching English for Specific Purposes (ESP) has become a great challenge for many English lecturers. Different from general English courses, ESP teaching involves a more specific register in which the course is aimed to assist students to master English and use the language in a specific environment e.g., English in Banking, English in Medicine, English in Aviation, etc. (Mauludin, 2021). In ESP teaching, classroom instructions and activities are designed based on the communication needs of students in a specific context. Students are expected to have higher motivation when joining an ESP course since the course is relevant to their needs. However, reality sometimes does not meet expectations. There are various problems identified during ESP teaching practices that may hinder the effectiveness of the course. Some of the major issues are the ESP curriculum which is too general and does not cover students' specific needs (Poedjiastutie & Oliver, 2017), lecturers' limited pedagogical and content knowledge (Pazoki & Alemi, 2019; Poedjiastutie & Oliver, 2017), and irrelevant and unauthentic materials (Lee, 2016). The quality of the students' input also complicates the situation in which many students with low English proficiency consider ESP courses too difficult for them, and thus feel demotivated and sometimes frustrated when joining the course (Belyaeva, 2015). The importance of General English proficiency in supporting ESP learning has been highlighted by Martinovic and Poljakovic (in Pazoki & Alemi, 2019). They found that students' low general English proficiency affects students' motivation in learning ESP and inhibits their active participation in the class activities.

Students' low general English proficiency has caused a lot of problems in ESP teaching. Many ESP courses have shifted from specialized language instruction toward the development of general English knowledge (Belyaeva, 2015). The lower-level students perceive specialized courses with highly technical vocabulary and the discourse are too difficult for them. In other words, they are not ready to join ESP courses due to their low general English proficiency. As a result, the lecturers often revert to the materials of basic English and cannot fully cover the ESP materials (Poedjiastutie, 2017). This situation can hamper the effectiveness of ESP teaching and in the end, can fail the learning objectives.

Maritime English (ME) with its distinctive vocabulary and specialized expressions is a branch of ESP that is used widely in the Maritime industry. It covers a wide scope, ranging from the language of highly technical written genres to simplified and standardized spoken contexts. In written Maritime English, various technical words and phrases related to the nautical and marine engineering fields are commonly used. For example, when describing the different parts of vessels, the movements of vessels, the repair and maintenance of engines, etc. In spoken Maritime English, the range of lexical choices is more limited. The language is simplified since it usually deals with the safety and security of the ship's operation. The spoken messages are primarily used in the "here and now" context. The use of imperative and performative in the present situation is dominant (Ahmmed et al., 2020; Franceschi, 2014).

The globalization era has narrowed the barrier across nations, and international shipping has become very common. Nowadays, there are many crews that come from different countries working together on a vessel. When working under pressure, the crews often simplify or even change the common language to fulfil their duties (Demydenko, 2012). Communication breakdown might happen because of difficulties in understanding each other intentions. The failure in communication due to the low English proficiency of seafarers has been considered one of the main factors contributing to maritime accidents (James et al., 2018). Thus, Maritime English proficiency to an agreed level is essential to ensure the safety of the ship's operation (Shi & Fan, 2021). Maritime English teaching then becomes significant to equip seafarers with skills to communicate effectively with people of different nationalities who speak different languages. As mandated by the International Maritime Organization, seafarers of all ranks must be able to conduct clear and understandable communications using English, both in written and oral form (Zhang & Cole, 2018). Maritime Education and Training institutions then play a very significant role in ensuring that students can master the necessary knowledge and skills when working on board the ships (Hrnić, 2021).

Maritime English is one of the primary subjects taught in Maritime education and training institutions. In Indonesia, there are several Maritime

Polytechnics that provide maritime education and training for students who want to pursue a career as seafarers. All of the polytechnics employ a boarding school system that requires the students to stay in a dormitory during their studies. The students have to follow the simulation of living onboard a ship by following certain procedures and schedules. They have to obey the rules set by institutions that regulate their uniform, their interaction with other students and lecturers, their daily activities (including classroom study time, physical training time, mealtime, etc.), and many more. When the COVID-19 pandemic struck, many educational institutions had to switch from face-to-face learning to emergency remote learning (Choi & Chung, 2021). The maritime polytechnics had to send the students back home and continued the process of study in the online learning environment. For English lecturers, this situation has brought a greater challenge (Batu et al., 2021).

The challenges of online language teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic have drawn the interest of numerous scholars in many parts of the world. In the Arabic setting, Hamad et al. (2021) involved 43 English instructors to complete a questionnaire aiming to explore 5 aspects of online language teaching, including the quality of teaching, students' interaction, learning outcomes, instructors' planning, and correction load, and macro and micro-skills. Their study revealed several major problems during online language teaching, including limited student-teacher interaction, difficulties in monitoring students' class participation and performance, and difficulties in assessing micro and macro skills. Online language teaching had also given "more burden" to the teachers since they had to spend more time and energy planning a lesson and preparing teaching materials (Hamad et al., 2021).

Gao and Zhang (2020) conducted a qualitative study to investigate the lecturers' perception of online language teaching in a Chinese university by interviewing three EFL lecturers. The lecturers perceived that their teaching plans were disrupted due to COVID-19 Pandemic and they were demanded to improve their information and communication technology (ICT) literacy to survive. Gao and Zhang's (2020) study also indicated the importance to understand students' learning needs, improve lecturers' proficiency in

conducting online teaching, and integrate traditional classroom teaching methods with online teaching practices.

Nugroho et al. (2021) conducted a similar study in the Indonesian context. They involved 27 Indonesian EFL lecturers in writing a self-reflection and joining a semi-structured interview. The study showed that many lecturers were not familiar with digital platforms used in online learning. They were unable to provide quick and direct feedback to students that have caused a lack of students' motivation and engagement during online class activities (Nugroho et al., 2021).

In the Korean context, Choi and Chung (2021) involved 7 EFL instructors in an in-depth interview to explore the challenges and strategies of online language teaching and learning in an English language program in South Korea. They reported problems with interaction and collaborative activities as the major challenges faced by the instructors. As remedies, the instructors used several strategies, such as encouraging the students to turn on the camera and asking them to use non-verbal communication cues such as thumbs up. They also instructed students to collaborate in writing a summary of their group work using Google Docs, etc (Choi & Chung, 2021).

In Vietnam, Hung (2021) explored the difficulties of online language teaching as well as its advantages. Involving 15 English lecturers, he conducted a study at the Center for Foreign Languages, Can Tho University in Vietnam. His study revealed 5 major difficulties faced by the lecturers, including students' and lecturers' access to technology, maintaining students' motivation and engagement, assessing students' progress, lecturers' lack of digital pedagogical competence, and increased workload and stress. However, the lecturers also admitted that online language teaching could bring advantages, including flexibility and improving autonomy, motivation, self-determination, and self-regulation among lecturers and students (Hung, 2021).

Many studies have explored the challenges of online language teaching. However, studies regarding Maritime English teaching are still rare and studies focusing on low-English proficiency students in Maritime Polytechnics are not yet available. Low English proficiency students in this research refer to students who have a low level of General English. Students'

general English level that affects their ESP learning has been discussed by Poedjiastutie and Oliver (2017). However, their discussion only covered students at an Indonesian university. This study aims to provide a more specific context by exploring the problems of ESP teaching in Maritime Polytechnics by involving the lecturers' perspectives. There are two research questions guiding the current study: 1) What are the problems faced by the English lecturers when teaching Maritime English online to students with Low English Proficiency? 2) What strategies are used by the English lecturers to overcome the problems?

RESEARCH METHOD

This research employed a qualitative descriptive method. One fundamental characteristic of this research is the naturalistic data taken under real-world conditions (Creswell, 2012; Yin, 2011). Compared to other types of qualitative research, the qualitative descriptive method is more descriptive rather than interpretive in focus. In qualitative descriptive research, data were collected and analyzed qualitatively by identifying themes or patterns (Nassaji, 2015). In this research, the authors attempt to describe a phenomenon by understanding the lecturers' opinions and perspectives regarding their teaching experience.

Research participants

To select the research participants, the authors used the purposive sampling technique. The selection of the participants was based on the consideration that they could provide the authors with the "best" information (Kumar, 2011). Problems with low proficiency students in Maritime Polytechnics have been discussed with some of the lecturers during informal discussions. Following up the discussions, the authors involved nine Maritime English lecturers who teach in seven maritime polytechnics under the Ministry of Transportation in Indonesia for the Applied Bachelor program. Their total teaching experience ranges from 4 years to 18 years. Four of them joined a follow-up interview after completing the questionnaire. The participants, their teaching experience, and their campus locations are shown in Table 1.

Table 1.
The research participants

No	Name	Gender	Teaching experience	Campus Location	Remarks
1.	SK	Female	6 years	Jakarta	Joined the follow-up interview
2.	AH	Female	4 years	Semarang	Joined the follow-up interview
3.	NR	Female	18 years	Barombong	Joined the follow-up interview
4.	DA	Female	4 years	Banten	Joined the follow-up interview
5.	TR	Female	17 years	Jakarta	-
6.	FT	Female	5 years	Semarang	-
7.	SL	Female	10 years	Makassar	-
8.	HN	Female	8 years	Aceh	-
9.	SM	Female	10 years	Banten	-

Data collection

The authors prepared a questionnaire using Google Forms, which consisted of six open-ended questions. The open-ended questionnaire was aimed to enable the participants to share their experience on their own terms within the format that facilitates the process of data analysis (Seixas et al., 2018). The questionnaire was used as a self-reflection for the lecturers to explore the difficulties they faced when teaching Maritime English online, especially to students with low English proficiency, and their strategies to counter the problems.

The questions in the questionnaire were as follows:

1. What do you think about the English proficiency level of your students?
1. What preparation do you make before teaching?
2. How do you conduct online Maritime English teaching? (synchronous/asynchronous, the duration of teaching, the delivery of the materials)
3. What teaching media do you use? To what extent the teaching media help you in teaching?
4. What difficulties do you face during online teaching? (Especially when dealing with the low English proficiency students)
5. What strategies do you use to handle the low English proficiency students?

At the end of the questionnaire, the lecturers were requested to join a follow-up interview. The interview was aimed to obtain more detailed and comprehensive information regarding the participants' online teaching experience. Four lecturers agreed to join the interview, which was conducted using the zoom meeting application. The interview was semi-structured and lasted for about 15 – 20 minutes. The interviews were recorded and transcribed.

Data analysis

In conducting the data analysis, the authors first downloaded the questionnaire results from Google Forms and transcribed the interview. The content Analysis (CA) protocol was used as a strategy for analyzing data (Leung & Chung, 2019). First, the authors read the questionnaire responses and the interview transcripts several times. In this step, small chunks or phrases with meaning were generated. After that, labels or codes were given to each chunk of data. The coded chunks were compared and contrasted against each other, and similar chunks were grouped to form conceptual categories. The categories were then compared to the related theories about the phenomenon. Finally, the authors summarize the findings and their implications on online ESP teaching practices.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In conducting online Maritime English teaching, the lecturers combined synchronous and asynchronous learning. They used various online learning platforms, such as Zoom, Google Class Room, Edlink, Quizizz, as well as the Learning Management System developed by the institution. They also used YouTube to find relevant teaching materials and a WhatsApp group to liaise with their students.

According to the lecturers, students' English proficiency level is varied, ranging from elementary to low-intermediate. As some of the lecturers mentioned in the questionnaire:

English language proficiency of our students is varied, depending on the program. Students of the regular program are quite good, but those of other programs have a very low English proficiency (NR).

In general, English proficiency level of our students is low-intermediate (TR).

In my opinion, the English proficiency level of our students varies. Some students are pretty good, but many others are still struggling with basic English (DA).

From the questionnaire, it can be concluded that the lecturers have to deal with students who have different levels of English proficiency. However, most of the students are in low proficiency levels.

The problems faced by the English lecturers when teaching Maritime English online to students with Low English Proficiency

The difference in students' ability has caused difficulty for the lecturers when conducting the teaching practices, especially when they have to deal with low English proficiency students. There are 3 (three) primary problems identified.

a. Students' lack of interaction and participation.

Students' lack of interaction and participation becomes the main issue reported by the lecturers. During synchronous learning using Zoom, students with low English proficiency often turned off their cameras. They tried to avoid direct interaction with the lecturers and were reluctant to involve in the online class activities.

As said by one of the lecturers:

Students with low proficiency were usually rather difficult to communicate with. They were reluctant to participate in teaching and learning activities. They just keep quiet and rarely speak up. They did not submit their assignments on time, and sometimes, did not submit the assignments at all (HN).

Another lecturer described her experience when asking questions to students.

One of the constraints of online learning was in the class discussion process. When I asked students: do you have any

questions regarding the materials today? They just kept silent and did not say a thing. However, when I gave them questions, they could not answer them correctly (DA).

Some students also used poor internet connections as an excuse for not being fully able to participate in the class. This problem was mentioned by TR.

Students with low English proficiency were usually passive and tend to be difficult to collaborate in the learning process. Some of them said that they had a poor internet connection (TR).

This problem caused difficulty for the lecturers to monitor students' attendance and performance, especially when students turned off their cameras during the video conferencing sessions. Do the students sit in front of their computers and give full attention to the lecturers? or do they scroll their Instagram and check their social media?

This problem was mentioned by AH and DA during the interview.

It was difficult for me to ensure whether all of the students really follow the lesson well (AH).

It was hard to make the class interactive. Students sometimes did not understand the materials, but they did not want to ask questions. Many were not serious when studying online because they felt that the lecturers could not supervise them directly (DA).

Regarding students' assignments, the lecturers reported plagiarism as the main issue. When students were given an assignment, some of them would wait for their friends to finish the assignment, copied it, and claimed it as their work. Realizing this, one of the lecturers (DA) said that she asked the students to hand-write their assignments instead of typing them with the hope that even though the student copied their friends' answers, at least they still could learn something. However, some

students also submitted the “wrong” tasks. DA said that perhaps the students thought that she would not check all of their work, so they did not give their best effort in doing the assignments.

I found it difficult when it comes to giving students assignments. Perhaps some of them think that I will not check all of their work. They did not do the assignment properly. They just copied their friends' works or they submitted unrelated documents (DA).

Students' lack of interaction and participation has made it difficult for the lecturers to monitor students' real performance. The lecturers could not explore students' abilities and monitor their progress.

This finding supports the study conducted by Habil and Lifa (2020), who investigated classroom management problems. They found that students' behavioral problems (for example students do not follow instructions and refuse to cooperate in any way) have become one of the greatest challenges for the lecturers in managing their class.

b. Students' low motivation and interest in learning English.

The lecturers also reported that the low proficiency students had low motivation and interest in learning English. English is probably not their favorite subject. This problem was told by NR who has been teaching in Maritime education institutions for 18 years.

Most of my students have low English proficiency. As we know that in our country, maritime colleges become the second option. High school graduates who are brighter and have better academic achievement usually choose more reputable universities to continue their education. If I ask my students, do you like studying English? I believe that 70% of them will answer 'no'. If my students are sitting in front of me right now, it is not because they are willing, but because they have to (NR).

Another lecturer also mentioned the problems when dealing with low-motivated students:

It is hard for me when I have to teach a class in which the students have different English proficiency levels. The students with a higher proficiency level usually do not experience significant difficulties. However, the low English proficiency students need extra effort to keep up with their friends. But many of them have low motivation for learning. When the students encounter difficulties, they tend to give up easily (AH).

Many studies have highlighted the importance of motivation in foreign language learning (Bower, 2019; Thuan, 2021). There are several characteristics of motivated learners. They have a positive task orientation, ego-involvement, need for achievement, high aspirations, goal orientation, perseverance, and tolerance of ambiguity (Mohammed, 2020). However, the low proficiency students lack those characteristics which hinder them from achieving their best performance.

c. Need more time to explain the teaching materials.

When explaining the teaching materials to the low proficiency students, the lecturers needed extra time. They had to prepare their lessons well to make the teaching and learning activities as effective as possible. As two of the respondents mentioned in the interview:

Teaching students with low English proficiency is full of challenges. We need more time to explain the materials to make them understand (NR).

When I explain the teaching materials, the students with higher proficiency usually can understand the materials easily. However, I need to repeat the explanation several times for students with lower proficiency levels. In an online class, it is more difficult because I cannot make sure they listen to my explanation (DA).

This problem has caused a dilemma for the lecturers who have to keep up with the lesson plans. If they slow the lesson to adjust the speed of the low proficiency students, the targeted materials might not be achieved at the end of the semester. However, if they go at a normal speed, the low proficiency students might not be able to catch all the materials.

Several scholars have explored lecturers' difficulties in conducting online language learning. A study conducted by Aziz et al. (2021) showed that lecturers struggled with the changing curriculum, lesson preparations, giving feedback, and online marking assessments. The finding of this study indicated that time spent for preparing the lessons, giving feedback, and grading the students may also be a source of stress for the lecturers.

The strategies used by the English lecturers to overcome the problems

The challenges faced by the lecturers have encouraged them to find solutions to overcome the problems. Some lecturers employ similar strategies, but they also have more specific strategies to be implemented in their classes. The strategies described by the lecturers are summarized as follows:

- a. Using various texts, pictures, videos, or online platforms to expose students to the maritime vocabulary.

Maritime English has a very specific and technical vocabulary which might be too advanced for the students with low English proficiency. To improve students' English proficiency, the lecturers often focused on improving students' vocabulary. As mentioned by AH during the interview:

My strategy is to focus on vocabulary because I think vocabulary is the basis of learning English. If students have already mastered adequate vocabulary, it will be easier for me to teach grammar. I must give students exposure to the vocabulary. I used various texts and videos which are related to maritime. The students need to

read or watch the video many times to familiarize themselves with the vocabulary (AH).

The current study supports the studies regarding the importance of vocabulary in language teaching and learning. Vocabulary is considered a core feature of language proficiency. Language learners need to understand at least 98% of the words to be able to comprehend a message without assistance (Bai, 2018; Bergström et al., 2021).

To expose students to maritime vocabulary, there were various strategies used by the lecturers. Some lecturers used YouTube videos to introduce students to maritime context and vocabulary. In the digital era, the use of YouTube has become popular among language lecturers. There are many studies regarding the use of YouTube. Most scholars reported the platform's effectiveness due to its accessibility and authenticity (Simbolon & Yusnita, 2020).

Besides YouTube, some of the lecturers also used online quiz platforms such as Quizizz and game-based learning platforms such as Kahoot. This research supports the findings of Sartini's study (2020). She found that the use of Kahoot! as an interactive online learning platform is proven effective to improve students' vocabulary mastery of Maritime English. Besides that, it can improve students' motivation and interest in learning English and encourage students' interaction and participation.

- b. Considering the learning style of students in designing the teaching and learning activities.

The learning style is one of the important aspects that influence the students' learning process. Every person has different preferences on how he/she receives information. How an individual acquires, retains, and retrieves information is a learning style (Alhourani, 2021). When designing teaching and learning activities, lecturers are often not aware that students may have different learning styles. However, one of the lecturers mentioned that she tried to understand the characteristic of her students when designing classroom activities.

I understand that my students may have different learning styles that make them have different preferences in the class activities. For example, when I say 'starboard is the right side of a vessel', auditory students will understand immediately. However, visual students need pictures to help them understand the same things. So, when we introduce vocabulary to students, we have to utilize various teaching aids. Using pictures and videos will help a lot (NR).

The issue of students' learning style, which affects their language learning, has drawn the interest of a number of scholars. They highlighted the significance of understanding students' learning styles that can help the lecturers design more effective instruction and more engaging class activities (Balci, 2017; Payaprom & Payaprom, 2020; Salam et al., 2020).

- c. Grouping lower proficiency students with higher proficiency students in a collaborative activity.

Students with low English proficiency often have affective barriers during the learning process. They often feel anxious and try to avoid interaction with the lecturers during class activities. When given a difficult task, they tend to give up easily. This problem was mentioned by AH during the interview.

In my opinion, students with low proficiency have low resilience. When they face difficulty, they quickly say, "I cannot do this". If only they give more effort and push themselves to the limit, I believe they can accomplish the target (AH).

Students with low English proficiency often realize that they have a very limited vocabulary and grammar. They also find it difficult to pronounce many words in English. Thus, they tend to keep silent and become passive in class. Group activity can become one of the solutions to reduce students' anxiety and boost their confidence. Many scholars have revealed the benefits of group work for students. Group work can create

a more relaxed learning atmosphere and thus reduce students' anxiety. Collaborative learning can make students feel more secure and decrease their concerns about negative performance evaluation (M. C. Liu et al., 2018).

One of the lecturers shared her experience regarding grouping students.

I implement collaborative learning in my class. I group the low proficiency students with the high proficiency students so they can collaborate and help each other. In a class discussion, a group that only consists of low proficiency students tends to be passive. On the other hand, a group that consists of high proficiency students tends to dominate (NR).

In grouping the students, NR mixed the low proficiency students with the high proficiency students with the purpose that they can help each other. This is in line with studies conducted by Kadir and Salija (2018) and Niu et al. (2018). They found that heterogenous grouping by combining students' abilities has a better impact than homogenous grouping. In collaborative learning, students with low proficiency levels can get benefit from heterogeneous grouping. They can receive help from their friends and learn more things. In the end, it can improve their self-confidence and reduce their anxiety.

d. Providing appropriate scaffolding for the students.

Lecturer's scaffolding is very important in language learning, especially for low proficiency students. The students need lecturers' assistance to help them learn new skills or concepts and accomplish their learning objectives (Mahan, 2022).

Some lecturers shared their experience of giving scaffolding to their students.

To help students understand the materials, I simplify the vocabulary based on the students' ability. For example, I give the basic vocabulary first. After they master the vocabulary, I move to

the next level. I group the vocabulary based on the difficulty level and the frequency used in the maritime field (AH).

I use repetition as the strategy to teach students with low proficiency. The theory says that students need to be exposed to new vocabulary 7 to 12 times before they can save them in their memory. I usually give various activities and tasks to students to give them exposure. I also use pictures and videos to help students understand the materials (NR).

There are a number of studies regarding scaffolding in language learning. Simplifying the language and using visuals help students to understand the teaching materials. The findings of this study support the studies conducted by Li and Zhang (2022), Liu et al. (2022), and Yildiz and Celik (2020). They agreed that scaffolding is a beneficial tool that encourages students' interaction and participation in the language classroom. The lecturers can select and implement the most appropriate scaffolding techniques based on the student's needs and characteristics.

CONCLUSION

Teaching students with low-English proficiency is very challenging for lecturers, especially during ESP teaching. Special attention must be given to ensure that all students can fulfil the learning objectives. This study has revealed three main problems faced by the lecturers when teaching Maritime English online to students with low English proficiency: students' lack of interaction and participation, students' low motivation and interest in learning English, and extra time needed by the lecturers to explain the teaching materials.

This study brings several pedagogical implications to Maritime English teaching. Firstly, lecturers need to be creative to explore the most suitable techniques and strategies implemented in their classroom. The lecturers can use various texts, pictures, videos, or online platforms to expose students to maritime vocabulary. Secondly, the lecturers need to consider students' learning styles and preferences in designing classroom activities. Students

may have different characteristics and it is important that the lecturers can design the most appropriate activities that can accommodate all students. Thirdly, the lecturers can employ various scaffolding techniques to assist students' learning. For instance, they can group lower proficiency students with higher proficiency students in a collaborative activity as one of the strategies to improve students' motivation and reduce their anxiety. This study also highlights the importance of lecturers' technological and pedagogical knowledge and skills in supporting their teaching practices.

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An Investigation of the Integration of Inter-semiotic Complementarity in Iraqi EFL Textbook

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Abstract

Nowadays, multimodal texts are widely used in the media, schools, and daily life. There have been several studies on nonverbal semiotics in multi-semiotic texts. This study examines the complementarity of verbal and visual semiotic modes in an Iraqi EFL textbook. Royce's (2007) inter-semiotic complementarity and Kress Van Leeuwen's (1996) structure of information value were used to analyse an Iraqi EFL textbook titled English for Iraq (Garnet, 2017). According to the analysis, the entire textbook is not built on a page-by-page path that allows linear and nonlinear reading. Although the information layout varies from page to page, the overall structure of the textbook image allows for a linear reading path from start to finish. Texts in multimodal EFL are required. This study investigated the relationship between verbal text and image in terms of address, social distance, and participation because multimodality conveys teachers' perspectives on language learning (the extent to which the reader engages with what is represented). This study's sample includes analytical units. Each verbal and visual sample text-image relationship was determined, and the participation and address levels were comparable. We discovered that social distance favors divergence over convergence in English education and learning. Young students select, design, and employ multimodal textbook materials.

Keywords: multimodality, inter-semiotic complementarity, semiotics' mode, EFL, school textbooks

INTRODUCTION

The classical intellectuals of the fourth-century B.C.C. emphasized the possible influences of voice, gesture, and expression on the art of the speech-making, which is when the multimedia concept was proposed. Humans have employed visual, aural, kinaesthetic, and other senses to create and receive literature. People have made meaning from ancient narratives to modern web browsers through visuals, sounds, gestures, and touch (Eisenmann & Summer, 2020). Because demands and aspirations are given to resources, technology, and internet access, cultural ideas and values influence textual production and consumption. Multimedia discourse has earned great interest since O'Toole and Michael (1994), Kress and van Leeuwen (2006), and others began using the term. Research topics include academic discourse, such as mathematical discourse (Nhat, 2017; O'Halloran, 2004) or textbooks (Unsworth, Cope, & Nicholls, 2019), as well as speech for entertainment, such as music videos and graphic novels, or advertisements, to name a few (Rajendra, 2015). Students with varying levels of education will benefit most from this type of research using illustrated books. English textbooks in educational institutions include text and visual images. Both of them have been used to construct meaning. As Kress and van Leeuwen (2006, p. 2) explain, "visual structures realize meanings as linguistic structures do also, and thereby point to different interpretations of experience and different forms of social interaction." This means that applying visual images to language teaching material has a different experience for students because they may connect it with their experiences (Nurul Hidayati et al., 2020). Some inter-semiotic studies have focused on textbooks for students' universities. Wignell (2011) revealed that science authors use evaluative language in textbooks for university writing. Liu and Qu (2014) state that the EFL textbook series for Chinese College students are similar because their representative multimodal texts are visually coherent for inter-semiotic semantic relations. These previous studies are insightful, but they focus on EFL textbooks. Recent research aims to fill this gap by investigating how inter-semiotic contributes to meaning-making in ELT textbooks used by foreign language learners. Each of these resources intersemiotically contributes to the construction of meaning through the meaning potentials of

that resource (Nurul Hidayati et al., 2020; O'Halloran, 2011). For this purpose, visual images offer text to show how visual images and languages may contribute to the processing of meaning-making. Multimodal literacy has gained more attention among literacy educators, researchers, and curriculum authorities (Damayanti, 2014; Hermawan & Sukyadi, 2017; Unsworth et al., 2019). As students' interactions with multimodal texts in recent years are increasingly pervasive, the focus of literacy in school can no longer be limited to the reading and writing of printed texts such as school textbooks. The current study is an attempt to justify and answer the question; what kinds of reading path patterns are used to track the flow of knowledge deriving from the language and image resources in Iraqi EFL textbooks and their potential for practical use in EFL classrooms?

As an alternative, students need support in making meanings from multimodal texts that integrate images and language (e.g., picture books) and from online and virtual settings (e.g., social media, websites, and wikis). In teaching English as a foreign language, picture books have been widely used to assist with children's language learning. Images, typically rich in picture books, are usually used to help students identify new lexical items as they provide context to create meaning (Lee, 2015; Mourão, 2016; Sun, 2015). While images tend to be treated as an 'addition' to words, meaning-making in picture books depends on pictures and words (Unsworth, 2006). Using picture books in EFL classrooms, thus, entails the necessity for EFL teachers to be concerned with developing their own and their students' multimodal literacy. Multimodal textbooks require skills in interpreting visual and verbal meanings. Using multimodal textbooks in EFL classrooms requires teachers and students to develop multimodal literacy. In response to the need for developing multimodal literacy, the study investigates reading path patterns to track the flow of knowledge deriving from the language and image resources in Iraqi EFL textbooks, as well as their potential for practical use in EFL classrooms (Grunbaum, 2021; Reynolds, 2015).

The current study is based on two SFL concepts: inter-semiotic complementarity by Royce (2007b) and compositional meanings in visual design by Kress and van Leeuwen (2006). These conceptual theories relate to the study's primary objective, mapping a children's book's reading path. The

reading path is the order and direction in which the reader approaches the text or images on the page (O'Halloran, Marissa, Podlasov, & Tan, 2013). The reading path is then divided into linear and non-linear paths. A linear reading path involves sequentially reading the text. In western societies, linear texts are usually read from left to right and top-to-bottom. Unidirectional or closed text is linear. The author of the page determines the reading path. A typical example of a linear text is a newspaper article without pictures. In non-linear reading, the reader engages with the text non-linearly and non-sequentially. Multidirectional or open text is non-linear text in which the reader chooses a reading path. Websites are examples of non-linear texts. Pictures in the textbooks sit between linear and non-linear texts because texts and images co-create meaning. Most authors decide how to read a story's words, but their readers can interact with the pictures.

Inter-semiotic Complementarity

Multimodal textbooks use language and images to communicate. It is essential to understand both sources by comparing them. The study uses inter-semiotic complementarity (Royce, 2007b) to understand language-image relationships. Royce (2007b) offers Inter-semiotic Complementarity as a multimodal analysis framework to help EFL teachers develop their students' multimodal literacies and design a pedagogical metalanguage to aid learning. This framework extends Halliday's SFL theory, which emphasizes the role of social contexts in constructing and interpreting meaning (Halliday & Hasan, 1985; Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). Meaning resources in SFL theory are ideational, interpersonal, and textual. The ideational metafunction represents our world experience (doing, thinking, relating, etc.) involving processes, participants, and circumstances. Interpersonal meaning expresses our attitudes and opinions. Textual meaning creates a coherent, cohesive text in context.

Royce (2007b, p. 66) refers to visual metafunctions as ideational-representational, interpersonal, and textual-compositional. Royce (2007b) suggests that focusing on ideational inter-semiotic complementarity may help EFL learners extract informational content from English language learning materials. This paper examines the idea of inter-semiotic complementarity in a multimodal textbook using Royce's (2007b)

framework. Ideational inter-semiotic analysis begins with identifying verbal meanings; each clause is analyzed in terms of its transitivity features, which include processes, participants, and circumstances (additional information related to where, when, and how). The next step is to identify the represented participants' visual message elements (VMEs), activities, circumstances, and attributes. VMEs are then grouped into lexical inventories and compared to verbal items for similar or differentiated meanings. Understanding frameworks is also needed to evaluate a textbook using multimodal text analysis. This area has influential figures. Kress and van Leeuwen's (2006, 2021) grammar of visual design and Royce's inter-semiotic complementarity were used in this study (1998, 2002, and 2007). These two frameworks cover ideational, interpersonal, and textual metafunctions under Halliday's systemic functional linguistics (Halliday, 1994; Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004, 2014). In this regard, the ideational metafunction concerns "reality, events, and experiences," the interpersonal metafunction concerns entrenching and keeping social rapports, and the textual metafunction concerns the organization of discourse through which "information flow" is managed and kept. Visual meanings and their relationships to verbal meanings are also elaborated under the notion of inter-semiotic complementarity, which in this regard is focused on the ideational metafunction. Royce (2007) posits that visual message elements (henceforth VMEs) capture the visual components that "carry semantic qualities, and these semantic properties or meanings may be realized in a number of visual ways." Once VMEs have been derived, they can be compared to the meanings expressed by textual semiotics. Identity, activity, context, and attributes can be used to code both the VMEs and the textual meanings:

Identification: represented participants, such as who or what is in the visual frame.

Activity: actions that were taking place.

Circumstances: The context of a situation, such as where, who, and how.

Attributes: The qualities and characteristics of the participants (Royce, 2015).

Royce (2007b) recommends using Halliday and Hasan's analysis of cohesion in a text, such as repetition (R), synonymy (S), antonymy (A),

hyponymy (H), meronymy (M), and collocation (C). Visual ideational meanings are also analyzed using Kress and van Leeuwen's (2006) narrative representation. It is used to examine how images represent our experiences of the world by identifying lines or "vectors" that emanate from participants or other elements in the image.

COMPOSITIONAL MEANING

Kress and van Leeuwen (2006) developed the fundamental concept of conceptualizing compositions in a static or page-based multimodal image. As a page-based multimodal text's overall composition, the representational and interactive elements relate to each other and integrate into a meaningful whole through compositional patterns (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2006). Three interrelated systems connect these functions: information value, salience, and framing. The information value of a page focuses on the value of the various sections of the page. Image salience refers to an image's ability to stand out visually. For example, a frame's presence or absence could disconnect or connect an image to its surroundings.

Table 1.
The inter-semiotic analysis framework by Royce, 2006.

Verbal meanings	Semantic relationships	Visual Message Elements (VMEs)
Lexical elements which relate to the visual meanings. These lexical items arise according to:	Various lexico-semantic ways of relating the experiential and logical content or subject matter represented or projected in both visual and verbal modes through the intersemiotic sense relation of:	Variations occur according to the coding orientation.
<i>Process</i> : what action is taking place, events, states, types of behaviours	<i>Repetition</i> : identical experiential meaning	<i>Activity (Process)</i> : what action <i>Circumstances</i> : where, who with, by what means
<i>Participant</i> : who or what is involved in any activity or process	<i>Synonymy</i> : the same or similar experiential meaning	<i>Identification (Participant)</i> : who or what
<i>Circumstances</i> : where, who with, and by what means are the activities being carried out	<i>Antonymy</i> : opposite experiential meaning	<i>Attributes</i> : the qualities and characteristics
<i>Attributes</i> : what are the qualities and characteristics of the participants	<i>Meronymy</i> : the relation between the part and whole of something	
	<i>Hyponymy</i> : the relation between a general class of something and its sub-classes	
	<i>Collocation</i> : an expectancy or high probability to co-occur in a field or subject area	

RESEARCH METHOD

The selection of Images from the Iraqi EFL textbook

The primary data for this study are a sample of pages from Iraqi EFL textbooks published by Garnet Education in 2017. The Garnet Education is a UK-based independent ELT publisher with decades of experience. Garnet Education, which focuses on English for Specific Purposes and English for Academic Purposes, works extensively with the Iraqi Ministry of Education to design EFL textbooks for the Iraqi schooling system. The story's central plot revolves around a variety of everyday concerns. As life skills topics, "cultural" practices vary from place to place. The attire and demeanor of the people in the various locations, topics, and his home country illustrate this contrast. For example the Japanese do not practice customs such as greeting visitors with politeness, marching, singing or eating with finesse, while the Iraqi culture shows the opposite as a part of their heredity customs.

They are transforming from inappropriate figures into a moral message emphasizing the importance of inner qualities over outer ones, time, and technology. One of the figures can acquire a deeper understanding of the moral message conveyed by the images by examining the images and the accompanying text (Christie & Derewianka, 2008; Painter, Unsworth, 2006). Students can learn to comprehend multimodal texts by recognizing characters and plot structures in written texts. Additionally, they can do so by analyzing visual representations and presentation order. Even though the written texts describe a photograph of an outsider, the visual details make the photograph appear even more out of place.

Data Collection

A qualitative, descriptive SF-MDA study was conducted. It was deemed a suitable approach because, according to O'Halloran and Fei (2014), it can be adopted to analyze multimodal texts ranging from two dimensions, such as printed or digital text, to three dimensions, such as arts, texts or gestures, and time-based texts, including music, film, television, etc. (Knox, 2013). The Systemic functional-multimodal discourse analysis (SF-MDA) henceforth SF-MDA can also be used to understand the meaning systems of image and verbal texts and a text's social functions (Jewitt, Bezemer, & O'Halloran, 2016). In

this study, the two modes' interpersonal meanings were compared. Also, several frameworks were used to interpret the interpersonal meanings of visual and verbal texts and their interrelationships. In this case, they were Halliday (1994) and Halliday & Matthiessen's (2004, 2014) interpersonal metafunction of systemic functional linguistics, Kress and van Leeuwen's (2006, 2021) interactive meanings of visual design grammar, and Royce's (1998, 2007) intersemiotic complementarity.

The examined artefact is a multimodal text in the form of a discussion accompanied by an image from an Iraqi EFL textbook titled *English for Iraq: Student's Book for six preparatory school students* (Garnet, 2014). The textbook was chosen because it is used in preparatory schools in northern Iraq (except in the Kurdistan Region). It was also designed and introduced by a reputable publisher with credible and reliable authors; one of them even had global teaching experience and it included artefacts in the form of discussion, covering not only verbal texts but also images, which is another reason why textbook selection should be scrutinized.

The identification of the design of each image was required to select the analyzed pages even though the study did not focus on genre analysis, and the data sets comprise two spreads (a double-page) and a page representing the Orientation and Complication stages of the story. These stages were selected as they provide rich analysis and valuable development for investigating the reading path patterns. Due to the copyright issue, this paper does not supplement the corresponding multimodal textbook pages. Instead, graphs and black and white sketches of the pages or spreads are supplied to visualize the mapping and visual analysis.

The three data sets are displayed in Figures 1–3. Figure 1 illustrates a spread that introduces the story's characters. Figure 3 displays a page that focuses on the characters' activity. Figure 3 illustrates another extent that presents an attempted solution made by the story's main characters.

In different shots there is plenty of information that needs to be clarified by both the teacher and the students. Clearly, this depends on how much knowledge there is and how each part of the educational situation is cultivated about English language.

Figure 1. An image presenting the different stages of the main characters of reading part of unit 2. Adopted from Iraqi EFL textbook for preparatory school.

Figure 2. Here is the image and the text are complete each other as the text describing what happening with the above shots for a student called Sami who is describing his school work.

Figure 3. An image of three shots about special school types which is unfamiliar in the Iraqi context.

PROCEDURES AND DATA ANALYSIS

The understanding process of the contents of images of study is constructed by two factors—the layout of the language and image content and the interrelationship between the meanings of language and image on specific pages or spreads. Both accounts contribute to the overall construction of the narrative's reading path. Before a detailed analysis of how the information value is organized and how each page's language and image elements work together, a general observation was made about how the school topic was chosen on the spot. The study combines two fundamental methodologies: the structure of information value proposed by Kress and van Leeuwen (2021) and the inter-semiotic complementarity proposed by Royce (2007a, 2007b). To unpack the information value and complementarity relations between inter-semiotics, Kress and van Leeuwen (2006) explain how the placements of elements (participants and syntagms that relate them to each other and the viewer) provide them with the specific informational values associated with the various 'zones' of the image: left and right sides, top and bottom margins, and center and margin.

Second, the relationship between the language and images in the multimodal textbook is examined. Royce's (2007b) research identifies these

connections as cohesive mechanisms realized through repetition (R), synonymy (S), antonymy (A), hyponymy (H), meronymy (M), and metonymy (M). There is a collocation (C) between language and image resources on the same page. After the analysis, the image in the textbook's overall reading path map will be created. In addition, classroom applications of this reading map's pedagogical implications are formulated.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The inter-semiotic complementarity analysis in this paper focuses on the stages in which the contrast between the characters in Denise's family and friends is established to build and release the tension encountered by the main characters. Denise's story introduces the characters regarding their identities, locations, and activities. In Figure 2, the identity of the characters is introduced on a double-page spread that depicts a single visual element spanning the two pages and one separated textual element on each page. The texts are annotated in the figure as Text A and B. The verbal texts identify the single girl as 'Denise' and the other five as 'her companions.' On the left page, the five girls are shown looking away from Denise. On the right page, they are shown looking at her.

In terms of verbal elements, each clause in the textbooks (Texts A, B1, and B2) was analyzed to identify the represented meanings. Figure 5 presents the analysis of the first data set as follows.

Table 2.

An introductory analysis of verbal element in the first page

Text 1		
Her companions Denise	were unnamed Process: identifying anonymously	Goodly, Lovely, Angel, Neatly, and Perfect Value
Text B1		
Her name Denise	Was Process: identifying but unknown to the student	Denise Value
Text B2		
Unknown Carrier	Was Process: attributive	an odd person (at the image) might be identified later Attribute

The analysis shows that each clause in the text blocks construes the identification of the represented participants. Interestingly, the identifying clauses in texts A and B1 name the characters with referents that reflect their qualities. For example, each of the five shots is unnamed with proper nouns with excellent features such as 'lovely' and 'perfect.' On the other hand, the 'different' quality of the girl in the shots from other people is not only identified by her appearance but also by the classifying attribute of being 'unknown.'

Turning to visual elements, this spread of meaning includes two main participants, a group of three shots, and the image itself.

Table 3.

Summarises the analysis of visual meanings that focuses on the introduction to characters

Elements	Visual Realisations	Visual Transitivity Roles	Visual Message Elements (VMEs)
Identification	A schoolgirl	Reactor	girl's friends and family
Attribute	Solid-colored bow ties, false collar, curly hair		family values
Identification	A family	Phenomenon Actor	The Mom
Attribute	Plaid bow tie, yellow flowery shirt, colored T-shirt, dark skin and wide eyes		An outsider, happy
Identification	A classroom, and a teacher	Goal	Classroom context
Activity	Learning in a group	Non-transactional action process	Majority
Activity	Be a teacher, dreaming	Transactional-action process	Comfort
Circumstance	Working in the farm, learning, and dreaming to be a successful teacher	Manner	Superior

A group of people to schoolgirls' vector reveals transactional reaction processes. However, even though all the girls' bodies are pointing in the same general direction as the teacher and most of their eyes are closed and chins raised, a transactional reaction process can be seen proceeding from one particular girl's gaze and the beaks of two people in the group's

center. People in the picture (reactors) who see the phenomenon (Denise) as the undesirable other are having an exchange in this shot. While the little girl is assigned as a phenomenon, she is also an actor in an active process; that is, she works and studies. The main characters, the girl and her mother, are also contrasted by their attributes. Her uniformed, solid-colored bow ties and false collars make it easy for her co-workers to blend in with the background. All of them appear refined and conservative in this context. On the other hand, the girl with curly hair and a flowery Hawaiian shirt represents formality and simplicity, which are at odds with the landscape's dominant environment of everyday life procedures.

Bringing the verbal and visual elements together, the analysis of ideational-inter-semiotic complementarity indicates that the introduction page in this story provides more information than merely naming the characters. Table 4 displays the inter-semiotic complementarity of the introduction to characters.

Table 4.

Inter-semiotic complementarity of introduction to characters

Text sources		Message elements				
VMEs	A group of people	Conservative values	Superior, majority	A girl	Outsider	Comfort, happiness
Text A	Denise's family and colleagues	Goodly, Lovely, Angel, Neatly, and Perfect				
Text B1				Her name Denise	The girl	
Text B2				The girl synonym	Odd synonym	
Complementarity notes:	Synonymy	collocation		y	y	

Bringing the verbal and visual elements together, the analysis of ideational-inter-semiotic complementarity indicates that the introduction page in this story provides more information than merely naming the characters. Table 5 displays the inter-semiotic complementarity of the introduction to characters.

Table 5.**Representational meaning of characters' activity**

Elements	Visual Realisations	Visual Transitivity Roles	Visual Message Elements
Identification	A school girl wearing a blue shirt with curly hair	Participant: Actor	School girl
Identification	A school countryside girl who dresses in a uniform way with other people. She is being acted upon by a girl with blue shirt and almost fall into the sea.	Participant: Goal	One of another group a friend
Identification	Four students sitting in a row; three on the left-hand side and no one on the right. In between, there is a messenger slapping on another person back.	Participant: Reacter Phenomenon	Tacky's four other friends The girl and her friend
Activity	telling a the girl's back	Actional process	Slapping on one's back
Activity	Wide-open mouth	Verbal process	Saying loudly
Activity	Group of students with rolling eyes watching a the guru, slapping on another person's back	Reactional process	Demeaning reactions from the girls colleagues
Circumstance	On farm and school background, positioned in the center of the image	Circumstance: locative	in school context

The image depicting the characters' activities has Denise and one of her friends in the center, as in Table 5. An almost-bending girl is caused by the girl's lashing out at one of its backs. The girl creates a transactional action process by drawing a line from his limb to the back of the girl—a phenomenon based on how the other girls were observing this event. The rolled eyes of the girls can also be interpreted as a disapproving look. Although there is no speech bubble, the girl's mouth is wide open, indicating a verbal process (Painter et al., 2013). Complementary processes in the image and the verbal texts have a direct correlation. Based on those mentioned above, visual and verbal meanings, a degree of interaction between the modes was discovered. First, the visual image is thought to interact cohesively with the verbal text regarding mood. In this

case, the producers or authors indirectly show the visual image created by the represented people, implying that they are viewed as a unit of thought. This conforms to the verbal text in passages where the viewers/readers are not directly addressed, as indicated by using the second personal pronoun, you. There were a few you-s in the passages. They are talking about the people in the scene, like Denise or Sami, or the person telling the story in the Meade School picture.

Furthermore, the instruction outside the image box states, "read and listen" to the audio to test your ideas, emphasizing the importance of using the visual image as an object to consider. The function of the visual image as an informational object to be evaluated by readers/viewers interacts cohesively with the presence of inter-semiotic complementarity tools such as a synonym for repetition and an antonym expressing the opposite idea. As a result, different modality indicators must be considered, as each has unique values and functions. Furthermore, when the modality markers *would*, *'ll*," *could*, *couldn't*, and *can't* are combined, the marker should indicate obligation. The modality marker will indicate the inclination.

The passages' evaluative words, such as surprised (affect, passion: security), excited, wanted to play (judgment: capacity), and good idea (appreciation: +reaction), also indicate whether the visual image functions as an object or piece of information (Jauhara et al., 2021). Furthermore, these evaluative words interact coherently with the individuals depicted in the image's facial expressions. For example, they are indicated in this case by the emoter—a term coined by Martin and White (2005). Sami's facial expression differs from Denis'; he is depicted with his mouth open, indicating a smile and enthusiasm (Chen, 2009), and in the verbal text, he is the one who initiates and speaks, whereas Denis is delighted to join the other girls at school. Denis is not participating in school groups because she is experiencing the emotions mentioned above and has sad facial expressions. Also, the use of declarative mood and modal operators ranging from moderate to vigorous is consistent with the mode and validity shown by the visual image, with full-color saturations showing a realistic portrayal (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2006, 2021).

CONCLUSION

The post-2003 environment in Iraq has promoted sustainable development, including education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles: human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and nonviolence, global citizenship and appreciation of cultural diversity, and the contribution of culture to sustainable development. Teachers and students concur that the EFL textbooks *English for Iraq* are excellent in various respects, including layout and design, social and cultural context, subject and content, language type, skills, objectives, and illustrations.

The language and image interplay and the flow of information value in multimodal textbook influenced the reading path. As a result, multimodal textbook readers can read the texts in a linear or non-linear fashion. Non-linear and linear reading paths can be found in the observed textbook's images. If this combination is used, readers can access the multimodal textbooks' semiotic resources via linear and non-linear reading paths. These textbooks may be designed by their authors with a linear reading path in mind, but the reader's choice of how to approach them is entirely up for grabs.

It is a preliminary investigation into the theoretical foundations of reading maps. The study's primary data source was a single textbook, which has its limitations. Data can be gathered from the available English as a Foreign Language (EFL) textbooks. In order to do this, it examines the textbook's content and how words and images are connected. Students and teachers in the classroom as readers could benefit from more research. It is also possible to expand the study by understanding composition and inter-semiotic complementarity in Iraqi EFL school textbooks.

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Exploring Lecturers' Standpoints in Composing Digital Fiction and Students' Multimodal Literacy Level

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Abstract

Multimodality, which encourages the combination of text, image, sound, and videos, could be varied from class to class. Multimodal literacy as a new dimension of literacy in the 21st century has emerged as a critical skill that EFL students must develop, given its role as a source of meaning in communication. The purpose of this study was to identify the level of students' multimodal literacy and to identify lecturers' standpoints on students' multimodal literacy. This study was conducted both quantitatively and qualitatively and involved 71 EFL students who took creative writing subject in an English education program in one state university in South Sumatera. The data were collected by distributing a questionnaire from Bulut et al. (2015) and by interviewing 3 lecturers who taught the subject. Descriptive statistics and one-way ANOVA were used to determine mean, standard deviation and differences in terms of gender and classes with different lecturer; qualitative data were thematically analyzed to categorize the themes. The results indicated that students' multimodal literacy level was categorized high as indicated by the mean of each aspect of questionnaire: 4.22, 4.11 and 3.6 respectively. There was no different level of multimodal literacy between male and female students, and different lecturers with different instructions did not influence the level. Finally, the lecturers perceived positively to students' multimodal literacy. Similarly, referring to the lecturers' view, the students gave positive attitude towards multimodal writing and hence making their multimodal digital fiction successful.

Keywords: multimodal literacy, digital fiction, creative writing, EFL

INTRODUCTION

In the global world today, digital fiction has started to be used by teachers in an English language classroom. As it is digitally born, digital fiction offers a deeper degree of interaction involving decision-making (Frank, 2019), thus going beyond the simple eye move or turning of pages. Students are allowed to have interaction with the text by selecting the move of the story which causes each to experience a different storyline (Astrid et. Al, 2016; Kaba, 2017; Frank, 2019; Skains, 2019). Unlike conventional fiction, students reading digital fiction are given multiple modes such as image, sound, and video besides text. In writing too, students are allowed to enrich the text with those multimodal aspects.

The modes of such image, sound and video distinguishes the text as multimodal. Today's digital fiction as multimodal text is one that students can easily locate in their daily lives, particularly outside of campus (Nouri, 2018; Almusharaff & Engemann, 2020) They will discover it on a variety of social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter; on websites such as blogs, Wattpad, YouTube; and on applications such as book creator, Canva, or Filmora. Additionally, they discovered it in the campus learning environment, such as teacher-led presentations and learning websites that they used for online learning, particularly during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Nowadays, multimodal texts are used as learning resources in the field of English education. These multimodal texts are used as a supplement to the textbook (which contains still images) and/or the module as the primary source. Multimodal texts are frequently used to aid students' comprehension of reading and to encourage students' participation in-class activities. However, because multimodal elements have not been explicitly taught to students, they lack experience constructing meaning using modes other than text. Thus, the opportunity for students to think critically has been underutilized, and multimodal literacy has received less attention from teachers during the classroom learning process (Warschauer, 2008; Eksi & Yakisik, 2015).

Multimodal literacy, as a new dimension of literacy has emerged as a critical skill that students in the field of English education must develop, given its role as a source of meaning in communication. Multimodal literacy is the

study of language in which two or more modes of meaning coexist (Mills & Unsworth, 2017). Multimodal literacy refers to the ability to interpret and produce multimodal artifacts in response to multimodal texts (Jewitt & Kress, 2003; van Leeuwen, 2017). Language and literacy facilitate communication by incorporating a variety of meanings, including writing, visual images, movement, posture, and sound. In this case, students must recognize all modes of communication used by semiotic sources to convey meaning (Kress, 2010), which must be explicitly taught. For example, visual texts depict objects, people, and places using a variety of visual semiotic sources such as lines, patterns, sizes, and symbols, whereas written language relies on a set of nouns and adjectives to convey meaning. Additionally, students should be taught how writers select various modes to determine the most effective way to tell a story and how meaning is "woven" into multimodal texts through the selection and use of various modes in various combinations (Jewitt, 2009). Literacy is determined by the analysis, review, and production of words and pictures as a whole, not by separate interpretations of words and pictures (Bearne & Wolstencroft, 2007).

In writing activities in EFL context, multimodal literacy is expected to be developed by creating or producing multimodal texts. This means that the product of the writing class is not in the form of ordinary verbal text but it has been equipped with other modes such as visual images, sound, or video. Students are asked to construct multimodal meaning based on the purpose of the written text so that the text becomes effective or easy for readers to understand. Writing multimodal texts in the classroom can be a motivation for students for it is relevant to their daily activities. (García et al., 2011) argued that multimodal texts are viewed as relevant and motivating resources that contribute to the pleasant and attractive nature of the EFL environment because the students believe that this type of text is profoundly connected to everyday life. By making writing assignments more relevant to students' lives and by creating more authentic audiences for students' writing, well-designed writing projects that incorporate student-created multimedia and multimodal outputs have the potential to increase struggling students' motivation to complete writing assignments (Darrington & Dousay, 2014). Students feel that multimodal text is more interesting for them (Tüzel,

2013) because it is authentic material that can support their communicative performance (Lotherington & Jenson, 2011), allow students to connect with personal literacies (Cappello et al., 2019), and because it is the genre that they are already familiar with on a daily basis (Williams, 2016). Walsh supported the use of multimodal texts to expand students' learning experiences and provide them with a broader understanding of information and abilities (2010).

In English Education Study Program, writing instruction has been directed at writing that supports multimodal literacy. This is to equip the prospective teachers with multimodal communicative competencies as they are responsible for the English language teaching at the secondary level. Haquin (2011) stated that it is important to know how to use the semiotic power of words and their characteristics and how they are used in teaching the things they can do to show the world and communicate. It is critical in teacher education to develop metalanguage to comprehend the connection between modalities and cultural meanings accessible to everyone in any situation (Hobson, 2014). In addition, reading and writing in this complex semiotic context requires not only "other literacy skills" but also a "metalanguage" to deconstruct the numerous modalities of meaning production (e.g., Kress, 1997; Unsworth, 2006, 2008). In a creative writing course, students are encouraged to produce multimodal compositions through digital fiction writing. In this course, students create digital fiction by using various digital tools that are their preferences or at the suggestion of the lecturer team who teaches them. Some of the digital tools that students use are video editors, Canva, and/or Twine. In this creative writing process, students can express creative ideas using imagination and reflect on imagination by constructing meaning from various choices of existing semiotic modes or sources.

In this study, the writers wanted to identify the level of students' multimodal literacy in digital fiction writing and the lecturers' view on the multimodal literacy. This investigation of multimodal literacy level was firstly introduced by Bulut et al. (2015), who also created an instrument to measure it. According to them, teachers must have multimodal literacy skills to keep up with evolving technology as part of their teacher training. Several

academics have investigated the level of multimodal literacy of prospective teachers. Pramono and Suherdi (2019) found that the multimodal literacy level of 40 PPG students was categorized as high. Similarly, the findings of Eksi and Yakizik (2015) revealed that pre-service English language teachers have quite a high multimodal literacy level, and ability and knowledge improve in direct proportion to the amount of time spent on the internet, the academic year, and gender. The more time pre-service teachers spend on the Internet and the more multimodal structures they encounter, the more multimodal literate they become. These 2 studies suggested that prospective teachers tend to have high multimodal literacy levels in their learning process and that future research should be conducted on a bigger sample than theirs. A high level of multimodal literacy was also indicated by a study conducted by (Ulu et al., 2017). In addition, they claimed that multimodal literacy has a positive and significant influence on critical reading self-efficacy perception. In this study, the level of multimodal literacy of prospective teacher students and lecturers' views on multimodality were investigated to verify the previous results. This study did not take a bigger sample as recommended by previous research; this study chose students of creative writing course as the sample. Moreover, identifying the lecturers' perspective regarding multimodal composition strengthened or confirmed the level of multimodal literacy obtained and provided insight into multimodal pedagogical practice. The results added new insight or contributions to the multimodal composition learning procedure which is in line with the development of 21st-century skills (4C). Perceptions of teaching multimodal literacy have also been studied by Ryu and Boggs (2016), and Almusharraf and Engemann (2020). The results of their research indicate that teachers respond positively to the implementation of multimodal literacy in the classroom. This implementation facilitates students in creating effective communication. Almusharraf and Engemann claimed that effective instruction in teaching multimodality is lecturers' multimodal competence and suggested that assessment should be done multimodal too. The most significant job of lecturers in a multimodal setting was to engage students in critical reflections on themes such as the usage of modes and media to transmit ideas, according to one crucial conclusion (Dahlström, 2021).

In conclusion, this study describes the level of multimodal literacy of prospective English teachers in writing digital fiction and the lecturers' view on multimodal literacy. The description of the level of multimodal literacy was enriched by the teachers' views which eventually become the basis for planning future instruction for multimodal composition.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study was conducted using both quantitative and qualitative method. Quantitatively, students' multimodal literacy was depicted through means and standard deviation. Therefore, a 17-items questionnaire from Bulut et al. (2015) was used to collect the data. This questionnaire consists of three categories: 1) Expressing Oneself Using Multimodal Structure, 2) Interpretation of the Contents Presented in Multimodal Structure, and 3) Preferring Multimodal Structures. The students were asked to determine one choice of agreement from a five-point Likert scale (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree). This questionnaire got a slight modification to meet the research goal. In addition, qualitatively, to portray teachers' views on multimodal literacy, an individual interview was conducted. In this case, 3 teachers teaching 3 different classes were selected. The interview questions were sent by e-mail to 2 teachers, and face to face interview was conducted with one of the teachers as she was available for an offline interview. Both kinds of interviews were documented by recording the conversation, noting down several important information, and then the record was transcribed.

The participants involved in this study were 71 students from 4 classes (Class A, B, C and D) who took a Creative Writing course in the second semester in the academic year 2020/2021. This research was conducted in a Creative Writing class in an English education study program of a state university in Palembang. One of the course's learning outcomes is the ability to master and use relevant and current information and communication technology in the context of English learning. This course is 2 credit hours and was done online using a variety of platforms such as e-learning, Zoom Meeting, Google Classroom, and Google Meet. Additionally, the other participants were 3 lecturers from 3 different classes of creative writing. The lecturers were selected as they were those who were responsible for the

teaching of creative writing in the department. Writing is their expertise and their teaching experience is more than 15 years.

The data from the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics to determine means and standard deviations. The difference among gender and group with 4 different lecturers were analyzed using one-way ANOVA. To interpret the data about students' level of multimodal literacy, the five points Likert Scale conversion was used. The weighted mean interval score includes 4.21-5.00 (very high), 3.41-4.20 (high), 2.61-3.40 (moderate), 1.81-2.60 (low) and 1.00-1.80 (very low). Meanwhile, data from interviews were analyzed thematically by following a procedure from Creswell (2012). The procedures include data organization-reading- data description- classification-interpretation.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Data from the questionnaire showed the demographic of the respondent-students. The students were grouped depending upon their gender and class they enrolled in.

Table 1.

Participant's Demographic

		N	Percentage
Gender	Female	62	87.3%
	Male	9	12.7%
Class	Class 6B-P	19	26.8%
	Class 6B-I	21	29.6%
	Class 6A-I	21	29.6%
	Class 6A-P	10	14.1%

Table 1 above shows that the students were grouped into 4 classes taught by 4 lecturers with different years of experience and methods in teaching creative writing.

Students' Multimodal Literacy Level in Writing Digital Fiction

As the questionnaire consists of 3 categories, students' multimodal literacy in writing digital fiction is discussed per category in the following sections.

Expressing Oneself Using Multimodal Structure

Based on the weighted mean interval score in data analysis section, it was found that, on average, students showed high agreement (4.22) on using multimodal structure. As described in table 2, students stated that multimodality or the use of varied modes such as images, sound, or videos offers easiness for expressing their ideas. It is indicated clearly in the statement “Using various elements (such as music and images) in presentations/digital fiction/story makes it easier to make my point” with mean of 4.41 and standard deviation of 0.623. Another evidence could be seen from the statement “I organize my thoughts systematically in my presentations/digital fiction/story. Thanks to various visual elements (such as image and video)” with mean 4.32 and standard deviation 0.528.

Table 2.

Expressing Oneself Using Multimodal Structure

Statements	Mean	Std. dev
Using various elements (such as music and images) in my presentations/digital fiction/story makes it easier to make my point.	4.41	0.623
I use visuals such as graphics/ tables/ pictures, and photographs in my writings.	4.06	0.735
I prepare an interactive presentation/digital fiction/story making use of music, visuals, and animations.	4.24	0.686
I organize my thoughts systematically in my presentations/digital fiction/story. Thanks to various visual elements (such as image and video).	4.32	0.528
I express myself more explicitly in environments in which writing, sound, and images exist together.	4.07	0.724
Total	4.22	

Interpretation of the Contents Presented in Multimodal Structure

Dealing with the second aspect of “Interpretation of the Contents Presented in Multimodal Structure”, students also had a high agreement (mean= 4.11) on 7 statements described in table 3 below.

Table 3.**Interpretation of the Contents Presented in Multimodal Structure**

Statements	Mean	Std. dev
I pay attention to the body language of the individuals I am listening to.	4.23	0.659
I can realize how visual, auditory, and written elements influence individuals.	4.18	0.723
I use body language that is in harmony with the words I choose when speaking.	4.08	0.751
I relate various visual and verbal information on various media tools to each other	4.13	0.584
I interpret the information that I gather from numerous resources.	4.07	0.683
I relate the information to which I have access using visual and auditory elements.	4.08	0.528
I can decide whether or not content presented on various media (newspaper, TV, social media, etc.) is true.	4.04	0.664
Total	4.11	

As revealed in Table 3, students do not only need verbal structure when making meaning. They interpret a certain meaning using various modes given. The statement “I pay attention to the body language of the individuals I am listening to” got high agreement from the students as the mean is 4.23 and the standard deviation 0.659. Similarly, the other 6 statements tend to have high agreement from the students. They believe that information is true and can be decided from multimodality as indicated by the statement “I can decide whether or not content presented on various media (newspaper, TV, social media, etc.) is true” with mean of 4.04 and 0.664 of standard deviation.

Preferring Multimodal Structures

Students have their preferences dealing with selecting structures for creating multimodal digital fiction. Table 4 presents that their level of preferences is categorized high with mean 3.6. For instance, the students showed disagreement (3.82) to the statement “The use of visual, auditory and written elements together leads to laziness of the mind” and “I only believe in the power of verbal expression when sharing my thoughts’ (3.11). All the respondents disagreed with all of the negative assertions in the questionnaire.

Table 4.**Preferring Multimodal Structures**

Statements	Mean	Std. dev
I do not like trying to interpret images, sounds, graphics, and writings simultaneously.	3.62	0.868
I only believe in the power of verbal expression when sharing my thoughts.	3.11	0.903
I get distracted in electronic environments in which visual, auditory, and written elements are used together.	3.49	0.876
The use of visual, auditory, and written elements together leads to laziness of the mind.	3.82	0.931
I get bored in communication in which written, auditory, and visual elements are used together.	3.80	0.804
Total	3.6	

As described above, the multimodal literacy level of the students involved in digital fiction writing activities can be classified high because the mean of each aspect exceeds (3.41). Based on the score interval depicted in research method section, the mean of the first aspect which is Expressing Oneself Using Multimodal Structure is (4.22). This was categorized as very high. The mean for the second and the third aspect are categorized high as the scores are 4.11 and 3.6. This high multimodal literacy level is relevant with results from (Ekşi & Yakışık, 2015), Ulu et al. (2017), and (Pramono & Suherdi, 2019). The result of this present study indicates that English prospective teachers are already aware of the use of multimodal structure in writing digital fiction. They have their own preferences and decide which mode they put in their digital fiction as using this multimodality allows them to have critical thinking and problem-solving skill or what Nouri (2018) claimed as 'active designers.' Furthermore, the result revealed that multimodal texts such as text, image, sound, video and body language are highly explored to build interpretation to support the production of digital fiction. This exploration of multiple communication modes has become digital writer's choices since several decades ago (Astrid et.al, 2016), and it is growing as the technology develops. To obtain deep insight into students' multimodal literacy based on the gender and the class they belong to, calculation using one-way ANOVA was conducted.

Table 5.

Multimodal Literacy Level Differences between Genders

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	mean Difference	F-hit	Sig	Remark
Male	9	3.92	6.20	-1.13	0.259	0.613	Not Significant
Female	62	3.99	6.21				

Based on table 5, the ANOVA test yielded an F-count value of 0.259 and a sig.F value of 0.613. Because sig.F is greater than 0.05, it is not significant. This explains that with significance level 5%, there is no significant difference between male and female students' multimodal literacy level.

Table 6.

Multimodal Literacy Level Differences among Classes

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F-hit	Sig	Remark
Class 6B-I	21	3.93	5.80	2.287	0.087	Not Significant
Class 6A-P	10	3.98	5.94			
Class 6A-I	21	4.14	6.46			
Class 6B-P	19	3.87	5.74			

Table 6 explains that the mean of multimodal literacy level of 21 students of class 6B-I is 3.9, the mean of for 6A-P is 3.98, the mean of 21 students in 6A-I is 4.14 and the mean of 19 students of class 6B-P is 3.87. Statistically, the Anova test obtained an F-count value of 2.287 and a sig.F value of 0.087. Because the value of sig.F is $0.087 > 0.05$, it means that it is not significant. Thus, statistically at a significant level of 5%, it can be stated that simultaneously there is no significant difference in the mean of students' multimodal literacy level among the four classes.

Perspectives and Challenges of Facilitating Multimodal Literacy in Writing Digital Fiction

The interview was conducted individually with each interviewee and done both virtually or face to face. The interview session was recorded through zoom meeting and video recorder. The result of the interview was transcribed, and the transcription was thematically analyzed. After the analysis, several themes were found to be relevant as lecturers' perspectives

on multimodality in digital fiction writing. The following are several passages from the interview session with the lecturers (RI and SS, CD).

The interviews with the lecturers (RI and SS) were done both online and face to face based on their preferences. The purpose of the interview is to address “What are the perspectives of the lecturers towards students’ multimodal literacy? As the finding from the questionnaire reveals that students-respondents have a high multimodal literacy level, the findings from the interview also affirm that the lecturer perceived the students are successful in writing their multimodal composition. Lecturer SS said:

So, I can see as the whole, and for some, for the one group that has difficulty finding the tools also they end up with a book which is – in terms of the content is pretty good, it’s just the composition of the picture is not as smooth. But I think, in general, I can see that they’re successfully doing the multimodal project.(SS)

This success could be associated with the instruction applied by lecturers. All the lecturers mentioned that in their creative class they support their students to collaborate and to explore various digital tools to create digital fiction. RI stated:

I applied collaborative learning model for three meetings. The steps: a) introducing the multimodal projects by asking them to read the material and discuss in a big group in a discussion forum in e-learning. b) composing the multimodal projects, and c) Creating the digital multimodal form.(RI)

Similarly, SS claimed that the cooperation that occurs in this class is therefore naturally mediated by many technologies, including multimodality, the platform itself, and the affordances that students employ when they write. Meanwhile, CD argued that the students develop ed multimodality through collaboration with peers. They gained knowledge from one another but maintained confidence in their own abilities to develop original things.

Another perspective from SS should be highlighted: She believed that the multimodal digital fiction composition in creative writing subject is a result of exploring experience as she stated

For writing books collaboratively, the process includes... also I think, in the beginning, revisiting their experience. So, I always begin with the

experience of the students, and how their experience manifested in different multimodal elements. So, it could be pictures, videos, the audio they have, or maybe the sketch that they make and so on. So, it always begins with the students' experience and then connects to how they experience at present and then how those experiences connected with other text that they learn or other students' experience. (SS)

In compiling a multimodal digital fiction, the lecturers admitted that students often use multiple technologies such as Filmora, Kidmaster, Ibis (digital drawing), Canva or Comic Strip, and other applications which are students' preferences. In selecting the application, the lecturers did not advise on certain applications because they were quite familiar with these applications in their daily lives. Dealing with this, RI stated "I let them select the kind of technological tool they knew exactly though I had provided a link for the material that "(RI) and CD agreed by mentioning that "About the devices used, the students are free to choose which they think they are familiar with"(CD).

Digital fiction learning in the creative writing class received a positive response from students. In other words, there is a positive attitude from the students towards multimodal composition activities.

The assessment of multimodal composition was carried out with different ways by the 3 lecturers. The first lecturer or SS evaluated by focusing on aspects such as content (plot, character, and language use) and creative design (smooth picture or good layout). This lecturer did not only evaluate students' works but also considered the process of making a multimodal composition, such as persistence and problem-solving in every problem encountered. SS stated:

I look at all the processes from the draft. So, the draft is ... well, actually from the very beginning, the outline. So how they... it's not just about the look because writing is also that content. So, the multimodal aspect is the... make what it looks like. So, the use... my assessments are two, so the first one is the content. The content means like the story, the essence of the story itself. And then, the presentation of the story into the whole book or memoir, or poetry. So I think that's the two aspects that complemented each other. In terms of content, then I will follow the content like we assess

writing, whether how they express the story, how the plot is clear, for example. So, that's more focused on the writing. Now, the other aspects, the multimodal aspect, the assessment is looking at how they can solve the problem, for example, oh they want to express the story into this picture. What kind of resources that they use? So, their effort to find the appropriate resource or the appropriate tool is also my consideration. Looking at how they afford the technology that meets their need. Because I think that's important, that's kind of problem-solving skills also, so finding out what is the appropriate tools to help them do the project (SS).

On the other hand, the second lecturer, RI, used a simple rubric that focuses on the composition of text, images, and sounds as well as student creativity. Meanwhile, CD stated "I emphasize my assessment on the originality of the students' work. I allow them to be as creative as possible"(CD).

The lecturers found no significant difficulties in teaching multimodal composition. However, RI stated that she needed to learn more about teaching with multimodal composition. Meanwhile, SS stated that the issue that could be a problem was that this writing project would take a long time.

In terms of difficulties, it's just all the work is a bit time-consuming, because in the regular writing it's just regular paragraph essays, for example, right? While in multimodal, they have to include all of the resources to make into an interesting writing (SS).

The high level of students' multimodal literacy is also supported by data from interviews. The data described several emergence themes which becomes essential aspects of multimodality (Figure 1). According to the lecturers' view, the students were successful in making their multimodal digital fiction. This success can be said to be directly proportional to their high level of multimodal literacy. Moreover, students had a positive attitude towards learning multimodal composition. Another factor influencing the high level of multimodal literacy is that students were already technologically literate before they participated in creative writing course, making it easy for them to be creative. The students were digital natives or active users of digital tools both in their academic or non-academic context. As a result, in shaping digital fiction, the students become independent learners who have

opportunity to choose independently digital tools that is familiar with them (Frank, 2016; Skains, 2019). By doing this, students were engaged in problem-solving skill and critical thinking skills.

Figure 1. Essential Aspects in Multimodal Literacy

What also needs to be an important concern from this research are the learning procedures which could facilitate students' writing of digital fiction. The procedures in this context include introducing multimodal writing projects, recalling experience (brainstorming), collaborative work, and independent multimodal assignment. Assigning students to a project-based activity while completing multimodal works provides opportunities for students to express more by using many modes (Skains, 2019) to achieve learning objectives and hence affect multimodal literacy level. The procedures designed in this study is potential in developing students' multimodal task as Jim and Polio (2020) proposed three important aspects: objectives and multimodal writing instruction, mode of language in multimodal tasks, and independent and collaborative work.

Dealing with assessment, the lecturers focus on the process of creating multimodal composition and the final product. Writing digital fiction does not

only deal with the multimodality of the product but also with students' effort in solving the problem, persistence, and hard work. Drafting, revising, editing and having peer and lecturer's feedback are promoted during the process of writing. Meanwhile, the multimodal digital fictions are evaluated its content (plot, character, language use), originality, design and creativity. Even though, the lecturers tend to have similar standard of evaluation, the standard is not well established and relevant. According to Adsanatham (2012) and Fjørtoft (2020), assessment in writing multimodal digital text should involve the students who are the writer-designers. Students are responsible for their own evaluation during the process of writing and thus the writing shows some progressions.

As a final point, teaching writing multimodal digital fiction is quite challenging for the lecturers. They believe that they themselves must recognize and learn digital tools for learning to write multimodal text. This makes sense as they are the facilitator and model for these student-teachers. Jiang et al (2021) believe that teacher or lecturers engage with digital multimodal composing is a multifaceted continuum. They may have different points when teaching digital multimodal composition. The findings also show that teachers' ideas of themselves, students, and language directed and mediated these personalized exchanges. Another problem is that giving multimodal task is a bit consuming. The lecturers should provide a good time management to encourage students to complete the task.

CONCLUSION

The level of multimodal literacy of the students tends to be high these days; they are millennials who have been exposed to and used to a range of multimodal texts from an early age, whether pictures (drawings and photographs), sounds, videos, or text. The students have had multimodality potentials before they began the academic life. They actively look for solutions to the problems faced in creating multimodal works. As a result, in writing digital fiction, the students do not have much difficulty, and they have a good attitude to writing it. Therefore, classroom instruction will undoubtedly serve as a catalyst for developing multimodal literacy. This study implies that lecturers should address two critical components while

teaching writing: multimodal writing instruction and multimodal writing evaluation. To summarize, the findings of this study will contribute to the growth of multimodal writing training in the field of English language teaching.

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Fluency Matters!: Chinese Netizens' Attitudes towards China English

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Abstract

This research examined Chinese netizens' attitudes towards China English (CE), a growing English variety in China, as well as the underlying reasons for their attitudinal responses. The corpus consisted of 905 tokens of Danmus (a form of video synchronous commentary used by netizens on the Internet video) that were collected from an online interview video. Instead of adopting the frequently employed questionnaire survey, these unique Danmus were utilized as the data resource and were analyzed via a paradigmatic approach to investigate Chinese netizens' acceptance of some potential features of CE. Four netizens were invited to an interview to investigate the reasons for their Danmu delivery on language attitudes. The results revealed that Chinese netizens showed overwhelmingly positive attitudes towards CE, which differed significantly from earlier findings. The participants' positive evaluations of CE were based on three key parameters: the fluency and confidence in using CE as a communicative tool, the possibility of CE to mark speakers' Chinese identity, and the ease of using CE in communication. The findings of the study may shed light on the increasing awareness of China English and English globalization among Chinese netizens in the web-mediated context where local varieties of English are emerging. This research also hopes to provide some methodological implications in terms of research subjects and data-collection approaches for current investigations of language attitudes. This study offers some pedagogical implications of introducing English varieties, especially China English, to the English language programs in China.

Keywords: china english, danmus, chinese netizens, language attitudes, english language teaching

INTRODUCTION

English is now broadly utilized as a lingua franca for global communication for different political, economic, cultural, and social purposes (Jenkins, 2007; Seidlhofer, 2011). As English is widely used, numbers of localized English varieties have emerged in various parts of the globe (Bolton, 2012). English is the most popular foreign language in China in terms of the number of foreign language learners (Wei & Su, 2012).

According to People's Daily Online (2020), there are estimated to be around 400 million Chinese people learning English. As English is widely learned and used in China, China English has been touted as a developing English variety arising in the setting of China and a feasible educational choice for Chinese English learners to challenge the dominance of native-speaker English in China (Deterding, 2006; Gao et al., 2014; Xu, 2010).

China English (henceforth CE), the local use of English in mainland China (Ma & Xu, 2017), is regarded as the fastest-growing English variety worldwide (Edwards, 2017). CE was initially coined in 1980 and refers to English expressions with distinct Chinese features (Ge, 1980). Some English expressions, for instance, *Fengshui* and *paper tiger*, were related to specific Chinese cultures and social norms, but not existing in other English varieties.

The concept of China English is getting momentum, and numerous researchers have discussed its definitions and features (Kirkpatrick & Xu, 2002; McKay & Bokhorst-Heng, 2008). Early research focuses on theoretical investigations to sustain CE's legitimacy (e.g., Gao & Wen, 2012; Niu & Wolff, 2003; Wang, 2002; Xie, 1995).

Empirical discussions have also been extended to identify CE's characteristics with regard to pronunciation, grammar, lexis, and discourse pragmatics (e.g., Bolton, 2003; Gao & Wen, 2012; Kirkpatrick, 2007; Xu, 2010; Yu, 2009). These investigations have advanced the understanding of CE by articulating and formalizing specific linguistic features. This also necessitates further explorations of language attitudes towards China English. The existing explorations have mostly concentrated on Chinese university students or teachers' perceptions of CE (Kirkpatrick & Xu, 2002; Hu, 2004; Hu, 2005; He & Li, 2009; He & Zhang, 2010; Wang & Gao, 2015; Pan et al., 2021). Kirkpatrick and Xu (2002) and Hu (2004) identified Chinese university

students' overwhelming support for native English, particularly American English, as pedagogical models in language teaching and learning, yet a weak identification with CE. English teachers in Hu's (2005) study appeared to be supportive of CE. Despite the fact that approximately 80% of the language instructors polled preferred American English, CE was still accepted by 53% of them. He and Li (2009) conducted a later survey on teachers and students, finding that they had increased support (62.6%) for incorporating "certain characteristics" of CE into the classroom. He and Zhang (2010), drawing on He and Li (2009), carried out a further investigation by evaluating the pronunciation and grammar of CE. They discovered that while over half of the participants (55.4%) had no difficulty speaking English with a Chinese accent, 71% insisted on precisely adhering to the native speaker's English grammar norms. Wang and Gao (2015) adopted a mixed-method approach to explore the attitudes of Chinese English learners and teachers towards China English features, differences, and reasons underpinning their attitudinal responses. The findings indicated that both teachers and students in China were hesitant to embrace CE as a legitimate variety, but their views on certain CE components differed.

There are also recent studies deploying questionnaires and interviews to examine Chinese university students' perceptions of China English and their particular linguistic identity regarding the practice of China English. The findings indicate a rising tendency in the majority of students' identification with China English, despite the fact that native English ideology continues to have huge impacts (Pan et al., 2021).

With technological advancements such as social networking sites and the global expansion of English, non-native English speakers now account for over 80% of the global English communication (Lee & Lee, 2019). Linguistically speaking, the influx of Internet resources brings numerous opportunities for English language learners in many countries to process language input/output. This is mainly due to the fast exchanges of information and being of ease at with revealing the user's preferred expressive means in the network spaces (Muftah, 2022). Recent inquiries of web-mediated discourses have shown that the Chinese experience online English practices on various social networking sites, especially with the

growth of domestic sites, such as Sina Weibo, YouKu, and so forth (Zhang, 2021). Previous studies suggest online English users in China exhibit creative and distinctive communicative strategies by practicing the English language (Zhang, 2021). These strategies display the linguistic complexity and flexibility of China English with regard to localizing English features in online discourses. China, as a prominent participant in the English-as-lingua-franca (ELF) circle, will undoubtedly have an impact on nowadays and future construction of ELF through the way it uses English (Fang, 2017b).

In other words, with the rise of China's participation in globalization, using English with certain Chinese features (e.g., China English) will influence the use of English in other social contexts. Simultaneously, China has the world's largest digital population, with 1.03 billion netizens as of 2021 (Statista, 2022), and Chinese netizens are more exposed to different varieties of English through the heavy use of the Internet. However, as aforementioned, a prominent feature in the researches of language attitudes towards CE has been that teachers and students make up the majority of the research subjects.

In other words, most of the previous studies have focused on investigating Chinese teachers and students' attitudes towards China English in curricular circumstances and pedagogical motivations in educational settings, which were mostly constructed by adopting conventionalized methodological measures, like questionnaire surveys.

Few studies have applied modern Internet information resources to elicit Chinese netizens' explicit and naturalistic attitudes. As past studies have mostly concentrated on the educational mechanisms, it is necessary to investigate language attitudes towards CE among the general public in other contexts to expand the understanding of language attitudes across different contexts. Drawing on the fact that more than 400 million people are practicing English for various purposes (Wei & Su, 2015) and that English is widely used in various fields beyond education in China (Pan et al., 2021), this study henceforth aims to explore the complexity of Chinese netizens' attitudes towards China English and investigate underlying reasons in the web-mediated context, which was fulfilled by incorporating the analysis of Danmus and interviews.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research draws on the use of multiple data collection tools, namely the combination of both qualitative and quantitative methods. The qualitative-quantitative research design has been depicted as showing many advantages in that these two resources of data can complement each other (McDonough & McDonough, 1997). The researchers can utilize the strength of each type of data collection and minimize the weaknesses of any single research approach to obtain a more comprehensive overview of academic phenomena (Gong & Firdaus, 2022). First, this study used a quantitative method in the form of Danmu corpus that was directly downloaded from the video website. Then, interviews with Danmu creators were qualitatively analyzed.

Data Collection

This study primarily approached with naturally occurring data that was composed of 3832 tokens of Danmus delivered by Chinese netizens in an online video. To begin with, Danmu or plural Danmus (Chinese: 弹幕, literally: “bullet curtain”, figuratively: “barrage”) is a form of video commentary used on the Internet videos consisting of scrolling user/viewer messages posted on top of the video in real time (Wikipedia, 2022). In other words, Danmu could be understood as a system of superimposed comments running across the screen from right to left as the video plays (Zhang & Cassany, 2020). These Danmus are collected from a video in Bilibili, which is one of the most popular online video sharing and social media platforms in China. As shown in Figure 1, a native English-speaking hostess (the left) is interviewing a respectable Chinese transgender dancing artist, Ms. Jin Xing (the right). The viewers who are watching the video can add synchronous comments or responses, i.e., Danmus, on the screen (as indicated in Figure 1 by rectangular overlay in yellow). The entire one-hour-long interview was realized in English.

Figure 1. Danmus as the Scrolling Marquee Comment in Bilibili Video Delivered by Chinese Netizens

This video has attracted wide publicity. As of May 2022, it has been viewed 838,000 times and there are 3,832 tokens of Danmus since it was uploaded in June 2019. During the interview, some distinguishing features of China English in terms of lexis, syntax, and phonology can be found in Ms. Jin's English. Consequently, a number of viewers used Danmus to comment Ms. Jin Xing's English language.

To help readers comprehend China English, several evident features of China English utilized by Ms. Jin in this video have been selected and offered as examples (see Table 1).

Among the total 3832 tokens of Danmus, 905 Danmus with apparent evaluations of China English were saved and examined to investigate those Chinese netizens' attitudes towards China English. The rationale for Danmu collection is that writing Danmus is easy for viewers while watching videos, and the written Danmus will be instantaneously overlaid onto the video and shown to writers as well as other viewers. With the use of such Danmu systems, users may interact with one another much more directly and also have a real-time sharing experience (He et al., 2017). By doing so, Chinese netizens' attitudes towards CE will be more visually evident in a straightforward mode. Following the Danmus collection, four Chinese netizens among those Danmus creators were recruited and invited for interviews to identify reasons underpinning their attitudes delivered in Danmus.

Table 1.
 Demonstration of Distinctive Features of CE Used by Ms. Jin

Category	Description	Explanation	Examples included in the video (in bold)	Occurrence Time
Phonology	Chinese accent	Influenced by Chinese phonology, CE speakers have a tendency to pronounce /θ/ and /ð/ as /s/ and /z/. (Deterding, 2006; Kirkpatrick, 2007)	<i>I don't know, I think [sɪŋk] at young age.</i>	0'47"
Lexis	Transliteration	Transliteration of Chinese words and use of <i>pinyin</i> such as <i>Putonghua</i> (modern standard Chinese). (Kirkpatrick, 2007; Xu, 2010)	<i>The idea, the attitude toward life, the energy (are) very authentic, very Jin Xing.</i>	12'12"
Syntax	Adjacent default tense	Use adjacent default tense as criteria to decide the tenses of a cluster of clauses uttered together. (Xu, 2010)	<i>I think for the young kid I didn't know that. Then dancing come up, choose me become a dancer. So I become a dancer.</i>	01'25"

Data Analysis

The analysis of Danmus was initially drawing on the adapted analytical model of Wang and Fang (2019), who have transcribed attitude-related data via a paradigmatic approach of “taxonomies and categories out of the common elements across the database” (Polkinghorne, 1995, p. 5) through repeated reading of the data. As shown in Figure 2, to begin with, the authors of this study organized themselves to view and code all 3832 Danmus independently, and communicated their viewing results. This initial step enabled us to form a general understanding of all Danmus and thus to eliminate those that did not involve the viewers' attitudes towards Ms. Jin's China English. 905 Danmus with clear attitudinal judgments were chosen as the valid data after rigorous and thorough discussion and selection. Next, these 905 Danmus were read again to provide preliminary coding of taxonomies and categories. In this phase, the 905 Danmus which showed unambiguous attitudinal judgments were divided into two macro groups, positive or negative, regarding the characteristics of China English

implemented in the video. In the third reading, these Danmus were coded according to the categories and taxonomies generated in the second phase while allowing micro topics/themes to arise. A fourth reading was performed after the previous three steps to analyze and verify the classification and coding.

Figure 2. Paradigmatic Approach to Commentary Data
(Adapted from Wang & Fang, 2019)

After the Danmu analysis, the interviews were conducted in Mandarin according to the interviewees' preference because the native language would enable them to respond to questions in more depth (Mann, 2011). All the Chinese Danmus and interview data were translated into English by the first author and proofread by the second author. The selection and classification about netizens' attitudes were finished by the two authors under rigorous discussions. This process of securing inter-rater reliability assists in achieving reliability for this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Netizens' Attitudes: Danmu Analysis

The analysis of Danmus reveals that netizens' comments are overwhelmingly positive towards Ms. Jin's English, with 842 tokens of comments (93%/among 905) expressing approval or admiration for the English of Ms. Jin during the interview. The remaining 63 (7%) tokens of

Danmus showed negative attitudes towards Ms. Jin's English. Initially, the findings indicate that the netizens might have rich and diversified mental perceptions of China English. As shown in Table 2, various themes that are mainly framed in the netizens' Danmus are presented and will be discussed in the following sections.

Table 2.
 Chinese Netizens' Attitudes towards CE and Framed Themes in Danmus

Attitudes Category/FrR.	Framed themes	Freq.	Percent. (1)	Percent. (2)
Positive	1 Fluency in using English	489	58%	
	2 Using English as a communicative medium	168	19.9%	
	3 General positive comments	156	18.5%	
	4 Awareness of ELF and Global Englishes	13	1.5%	
	5 Closeness to the Chinese language	9	1.1%	
	6 Comparison with Standard Mandarin	7	1%	
Sub Total		842	100%	93%
Negative	1 Non-standardness	21	33.3%	
	2 Inadequate communicative effectiveness	19	30.2%	
	3 Discrepancy with ELT classes/textbooks	12	19%	
	4 China English is riddled with mistakes	11	17.5%	
Sub Total		63	100%	7%
Total		905		100%

Positive attitude towards Ms. Jin's English

Scrutiny of the reasons that netizens give to justify their positive evaluations show that the majority of Chinese netizens focused on fluency (n=489/58%) when evaluating others' English. Furthermore, some positive Danmus convey a strong message that these netizens generally conceptualize that the function of English is attributed to a communicative medium (n=168/19.9%). It seems that the level of fluency is the most important element to consider in evaluating a speaker's English in China from the perspectives of those Chinese netizens. In addition, some of the comments show positive attitudes towards Ms. Jin's English by simply voicing like: "Her English is brilliant" without supplementary explanations (n=156/18.5%). Besides the emphasis on fluency, communicative function, and general positive comments, there are also other rationales and reasons (n=29/3.6%)

for positive attitudes among the 842 positive Danmus. Some positive-sense Danmus are excerpted as follows:

- E.g.1 Woww, her English is so fluent and natural, love it. (Danmu 7)
- E.g.2 It's not a big deal to have Chinese accents, what really matters is that Jinxing expressed herself very fluently and make her idea clearly output. English is just a tool! (Danmu 43)
- E.g.3 It's really great to express ideas fluently and confidently. (Danmu 123)
- E.g.4 Accent, accents! You only have accents in your mind! I am envious of this accent. Fluency, and accuracy, are the heel of the language. Accent judges, you are jealous. (Danmu 172)
- E.g.5 From my point of view, it's ok to have our own accents when speaking English fluently. (Danmu 196)

These instances of Danmus suggest that Chinese netizens seem to place a higher priority on fluency when a Chinese speaks English. Fluency usually refers to adequate content of speech used by speakers to communicate as effectively as possible (Harmer, 2015). It also means speaking languages quickly and confidently, with limited hesitations, unnatural pauses, etc. (Baily, 2003). As indicated in Example 1, the netizen showed an apparent admiration for Ms. Jin's English. Example 2 shows that English is merely a tool for communication, and this can be regarded in some way as Chinese netizens' awareness of English as a lingua franca, which is defined as any use of English among speakers of various first languages for whom English is the communicative medium of choice and often the only option (Kaur & Birlik, 2021; Seidlhofer, 2011). Example 3 emphasizes the significance of fluency while using English since it is a significant aspect in accomplishing communicative functions in conversations (Shahini & Shahamirian, 2017). Examples 4 and 5 are connected with the refutations of the harsh comments on Ms. Jin's accent in English speaking. Example 4 criticizes excessive nitpicking and criticism of accents and expresses appreciation for Ms. Jin's unique accent. Similarly, Example 5 shows explicit support for possessing our accent in speaking. Both highlight the focal idea that "fluency" or "fluently" is all that matters. These five excerpts suggest that many Chinese netizens prefer to focus on "the interactional and transactional purposes of the talk, as

well as their interlocutors as people rather than the linguistic code itself” (Seidlhofer, 2011, p. 98). To put it another way, when Chinese netizens experience English conversation, e.g., interview video in this study, they tend to focus more on the content of the communication rather than the level of normality of Ms. Jin's use of English and China English features. This is accounted by Danmu 43 in Example 2, many Chinese netizens have already formed a position that English serves as a lingua franca and a language tool for communication.

E.g.6 There are more dialectal accents in English, most parts of the UK have a different accent from the so-called Oxford accent, as well as Ireland, Northern Ireland, the USA, Canada, and Australia, so Ms. Jin's China English is very acceptable. (Danmu 462)

E.g.7 What is standard? Old English, British accent, American accent, African accent, Russian accent, Asian accent, even European and American countries are multiethnic. Come on, what is standard pronunciation? Why can't China English become one standard? (Danmu 865)

E.g.8 Irish English can sound like Irish, American English can sound like American, and Indian English can sound like Indian, so why can't China English sound like Chinese? (Danmu 895)

In this case, it can be observed that some Chinese netizens have the awareness of Global Englishes, which is operationalized as the metamorphosis of English across borders in today's globalized world (Jenkins, 2015). These Danmus justify the legitimate use of China English. The key reason these netizens believe China English is acceptable is that they believe there should not be just one type of English and that it is entirely reasonable and acceptable for Chinese people to use English in a Chinese way. Example 6 demonstrates that people from different countries use English in various ways since English is moved over the world, it evolved to suit and accommodate specific local demands for expressions and identities (Yano, 2009). Example 7 argues that there are many varieties of English with different accents, even native English speakers from Britain and America use different accents. Therefore, this netizen questions what the definition of so-called “standard English” is. From the perspective of this netizen, there is no

conventionalized form of standard English. The concept of standard English is notoriously hard to be defined and is extremely weak indeed in speech (Gupta, 2006). The netizen of Example 8 believes that using China English can show a Chinese identity as different people around the world form their own characteristic varieties of English. As a result, they hold the idea that China English should also be recognized as a variety of English that is particularly utilized by Chinese people, which is unique in the global Englishes world. Interestingly, Standard Mandarin is also often mentioned by those netizens when they refute the criticisms of Ms. Jin's English with regard to her accent. They claimed that people who speak Mandarin in different regions might have hometown dialectal accents, thus there is no need to foreground Chinese English speaking with the Chinese accent.

E.g.9 Hahahahahahahahaha. This is a direct translation using Chinese grammar. Such grammar is very good to understand. I like it. (Danmu 218)

China English is also valued for its closeness to the Chinese language. Example 9 shows that many Chinese netizens believe Ms. Jin's English is commendable because of the intermingling with Chinese grammar, e.g., direct translation or literal translation. It creates a sense of ease for those Chinese netizens to understand English words, phrases, or sentences by provoking their native-language competence.

E.g.10 Language is a tool for communication, so you don't have to focus too much on grammar and syntax when speaking. Just express what you want to say. (Danmu 884)

E.g.11 Those who struggle with the Chinese way of using English are really poisoned by stereotypical teaching. (Danmu 117)

Example 10 presents the idea that English is merely a communication instrument. Rather than focusing on grammar, what counts is that the communicative purpose of the speaker can be readily grasped and comprehended by the interlocutor(s). Considering that today's mainstream English-language-teaching practice in China still heavily emphasizes "native English" (Fang & Ren, 2018), Example 11 argues that English teaching in China is so stereotypical by employing the appraisal markers "struggle" and

“poison”, which indicates the exceedingly destructive effect of such pedagogical philosophy.

In sum, the analysis of the positive Danmus reveals most netizens' alignment with fluency into the use of English rather than the pursuit of standardized English and conventions. In addition, today's Chinese netizens also have the awareness of Global Englishes and appreciate China English as a particular English variety used by Chinese people. Also, there are some Chinese netizens who prefer to use China English as they believe it is easier for them to communicate in English, and makes them feel much more grounded because they are familiar with using English in a Chinese way. In particular, China English is put forward as easily understandable and accessible to the general public. The results show that Chinese netizens' attitudes are remarkably positive towards China English, which differ from the previous findings that Chinese English learners and users (e.g., teachers and students) were generally reluctant to accept CE as a legitimate variety (Wang & Gao, 2015). These findings further show that people's language attitudes should be reconceptualized not as stable characteristics of language learners but as dynamic variables (Csizér et al., 2010).

Negative attitude towards Ms. Jin's English

In contrast to the positive attitudes discussed above, there were Danmus portraying negative attitudes towards Ms. Jin's English. The Danmus belonging to this category convey a strong message that some netizens were reluctant to accept different specific features of China English, particularly the phonological perspective (i.e., Chinese accent). Of the total 63 (7%) tokens of negative Danmus, most of the which cite non-standardness ($n=21/33.3\%$) as reasons for their criticisms on Ms. Jin's China English, as shown in Table 2. Other reasons are attributed to inadequate communicative effectiveness ($n=19/30.2\%$), discrepancy with ELT classes or textbooks ($n=12/19\%$), and incorrectness (i.e., China English is riddled with mistakes) ($n=11/17.5\%$). They are illustrated with Danmus below:

E.g.12 Fluency is superficial. People with high English proficiency will know at first glance that all her English is full of bugs and too Chinese style. (Danmu 269)

- E.g.13 Chinese accent, her expressions follow the Chinese way of speaking, straightforward, which may affect other people's understanding. (Danmu 880)
- E.g.14 It's not as good as others make it out to be, the English is so Chinese. It does not sound nice. (Danmu 694)
- E.g.15 Her English grammar is very problematic and there are also many China English expressions. (Danmu 874)
- E.g.16 To be honest, the accent is heavy. The language is very China English and the pronunciation is not clear enough. (Danmu 887)

These Danmus reveal that some Chinese netizens seem to look down upon Ms. Jin's English, as a representative of China English. They criticize China English and the Chinese way of using English. Example 12 indicates that China English is riddled with mistakes and that "Standard" English shouldn't be implemented in a Chinese-communicative mode. Examples 13 and 14 both criticize the Chinese accent produced by Ms. Jin in this interview, citing concerns that Chinese accents may cause interlocutors' misunderstanding when they may hardly identify the corresponding vocabulary. In other words, the communicativeness of China English especially Chinese accents is doubted by Chinese netizens. The netizens of Examples 15 and 16 believe that the expressions and grammar in this video are also problematic because she is in a Chinese-speaking way.

In summary, the analysis of negative comments reveals that some netizens continue to place a premium on Standard English ideology, particularly in their belief in and use of Standard English norms and conventions when assessing linguistic features of Ms. Jin's English, and regard what they learned in class as the norm. These findings substantially corroborate prior research findings that CE is widely recognized but not universally associated with Chinese English users and learners (Wang, 2015).

Interview Findings

According to the above Danmu analysis, the interview process drew on a binary coding criterion, namely revealing positive or negative attitudes (see Table 3). Among the four Chinese netizens, two of them expressed positive

attitudes towards China English while the other two held negative attitudes. These four participants are from different backgrounds (i.e., genders, ages, occupations) and all of them have been learning and using English for many years (see demographic information in Table 3).

Table 3.
Profile of the Interview Participants

Attitude	Name	Gender	Age	Occupation	Length of Interview
Positive	Feng	M	46	Foreign trade salesman	28'16"
	Meng	F	20	University student	23'34"
Negative	Zhang	M	33	Bank employee	25'28"
	Zhao	F	58	English teacher	30'45"

To begin with, semi-structured interview findings indicate that both Participants Mr. Feng and Ms. Meng consider that Ms. Jin's English is acceptable (see interview extracts in Appendix A). Ms. Meng deemed her use of English, featuring localized attributes, as an identity marker of herself, namely a Chinese English speaker. In addition, Meng's positive evaluation of CE, e.g., Ms. Jin's speaking, was based on the considerably easier and flexible syntactic and grammatical constructions. From the perspective of Ms. Meng, following the Chinese language structure seems to render her ease to form colloquial English. Although English in outer circle countries is still norm-dependent or exonormative which means relying on native/standard English for correctness, the comments seem to indicate that even in expanding circle countries like China, people have also begun to break away from exonormative models of English and started developing norms of their own (Wang, 2015). Interestingly, Ms. Meng has also voiced her appreciation for Ms. Jin's English, which is asserted: "she is my idol and role model" because of Ms. Jin's accomplishment as a popular celebrity and renowned dance artist. Based on this, we hold a hypothesis that Chinese netizens' evaluations of China English may have been influenced by the speaker's public identity and social status, and other characteristics of the individuals using China English. Mr. Feng has an optimistic attitude towards Ms. Jin's China English because he sees English as a communicative tool for interaction among various L1s. This

confirms the fact that “English is not inherently used intra-nationally among Chinese speakers of English on a daily basis” (Fang, 2017a, p. 22). He also emphasizes that Chinese English learners should not go overboard with English standardization. According to him, the emphasis should also be connected with speakers’ confidence which is one of the most demotivating elements affecting individuals’ motivation to speak in the English context (Pale & Wisrance, 2021). These responses, from Ms. Meng and Mr. Feng, generally suggest that CE is not a concern for participants who are more preoccupied with communication than with standards. In other words, CE would be acceptable if it fulfills the speaker’s communicative purpose, but not necessarily if it realizes native English norms. In short, the fluency and confidence in using CE as a language tool, the possibilities of CE to mark speakers’ Chinese identity, and the much easier formation of English conversations through CE, are three major reasons leading to participants’ positive evaluation of CE.

On the contrary, opposite opinions were voiced by participants Ms. Zhao and Mr. Zhang who think China English, such as Ms. Jin’s, is not acceptable to them. Ms. Zhao sticks deeply to the Standard English ideology in ELT (see Appendix A). She argued that allowing China English to be used in educational contexts, e.g., in classes and exams, would pose a dilemma for English language teachers. Such disapproval of China-English expressions is owing to the lack of cohesion and coherence in authentic discursal constructions, regarding both writing and speaking conventions. This explanation for her refusal of CE further indicates that native speakerism and Chinglish remain the predominating ideologies in the English educational context in China. Because native English is taken as the standardization and normalization, the English that deviates from these standardized norms is treated as an unacceptable expressive variety, e.g., Chinglish, particularly by English instructors. Another reason for Ms. Zhao’s pessimism is that the exam-based syllabus is a result of the ineradicably established examination culture in today’s China. Students cannot receive marks on the exam papers if they utilize much China English, as Ms. Zhao mentioned. In consequence, the mentality of “put exams first” reigns dominance among teachers, parents, and students (Pan & Block, 2011). Mr. Zhang also expresses concerns or anxieties

about communicativeness when speakers use China English, implying that "most learners of English will assume that the only meaningful goal is native-like pronunciation" (Walker, 2010, p. 61). Generally speaking, Chinese netizens' negative attitudes towards China English are concerned with native-speaker ideology, exam-based syllabus, and communicativeness. This kind of negative-attitude responses consists of two widely acknowledged agreements of English in the Chinese educational context: the ideologies of native speaker standards and the China English as Chinglish stigma (Pan, 2011; Xiong & Qian, 2012).

CONCLUSION

This study investigated Chinese netizens' attitudes and perceptions towards China English (CE) and probed into the reasons underlying their attitudinal judgments. Through analyzing their Danmus delivered in Bilibili revealing attitudes towards Ms. Jin Xing's English, the study has so far revealed that China English is a very discussable term encompassing diversified concerns and features from the perspectives of netizens.

The initial findings identified a high degree of positive evaluations of CE among Chinese netizens. As in Figure 3, the dominant influential factors include the participants' faith in fluency and confidence in using CE as a communicative medium to construct interactions. At the same time, for Chinese netizens, China English marks their bilingual identity as Chinese who can use English. Those netizens' positive perceptions are also attributed with a sense of ease when they speak English following Chinese-language modes (e.g., grammatical structure, lexical adaptations). Besides, some Chinese netizens have established an awareness of Global Englishes and English as a Lingua Franca. In fact, there has been an explosive growth in the number of English speakers in China, and this increased usage on a global level has resulted in innovations in its use as it is employed by speakers from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds and assumes distinct functions and forms in different contexts (e.g., CE used in China) (Liu et al., 2021; Zhang, 2021). Therefore, it is no longer relevant to associate English purely with native-speaking nations, rather, English is spoken by the global community today (Galloway & Rose, 2015).

Based on this, many Chinese netizens believe that CE is also acceptable as one of the English varieties with unique Chinese characteristics, which as well triggers their positive attitudes towards China English. On the other hand, it is also noted that some Chinese netizens, who are caught in native English norms and concerned about CE comprehensibility (communicative effectiveness) to the western world, hold apparent negative attitudes towards China English. In particular, most EFL teaching practices still consider native speaker English to be the goal of English learning and take native speaker English as standards and norms, resulting that CE, as a developing variety, has not yet been widely recognized by its speakers (Wang, 2015).

Figure 3. China English with relevant Qualities and Features
Note: ELF: English as a Lingua Franca

The research findings have certain implications for current investigations of language attitudes. Firstly, the findings show that Chinese English learners and users' language attitudes towards CE are not set in stone but changeable, which testifies that language attitudes are inherently prone to change (Dragojevic, 2017). In addition, the study of linguistic attitudes should also be done on a community-wide scale rather than being limited to very restricted or highly popular representative groups such as educational communities (Yan & Moody, 2010). In other words, more participants among the general public are needed in language attitudes investigations.

This study recommends that netizens should be served as the suitable representation of the general public and function as more valid data resources to reflect the general attitudes or perceptions. Instead of being merely employed in investigating language attitudes, they can be used as research subjects in other socio-cultural phenomena. Thirdly, Danmus, as a real-time comment channel that can reflect netizens' immediate attitudes, are suggested to be applied as a discourse-based approach to investigate future language attitudes, as a means of the methodological implication. Then, as most Chinese netizens focus on fluency and confidence when evaluating English speaking in China, more efforts and attention need to be attached to how to use English fluently and confidently in English teaching contexts, which is definitely beneficial to Chinese students to establish linguistic confidence to transition from perennial language learners to legitimate language users (Fang, 2017b).

Finally, we propose that discussing users and learners' attitudinal perceptions of a target language can be an effective pedagogical device. For instance, a classroom discussion of the evaluations of China English contributes to English language instructors to increase students' awareness of world Englishes and also help them perceive themselves as legitimate language users, thus to dispose of the pervasive problems of linguistic racism caused by the rigid native phantom and the Chinglish stigma.

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Appendix A Interview Excerpts

Participant 1: Mr. Feng Excerpt 1

R (Researcher): Do you think Ms. Jin is using China English and do you think it's acceptable to you?

Feng: Definitely, that's China English and I believe it's quite acceptable for me.

R: Well, could you please explain why you accept China English?

Feng: I am a foreign trade salesman, mainly in charge of the overseas department and I have to deal with people from different countries every day. So I can't expect everyone to be like the English listening test, right? hahaha. After all, we are Chinese, and English is a totally foreign language for us.

R: So you mean that we may meet different varieties of English in real communication and then what's the most important in using English in real communication from your point?

Feng: Well, personally speaking, I think confidence matters most because once you speak out and express your ideas, it's enough!

Participant 2: Mr. Zhang Excerpt 2

R: Do you think Ms. Jin is using China English? And could you explain why you doubt whether a foreigner could understand the Chinese accent and structure?

Zhang: From my point of view, it's China English. I remember once there was a customer from Canada and it was really hard for him to understand me because I speak English with a strong Chinese accent.

R: So do you think that China English is not a good choice when using English?

Zhang: Agree, we need to try to imitate Westerners but not in a Chinese way, it's really a trouble for communication.

R: You mean that we need to try to sound like a native speaker when speaking English? Why do you think so?

Zhang: Yes, at least trying to make it. I think if you speak English with a too heavy Chinese accent, you will be laughed at for being so vulgar.

Participant 3 Mrs. Zhao Excerpt 3

R: Do you think Ms. Jin is using China English? And as you mentioned that her grammar is not good, does that mean you can't accept this kind of China English?

Zhao: Sure, I don't like China English, and I totally can't accept China English.

R: Could you please explain why you don't like China English?

Zhao: I am a teacher and I always meet students using China English. Like "horse horse tiger tiger (which refers to the Chinese idiom meaning "careless"); I am read a book". All these mean zero marks in exams, which is really a headache for me.

R: Therefore, you mean that students' use China English is not suggested in English classes and exams?

Zhao: Yes, but not "suggest" but "forbid". Students mustn't use China English in exams because there will be zero marks for students if they use China English instead of British or American English in the textbook. What's more, if China English is used in English teaching, how can we give marks?

Participant 4: Miss Meng Excerpt 4

R: Do you think Ms. Jin's English is China English? Could you please explain why you say Ms. Jin's English makes you comfortable?

Meng: Emm, yes, it's China English. It's really fluent and I like Ms. Jin very much. The confidence on her face really moves me. She is my idol and role model!

R: That's to say, do you think China English is acceptable for you? Do you like China English?

Meng: Yes, I like China English because I think it's much easier for me to learn and understand. Like when writing English sentences, I prefer to use Chinese grammar.

R: All right, do you think learning British English is our final goal in English acquisition?

Meng: Well, according to textbooks, probably it is, I don't know. But I am Chinese, speaking China English can show my Chinese nationality, it's emm, how to say, good.

Scrutinizing Register Realization in Facebook Trading Group

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Abstract

This study aims at scrutinizing the register patterns used by the sellers in promoting their goods in the popular Facebook trading group used by people in Ngabang, West Borneo, "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*". The group is an ambient representation of language variation used in West Borneo. The register analysis covers the field, tenor, and mode of the discourse. The data analysis encompasses domain, taxonomy, componential, and cultural theme analysis modified by Santosa (2017). The domain covers the kinds of goods being sold. The taxonomy analysis is the three metafunctions in the SFL framework. The combined domain and taxonomy in the componential analysis figure out the register patterns in the group. The findings reveal that in the field of discourse, the posted clauses are dominated by the use of the material process, relational identification, and relational attributive process. The material process reflects the experiential meaning of the current activities. Meanwhile, the information of the goods realizes relational identification and relational attributive processes. With respect to the tenor of discourse, there is a tendency for the sellers to use declarative clauses which reflect equal status between the sellers and the customers by considering the minimal social distance. Furthermore, in the mode of discourse, the unmarked topical theme reflects as the majority of the ellipsis subject referring to the sellers. The study implies the language used in digital trading should take into account the participants, the relationship among the participants, and the media used to persuade their target market.

Keywords: facebook trading group, online shop, register, systemic functional linguistics

INTRODUCTION

Facebook changes the way people sell their goods. Its ability to provide information, personal text, and photo as the media richness is the vividness of online content (Coyle & Thorson, 2001; Van Der Heide et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2010). A good understanding of the product and the ability to simplify sophisticated functional and technical terms of the offered products are outstanding selling skills that online sellers must have to provide similar-understandable information within their posts between the sellers and the potential consumers. The ability to provide rich information using simple language may support the effectiveness of the sellers' posts. To achieve effective selling, the sellers should prioritize caring about creating successful posts when offering their goods. However, it is not an ability that every seller has. The members of the Facebook trading group are known to vary in age, gender, goods expertise, and educational levels. Facebook posts in Facebook trading groups display a variety of language used by the members of the groups as they engage in communication and business dealings with one another. Given this variability, the sellers must be able to identify the participants they are interacting with, the nature of their interactions with customers, and the appropriate terminology to use when posting on Facebook. In online selling, the use of language is one factor that influences the sale (Tabpawan, 2022). A register viewpoint makes it simple to see the language dimension used in a particular community. The chosen register is meant to make communication between the members of some specific groups easier (Nurani et al., 2014).

The present study investigates a Facebook trading group named "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*". This Facebook group is popularly used by people in Ngabang, Landak Regency, West Borneo. It has 27.400.000 members from several districts around the Landak region and 110-120 average daily posts. The group consists of various sellers depending on the offered goods such as electronics, vehicles, food and beverage, and fashion. Each seller employs a different register covered by mixed language, English and Indonesian (Agung et al., 2021) which makes this group worth scrutinizing.

In the context of Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL), register is defined as the configuration of semantic resources that the member of the

culture associates with a situation type (Halliday, 1978). It is the meaning potential that is accessible in a given social context. In this case, the register refers to the linguistic functional variation known as language style. As a language variation viewed from the use, register is affected by the context of the situation and also the linguistic features realized in the text.

Halliday & Hasan (1989) defined register as a variety according to its use including three parameters of the context of the situation in which it is used. Those parameters cover field, tenor, and mode of discourse. The first parameter, the field of discourse refers to what is happening, to the nature of the social action that is taking place: in what situation the participants are engaged in, and in which language figures as some essential components (Halliday & Hasan, 1989). Field is the realization of ideational metafunction which analyzes clauses and discourse. At the clause level, the analysis goes to transitivity, a group of verbs, and a group of nouns. Meanwhile, at the discourse level, the analysis covers reference chains, lexical strings, and activity order (Wiratno, 2018).

The second parameter, tenor of discourse refers to what kinds of role relationships are being obtained among the participants, including permanent and temporary relationships in which they are involved (Halliday & Hasan, 1989). Tenor can be viewed through the negotiation relationship among the language users involved in the text. Tenor is the realization of interpersonal metafunction involving three kinds of relationship, namely status, contact, and affect (Wiratno, 2018). Status is the position of each participant in the discourse, whether they are in an equal position or not. Contact reveals the intimacy of the relationship between participants such as whether the participants are in face-to-face, indirect, or one/two ways communication. Affect relates to the emotional relationship among the participants.

Third, mode of discourse refers to what part the language is playing, and what the participants are expecting the language to do for them in that situation: the symbolic organization of the text, the status that it has, including the channel and the rhetorical mode (Halliday & Hasan, 1989). Mode is the realization of a textual metafunction. To reveal the mode of the discourse in the text, it can be seen through kinds of moods, theme realization,

lexis use, the complexity of the clause, and the interdependency of clause relationship (Wiratno, 2018).

Studies of registers on online trading have been conducted by some researchers (Agung et al., 2021; Alfi, 2013; Lubis et al., 2016; Wardana, 2013). The studies of register on Facebook trading reveal the domination of verb register form in the sellers' posts (Agung et al., 2021; Alfi, 2013; Lubis et al., 2016). Moreover, the registers are formed by the mixed language (English and Indonesian). The register functions are mostly in the form of offering and consultative. Their studies employed a sociolinguistics perspective to depict register realization. These studies can identify the different linguistic forms of register used in Facebook's online buying and selling. However, they are unable to explain how clauses are produced within the activity of promoting goods and services on Facebook. The depiction of mixed-language use to the traits of clauses in the sellers' posts throughout their promotions is a myriad of analyses for upcoming research. Those earlier research, in contrast to this one, were not designed to capture the phenomenon of register utilized by the sellers, particularly about its classification of the supplied commodities. Online sellers on Facebook also come from a variety of social backgrounds. Since each seller probably uses their technical jargon, there are many different terms. Furthermore, those studies have not yet taken into account how well-developed interpersonal relationships between the sellers and the customers lead to successful selling.

Meanwhile, Wardana (2013) scrutinized register realization in action figure trading on Kaskus online trading forum using the SFL approach. The study reveals there are 10 ordinary terms and 4 uncommon terms. The meaning of the terms should be viewed through field, tenor, and mode dimensions. Additionally, the language used in the forum is informal which enables sellers and customers to build a close relationship. Despite this research was able to use SFL views to disclose a three-dimensional register, it is still relatively limited in terms of the language used for buying and selling in online forums in Kaskus. The peculiarities of the creation of clauses in online forums for buying and selling in Kaskus are not yet covered by this research.

According to a review of earlier research, a register study is required to reveal the proliferation of clauses in sellers' Facebook posts in Indonesia. Facebook users in Indonesia are diverse therefore the sellers have to adjust and simplify the use of promotional language to enhance a simpler understanding of the Facebook users when reading the sellers' posts. In addition, interpersonal relationship is a part of the priority of analysis in online buying and selling on Facebook to take a holistic picture of registers in buying and selling on Facebook. This study offers an analysis of register from an SFL perspective. It enables to reveal the characteristics of clauses in the sellers' posts in the online trading group on Facebook. Furthermore, the register realization from three dimensions in field, tenor, and mode based on the offered goods is another priority. A register study is necessary to involve the context of the situation yet where its immanent register lies in the context of situation level, one level higher than language, and one level lower than genre in the context of culture field (Martin, 1992; Wiratno, 2018).

Given that case, the context of the situation is supposedly circumscribed in the kinds of the offered goods. Each seller may have a different register for promoting them. Giving domain classification to the kinds of goods being sold offers a new paradigm to the register study. It also depicts the patterns of register in online trading within Facebook Group. Moreover, to the best of our knowledge, the register study employing SFL approach on local Facebook online trading in Indonesia is very limited. This study is expected to provide new insight into register in SFL which reveals linguistic phenomena in the context of online buying and selling of the "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook group in West Borneo. Hence, the present study attempts to answer the gap by answering the following questions:

1. What are the language characteristics of the sellers in the "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook Trading Group?
2. What is the register realization covering field, tenor, and mode in each domain of the sellers of the "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook Trading Group?

RESEARCH METHOD

This qualitative study employs Systemic Functional Linguistics to depict the register realization. It describes the analysis based on the Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) framework developed by Halliday & Hasan (1989) covering three parameters, namely field, tenor, and mode of the discourse. The field of discourse includes experiential meaning (experiential). This involves transitivity analysis which realizes experiential meaning, namely process, participant, and circumstance (Santosa, 2003). The tenor of discourse involves interpersonal meaning. Tenor relates to three interpersonal relations, namely status, contact, and affect (Santosa, 2003; Wiratno, 2018). The mode of discourse is realized through textual meaning. This analysis is realized in the kinds of MOOD and theme.

The data of this study is the clauses derived from the sellers' posts in the "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook trading group in West Borneo that realized the register of online trading limited to the postings from January 2021 to December 2021. The variety of the sellers and the prevalence of the mixed language are the reasons for choosing this group. The data were analyzed by domain, taxonomy, componential analysis, and cultural theme (Spradely, 1980; Miles & Huberman, 1994; modified by Santosa (2017) whereas the domain covers the kinds of the offered goods; the taxonomy analysis is the three metafunctions in the SFL framework. The domain analysis identified the usage context (Santosa et al., 2021). The domain and taxonomy were combined in the componential analysis. It portrays the register patterns in the "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook trading group. The componential analysis investigates the relationships between the data categories in the taxonomy and the context of the data in the domain. Theoretical analysis is employed to depict the contextual relations among the categories in the cultural theme.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

As explained above, the register of the discourse can be obtained through the three parameters: field, tenor, and mode of the discourse. Field of the discourse is realized through experiential meaning. The experiential meaning can be revealed through transitivity analysis involving the lexico-grammatical analysis of the clauses. Tenor of the discourse is realized through

interpersonal meaning. The interpersonal meaning has its grammar structure called MOOD system and MOOD structure. Mode of the discourse is the projection of textual meaning. It is oriented to the medium of communication in terms of spoken and written language. However, the influence of the local language on the use of Bahasa Indonesia in promotion dominates the data of the study. Hence, the description of the characteristic of the data is drawn as follow.

Characteristics of the data

Fifty posts obtained from the "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook trading group from May to July 2021 are considered as the data of the study. As a member of the group, we have observed and found out that there are four kinds of goods offered in the group, namely vehicle, food and beverage (F&B), electronic, and fashion. These goods are considered as the domain of the analysis. First is the analysis of the pattern of the clauses. The analysis divulges the partiality of using a simple-clause ellipsis in the subject, predicate, or complement. The sellers are keen on omitting the subject of the clause. Table 1 describes the pattern of the clauses of the posts.

Table 1.

Post with ellipsis

No	Kinds of goods	Ellipsis (in %)		
		Subject	Predicate	Complement
1.	Vehicle	9.8	12.0	4.3
2.	F&B	6.5	12.0	-
3.	Electronic	35.7	11.0	6.5
4.	Fashion	-	2.2	-

According to the offered goods, each seller uses a different pattern of clauses. Electronic sellers mostly omit subjects in their clauses. They initiate the predicate in their clauses. For instance:

- [1] *Jual hp Vivo v19 harga 1,800 nego kondisi hp seperti di poto minat Chet*
(Selling Vivo V19 cellphone-price 1,800- negotiable-cellphone's condition as seen in the picture-interested kindly chat)

Ø	<i>jual</i>	<i>hp Vivo v19</i>	<i>harga 1,800 nego [kondisi hp seperti di poto minat Chet]</i>
S	P	O	Complement

Vehicle, F&B, and fashion sellers tend to omit the predicate of the clause in their posts. For instance,

[2] *Soul gt.2014. Surat lengkap, tangan pertama.*

(Soul GT 2014 (has) complete vehicle registration certificate, first-hand)

∅	[menjual]	<i>Soul gt.2014</i>	<i>[dengan] Surat lgkp, tangan pertama</i>
S	P	P	Complement

[3] *1 buah 8000 besar2 ya*

(The (price of each) big fruit (is) 8000)

<i>[harga] 1 buah</i>	∅ <i>[adalah]</i>	<i>8000 besar2 ya</i>
S	F	Complement

[4] *Ready sepatu cewek ukuran 38 bahan karet, lentur, ringan, kuat.*

(Ready, women shoes size 38, material rubber, light, and solid)

<i>[it]</i>	<i>[is] ready</i>	<i>sepatu cewek</i>	<i>[dengan] ukuran 38 bahan karet, lentur, ringan, kuat</i>
S	F/P	Complement	Circumstances

Analyzing the characteristics of the data, particularly on the language use reveals that the sellers tend to simplify the clauses by omitting subject or predicator/finite. They merely focus on the complement referring to the goods, price, and quality.

Field of discourse

The description of field of discourse in the "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook group reflects the experiential process derived from transitivity analysis covering process, participant, and circumstance. As Matthiessen (2019) said that register relates to what is happening to the nature of the social action that is taking place; what the participants are engaged in, in which the language figures some essential components. The transitivity analysis of the process also involves material, mental, relational identification, and relational attribution. Its analysis of participants covers the actors or phenomena of the process. Meanwhile, circumstance includes

location, manner, thing, and time. Table 2 presents the result of transitivity analysis in experiential meaning.

Table 2.

The frequency of transitivity analysis in experiential meaning

No	Kinds of goods	Experiential Meaning (in %)							
		MEN	MAT	IDT	ATT	Circumstance			
						LOC	MAN	THI	TIM
1	Vehicle	-	12,12	2,02	11,11	15,38	-	-	-
2	F&B	5,05	4,04	11,11	8,08	-	-	15,38	8
3	Electronic	-	19,19	4,04	18,18	23,08	23	11,54	-
4	Fashion	-	1,01	1,01	3,03	-	-	3,85	-

The transitivity analysis reveals that the material process is dominated by the clauses which are used by the sellers of Vehicle and Electronic. An example of a material process can be seen below.

- [5] *Jual/ tukar-tambah Vivo y81.*
(sell/trade-ins Vivo Y81 cellphone)

Ø	<i>Jual/ tukar-tambah</i>	<i>Vivo y81</i>
Actor	Material (doing) process	Goal

The clause *Jual/ tukar-tambah Vivo Y81* is *jual /tukar-tambah* (sell/ trade-ins) considered as a material process. It is because the verb shows the process of doing something that is selling/ trading the cellular phone Vivo Y81. The actor of this process is the ellipsis. Yet, it refers to the seller itself.

Reviewing the promotion activities posted by the sellers, the study finds that most of them realize the material process. It is indicated by the terms which are used by the sellers such as *jual* (sell), *tukar-tambah* (trade-ins), *melayani* (serve), *pesan* (order), etc, and reflect the material doing the process. The goal of the process is the offered goods.

Meanwhile, the trend in Food & beverage sellers is to use a relational identification process in their clauses. It is accustomed to establish identity to something. The characteristics of its participant are token and value. The occurrence of the identification process of F&B posts was 11.11%. The example can be seen below.

- [6] *Gandaria masak 20.000/ bungkus*
 (The [price of] ripe Gandaria fruit is 20K/Pack)

(Harga) Gandaria masak	∅ [adalah]	20.000/ bungkus
Token	Process	Value

The finite *[adalah]* (is) can be categorized as a relational identifying process. That finite relates to "the process of being" to establish value. Its process is realized by an identity *[adalah]* (is) *20.000/ bungkus*. The clause of *Gandaria masak 20.000/ bungkus* signifies that the F&B seller wants to give information that the price of the ripe *Gandaria* is 20K rupiahs per pack. The finite *[adalah]* (is) belongs to the relational identifying since it substantiates a value of *20.000/ bungkus* as the identity to the token *Gandaria masak*.

The data also shows that all of the sellers operate attributive processes in their clauses. Its frequency is 18.18% in the electronic posts, 11.11% in the vehicle posts, 8.08% in the F&B posts, and 3.03% in the fashion posts. The relational attributive process realizes a quality to something "the process of being". The characteristics of its participant are carrier and attribute. The attribute is typically an indefinite nominal group or nominal group with an adjective as the head. An example of an attributive process can be seen below.

- [7] *Motor kami noken, kk (Motor [yang] kami [jual] tidak ada kendala, kakak!)*
 (The motorcycle [we offer] has no mechanical problem)

Motor [yang kami] jual]	tidak ada kendala	kakak
Carrier	Attributive process	

Data [7] reveals finite/predicator *tidak ada kendala* as a relational attributive process since it indicates "the process of being" to assign a quality to something. Its process is realized by the quality of the motorcycle with no mechanical problems. Thus, *the motorcycle* is the carrier of this attributive process. In short, the clauses that use relational identification and attributive process conceive that the sellers want to give value to the promoted goods.

In the "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook group, mental processes are found in fourth place and come out with a percentage of 5.05 appearing in F&B posts. Mental processes involve the senses for instance feeling, thinking, perceiving, etc. The mental process consists of three kinds, namely affective (feeling), cognitive (thinking), and perceptive (perceiving through the five senses).

- [8] *Pelanggan2 saya suka dengan Ayam Gepreknya.*
(My customers like the mashed chicken)

<i>Pelanggan2 saya</i>	suka	<i>dengan Ayam Gepreknya</i>
Senser	Process	Phenomenon

The verb *suka* (like) belongs to the mental process in the subcategory of affective (Santosa, 2003; Wiratno, 2018) since the sensing process is reflected through the feeling "like" the (smashed chicken) *ayam geprek* being sold. The characteristics of its participants are recognized as senser and phenomenon. In this case, the senser is realized by *Pelanggan-pelanggan saya* (my customers). It acts as the subject of the clause. Meanwhile, *dengan ayam geprek* (the smashed chicken) acts as a phenomenon. By using a mental process, the seller wants to tell that the customers have the same feeling as them about the food being sold.

It is done by delivering strong evidence, the F&B sellers tend to use the customers' testimony. Showing the same feeling and perception toward the taste of the promoted food is considered important. The promotion activities also embrace the circumstance (location of the online shops), manner (negotiable price), thing (the condition of the goods), and time of the delivery service.

Tenor of discourse

The tenor of discourse reflects the interpersonal relationship between the sellers and the customers. The analysis steps in three aspects namely status, affect, and contact (Wiratno, 2018). The status reflects the intimate relationship between the sellers and the customers. The affect relates to the emotional point of view or the participant's judgment (Santosa, 2003; Wiratno, 2018). It means that affect refers to the sellers' justification of the

promoted product to the customer candidates. Meanwhile, the contact is looking for the familiarity of the language used between the participants. It involves the signature of the relationship whether it is one- or two-way communication, direct or indirect communication, and how close the relationship is.

The findings disclose the sellers' clauses are dominated by the interaction of giving information. Figure 1 illustrates the composition of interpersonal interaction of the sellers' clauses.

Figure 1. Mood structure analysis

Reviewing, the data, the sellers exploit giving information clauses largely in their postings. They describe their goods and services to provide information catchy information to the Facebook group visitors. Meanwhile, there are 7% of the sellers' clauses ask for service such as asking for the buyer's identity for the delivery kinds of stuff. The interpersonal interaction is best portrayed in the MOOD system analysis. The data divulges that indicative declarative clauses dominate the sellers' postings. They are presented in various goods. In addition, the imperative clauses are also presented in F&B, electronic, and fashion domains with lower frequency. Table 3 below shows the MOOD analysis.

Table 3.
The frequency of MOOD system analysis

No	Kinds of goods	Interpersonal Meaning (in %)	
		Indicative declarative	Imperative
1.	Vehicle	24.49	0
2.	F&B	22.45	1.02
3.	Electronic	42.86	4.08
4.	Fashion	3.06	2.04

Table 3 manifests the declarative clause becomes the majority in the "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook Group. The identification of declarative clauses can be seen from the position of the subject that precedes the predicator or finite. Declarative clauses are beneficial to provide information on the promoted goods to the customer candidates. The finding indicates that the degree of relationship between sellers and customers is equal. An example of the declarative clause is as follows.

- [9] *Vivo Y12i mulus ori 1,400 nego tipis*
(Vivo T12i flawless original, price 1,400, negotiable)

(<i>kondisi/condition</i>) Vivo Y12i	∅ [<i>adalah</i>]	<i>mulus ori 1,400 nego tipis</i>
S	F	Complement
Mood	Residue	

Indicative: declarative; giving information

Meanwhile, the imperative clauses can also be found on the sellers' posts in F&B, electronic, and fashion. Imperative clauses are identified from the position of predicator or finite that precedes the subject. They are used by sellers for particular reasons. First, F&B sellers utilize imperative clauses to ask the customer candidates to list their names in the Pre-Order list.

- [10] *Tulis nama dan alamat untuk PO*
(Write your name and address for Pre Order)

<i>Tulis</i>	<i>nama dan alamat (anda)</i>	<i>untuk PO</i>
Predicator	Subject	Complement
Mood		Residue

Second, some electronic and fashion sellers utilize it to ask the customer candidates to visit their offline shops for further transactions such as quality checking or sampling.

- [11] *Cek kondisi barang, datang saja ke Toko Anshana di Jalan Tungkul nomor 105*
 (Kindly visit Anshana shop at Tungkul street number 105 to check the condition of the good)

<i>Cek (kondisi barang), datang saja</i>	<i>ke Toko Anshana di Jalan Tungkul nomor 105</i>
Predicator	Complement
Mood	Residue

As the predicator precede the subject or complement, it indicates that the sellers bespeak the buyer to do something. They lead and attempt to provide the opportunity for the buyer candidates to check the quality of the goods to prevent complaining. The imperative clauses help the sellers to persuade buyer candidates to visit their shop and provide face-to-face transactions are excluded.

Furthermore, the next aspect to be considered is the affect. Considering the frequent use of declarative clauses, it denotes that the sellers put themselves as part of the customers' social life. Providing a detailed description of the promoted products is for the sake of building product value. The agentive role is said to be equal and the social role is considered non-hierarchic. Viewing the aspect of contact, the use of familiar terms of trading is customer friendly and more understandable for instance *jual/ tukar-tambah, pre-order, minat, chat, inbox, pengantaran*, etc. The minimal frequency of the appearance of the technical terms implies that the social distance between participants is considered minimal.

Mode of discourse

Martin (1992) in Santosa (2003) states that mode covers two variables namely channel and media. Channel relates to language use; it tends to be spoken or written language. Meanwhile, media refers to the proportion of the language used in certain media. Those variables are realized in the textual

theme of the clause. In the "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook group, the textual theme is mostly expressed by unmarked topical themes. Table 4 shows the percentage of the realized textual meaning in the group.

Table 4.

The percentage of textual meaning

No	Kinds of goods	Textual Meaning (in %)	
		Marked topical theme	Unmarked topical theme
1.	Vehicle		24.49
2.	F&B	1	22.45
3.	Electronic		46.94
4.	Fashion		5.10

The unmarked topical themes are realized through the use of the subject ellipsis "I" which appears in the "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook group that refers to the sellers. The existence of unmarked topical themes mirrors the position of the actors (sellers) as the doer of promotion activity. The channel variable can be analyzed through the pattern of the clauses. Most of the clauses are complex clause-type paratactic. The indication is obvious in the use of elaborative conjunction comma (,) in the clause (Santosa, 2003). The function of complex clause-type paratactic tacks on the information especially the specification of the promoted goods. Since the clauses are mostly omitted either in the subject or predicate, it signifies that the language form in the group tends to be spoken text with two ways of communication (Eggin, 2004; Pratiwi, 2016). It gives a significant result to the number of followers of Ngabang *Jual-Beli*. Various social backgrounds of the group's members can easily understand the posted promotion by the sellers. With respect to the language, Ramirez-Asis et al. (2021) noted that promoting products on Facebook needs both interactive language and real-time connectivity to keep in touch with the customers. Hence, the usage of spoken text channels is appropriate in social media.

Discussion

The study demonstrates that the language characteristic of "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" posts represents the usage of simple clauses. It is indicated by the omission of the subject or predicator (finite) for the sake of effective

promotion by exposing the complement referring to the goods, price, and quality. The result of the study corroborates Lubis et al. (2016) and (Wardana, 2013) that the role of language in promotion is oriented to persuade people to buy goods by applying effective and efficient words.

Concerning the field of the discourse, the results reveal that the sellers frequently use relational and material processes to shape their promotion. It is because buying and selling are the prime activities in such a group. Sellers use various terms of language as a medium by writing the word “*jual*” (sell), “*tukar-tambah*” (trade-in), and so on. This study confirms that promotion posting involves large numbers of verbs (Alfi, 2013). The social setting and purpose of the interaction are referred to as the field. The social setting of the register occurs when the sellers provide additional information about the purchasing and trading system, the merchandise, and its specifications. The material process helps the sellers convey the process of doing which is realized through verbs showing physical activity (Wiratno, 2018). Additionally, the relational process helps the sellers to describe the offered product (ibid.).

For the tenor of the discourse, the domination of proposition clauses contributes to the equality relationship between the seller and the potential buyers. The existence of a declarative clause in most of the seller's clauses indicates that the sellers pose their selves in an equal position with the buyer. This is in line with the study from Agung et al. (2021) and (Wardana, 2013) revealing that the social distance between seller and buyer in trading tends to be minimal. The findings of Pratiwi's (2016) study, which asserted that there is less interaction between advertisers and their target consumers in mass media commercials are in conflict with this. The assumption that there is an intense interaction between buyers and sellers in social media trading is supported by the study's outcome comparison. The sellers attempt to polish their postings as interactive as possible by eliminating the distance.

The result of mode of the discourse analysis reveals that the sellers tend to use spoken text in their promotion activity to give informative content. It can be seen through the form of two-way communication, the existence of many ellipses clauses, and more dominant complex clauses (Santosa, 2003). Moreover, spoken text which is appropriately used in social media such as

Facebook is proven successful in attaining customer response (Chetioui et al., 2021). In line with this, "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook group has massive followers and active members. They have various social statuses and educational backgrounds, so simple language use is effective. The use of language is the art of selling in advertising to persuade consumers to change their concepts and attitudes which evokes more interest in the offered posts (Thongchuay & Srinuanpam, 2019). This strategy is an effective implementation to be adopted in the level of post advertising, namely from "push advertising" to "trust advertising" which leads to the successful selling of the sellers (Dehghani & Tumer, 2015).

CONCLUSION

Register realization in the "Ngabang *Jual-Beli*" Facebook group can be magnified through its variables namely: field, mode, and tenor of discourse. The field of discourse presents the experiential discourse covers the process involving the clauses, participants, and circumstances. The material process is the most dominant process realized in the sellers' clauses. In this case, the majority of electronic sellers use it in their posts. It signifies the involvement of physical activity in selling and trading. Furthermore, relational identification and attributive process are used by the seller to describe their promoted goods. The circumstance of the process involves the circumstance of location, thing, manner, and time. The tenor of discourse reveals that the relationship between the seller and the customer candidates is agentive or social roles. Their status is equal and social distance is minimal. With respect to the mode of discourse, the unmarked topical theme is the majority theme that is used by the sellers. The unmarked topical theme is realized through the ellipsis subject "I" referring to the seller. In addition, the promotion texts are the form of spoken-written text with two ways of communication. This implication of this research actualizes the need for language use in the context of marketing on social media, especially Facebook. Informative, effective, and efficient are the characteristics of that needs. The Sellers have to notice their language use and its affinity with what the participants are doing (field), the relationship among the participants (tenor), and the suitability of form and meaning towards the choice of the media (mode). Despite the present study

could reveal the pattern of the register in the online trading group, there is a limitation regarding the time of the study. The source of data has no various patterns since the limitation of the focus is only on the seller and buyer's interaction without comparing to the other groups. If similar research is conducted within a larger group for a longer duration, the interaction between seller and customer candidates in the comment box will gain more interesting topics and findings for future study.

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